

Rhythm, Meter, Tempo, and Beat:

A Cross-Cultural Model of the Evolution of Human Musical Timing with Provisional Timeline.

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Supplemental files:

1) Audio examples

2) Video examples

3) Appendix. The integralist school of music analysis in the USSR. Brief description and bibliography.

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Abstract

Human music is distinguished from language and animal calls by its sophisticated temporal organization. The key role in it belongs to rhythm. However, studying rhythm is complicated by lack of clarity in how exactly rhythm relates to other means of temporal organization: meter, tempo, beat, tactus, foot, pulse, divisions, etc. This paper reviews the data from music theory, history, ethnomusicology (including little-known sources), psychoacoustics, versification, historical linguistics, prosody, orchesography, organology, archaeology, and anthropology to clarify the terminology for cross-cultural study of musical timing and summarizes what is known about it. Rhythm, meter, and tempo are identified as the autonomous nearly-universal aspects of music expression, interconnected by their mutual dependence on beat. Musical traditions employ different types of “beat”: unitary, binary, foot-based, syllable-based, breath-based, instrumental-technique-based, and body-motion-based. Each of them generates its own typology of meter and tempo through the ongoing genre application within a community of music-users. Tracking historical changes in important genres through their structural and semantic functionality makes it possible to identify and plot metrical and tempo typologies on a timeline in relation to the landmark prehistoric and historic events. The timeline proposed here is a probing step towards reconstruction of the general evolution of rhythm. Musical examples are provided.

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Introduction

Recent research in music cognition, psychoacoustics, and evolutionary theory has significantly advanced our understanding of rhythm and beat perception and their possible origins (Bowling et al., 2013; Brown, 2022; Háden et al., 2024; Iversen, 2016; Jacoby & McDermott, 2017; Jones, 2019; Kim & Schachner, 2023; Kotz et al., 2018; Larsson & Falk, 2025; London, 2012; Madison et al., 2017; Patel, 2014; Ravignani, 2014; Snyder et al., 2024). These advances include more detailed models of sensorimotor entrainment, the possible contribution of bipedal locomotion to beat induction, the role of caregiver–infant rhythmic interaction, and the social regularization of temporal patterns in collective behavior. Sophisticated musical timing—including rhythm, meter, tempo, and beat organization—distinguishes human music from verbal and animal communication. Yet while typologies of pitch organization are widely recognized across disciplines, typologies of temporal organization remain largely confined to specialized musicological traditions and are insufficiently integrated into cross-cultural and cognitive models of musical evolution.

Historical and comparative musicologies look into musical structures in conjunction with where, when, and how they were/are used. This enables tracking of historical and geographical changes. However, many empirical studies have relied on analytical categories derived largely from Western pedagogical theory—e.g., strong/weak beat hierarchies, simple-versus-compound meter, and 4/4-based metrical grids—as if these provided a neutral vocabulary for musical rhythm in general (Clayton, 1996; Haumann et al., 2018; Jacoby et al., 2020; Matthews et al., 2026). Problems arise when scholars adopt the theoretical concepts specific to Western art music from the common-practice era as universally applicable to and representative of all forms of human music-making.

We do need those analytical, descriptive, and categorizing tools created by Western music theorists that are applicable to non-Western music. Without such tools we cannot trace cross-cultural and historical transformations of specific structures. But we should see where these tools are unsuitable—where the object of

study abides by principles radically different from those that necessitated creation of these tools. To avoid anachronistic mismatches (e.g., analyzing modal music by the rules of Western tonality), we should implement earlier Western tools (e.g., modal theory). In a nutshell, Western music theory enables etic evaluations (synchronic and diachronic), but itself constitutes an emic product of Western culture—therefore, requiring careful matching of its concepts to those of the studied culture to avoid mis-labeling. Unfortunately, accurate emic-etic “translation” of temporal structures is very difficult. The multifactorial nature of meter and its reliance on attention, guided by expectations and therefore relying on experience and knowledge, make the study of rhythm inherently dependent on cultural conventions.

The very concepts of rhythm, meter, and tempo are often confused even by professional music theorists unfamiliar with the history of versification and practices of folk lyric/epic poetry. Theories of rhythm, meter, and tempo have passed through drastic historical transformations in different cultures, complicating their etic labeling (e.g., application of the notion of “beat”). Moreover, rhythm, meter, and tempo share the same perceptual qualia: each of them can appear fast/slow, simple/complex, fixed/flexible, new/same, interrupted/continuous, proportional/disproportional, and salient in projecting specific expressions. To complicate things further, all three influence one another, and the contribution of each is hard to isolate. One solution is to identify rhythmic, metrical, and tempo structures in relation to their semantic functionality. Practically, this entails connecting patterns of rhythm, meter, and tempo to specific genres. This is especially important for experimental research, where scholars routinely use *unmusical* stimuli (clicks, pure tones) without semantic context to test *musical* perception. Their findings often have little connection to actual uses of music.

The temporal organization of human music rests on biological foundations that predate any particular cultural tradition. Research on sensorimotor synchronization has demonstrated that the capacity for entrainment to an external periodic pulse is deeply rooted in human neurobiology (Repp, 2005; Repp & Su, 2013). Bipedal locomotion provides a pervasive periodic motor pattern whose influence on rhythmic cognition has been widely discussed (Todd et al., 2007; Todd & Lee, 2015). Caregiver–infant interaction involves rhythmic vocalizations and rocking that may scaffold early musical timing abilities (Malloch & Trevarthen, 2009; Trehub, 2003). The gradual audiomotor evolution hypothesis proposes that the tight coupling between auditory and motor systems enabling beat-based timing evolved incrementally in the hominin lineage (Honing et al., 2018; Merchant et al., 2015). These biological substrates constrain and enable the cultural elaboration of rhythmic structures examined in the present article.

Empirical work on novice and cross-cultural listeners reinforces this layering of biological substrate and cultural shaping. Infants as young as 6–12 months discriminate meters more readily in the metrical framework of their own culture than in unfamiliar ones (Hannon & Trehub, 2005). Musical training sharpens sensitivity to metric deviations and to fine rhythmic categories (Acevedo et al., 2014; Honing et al., 2018; Smith, 1997), and cross-cultural comparisons show that listeners raised in different metrical traditions form different rhythmic priors—Western listeners tend to regularize Balkan additive meters toward isochrony, while Balkan listeners do not (Cameron et al., 2015; Jacoby et al., 2024). These findings are consistent with the present argument: the capacity for beat induction is biologically grounded, but the specific metrical prototypes, their privileged beat levels, and the boundaries of “expected” versus “deviant” are learned from exposure to a particular tradition.

The cross-cultural comparison of musical timing systems undertaken here is informed by cultural-evolution theory, in particular the distinction between content bias (the intrinsic attractiveness or learnability of a cultural variant) and context bias (the social circumstances of transmission), and the complementary processes of faithful transmission and creative transformation (Boyd & Richerson, 2024; Mesoudi, 2023).

Working Definitions, The Roadmap of This Article, and Its Limitations

Before proceeding to the substantive analysis, it is useful to establish provisional definitions for the core concepts that organize this discussion.

Music: In this article, “music” is treated operationally as culturally recognized sonic practice organized for expressive, coordinative, or genre-specific use. The present discussion does not attempt a general theory of the boundary between music and speech (for such a treatment, see Nikolsky & Benítez-Burraco, 2024, which proposes a working definition of music); it is limited to the temporal organization of practices treated as musical within their historical and cultural contexts.

Beat: A regularly or quasi-regularly recurring temporal reference point that listeners tend to infer from the musical surface and against which durations are estimated. Beat takes multiple forms across cultures, which are examined in detail below.

Rhythm: The pattern of durational contrasts and temporal groupings formed by successive sounds within a musical passage.

Meter: The organization of beats into recurrent grouping patterns that establish a framework of temporal expectation.

Tempo: The characteristic pace at which the underlying musical pulse unfolds.

Tactus: A specific, historically Western concept referring to one privileged beat level within a metrical framework, typically the level most readily tracked in score-based coordination.

These working definitions operate at a preliminary level; they are refined and deepened throughout the sections that follow. The following figure illustrates how the core concepts of this paper relate to each other.

Figure-1. The dimensions of musical temporal organization. The diagram shows the relations between rhythm, tempo, meter, beat, and tactus, and the contextual inputs that shape both the beat typology and its metrical realization. Arrows indicate the direction of influence. Gray ellipses and arrow illustrate the semiosis.

Two terms central to this approach require clarification. *Expression*, as used here, refers not to the individual performer's subjective interpretation but to the characteristic affective-communicative quality that a musical structure projects within a given genre—the recognized quality that competent users of that genre consistently perceive. A lament, for instance, carries a characteristic mournfulness. This generic expression emerges not from the performer alone but from the accumulated conventions of how a structure is characteristically articulated, accented, and used within a tradition.

Semantic functionality refers to the capacity of rhythm, meter, and tempo patterns to convey recognizable meaning within a culturally shared genre system. Specific metrical or rhythmic configurations become associated through prolonged communal use with particular functions, affects, or social contexts. Understanding these associations is crucial for analyzing why the same notated pattern can project entirely different meanings depending on its genre context and performance tradition.

I use the term *musical motion* to refer to the overall mode of kinetic unfolding perceived in performance: the integrated impression arising from the interaction of tempo, meter, rhythmic patterns, melodic gestures, articulation, texture, and harmonic rhythm. This performance-oriented concept has a long history in French, Italian, and Russian music literature, where the cognate terms (*mouvement*, *movimento*, *dvizhenie*) denote not a structural unit of a composition but the perceived quality of its temporal flow.

This article focuses on the structural and semantic analysis of rhythm, meter, and beat across cultures and historical periods. It does not address the neurophysiology of meter perception, the paleoneurology of rhythm processing, the musilanguage hypothesis, or the auditory capacities of non-human primates. These are important and active areas of research (readers interested in such topics should consult Brown, 2017; Kotz et al., 2018; Nikolsky & Benítez-Burraco, 2024; Patel, 2014).

Two questions guide this article. First, what cross-culturally valid definitions of rhythm, meter, tempo, and beat can serve as common analytical tools across diverse musical traditions? Second, what does the evolutionary timeline for the temporal organization of human music look like when one takes into consideration the totality of the available ethnomusicological, archaeological, historical, and versification data?

This article proceeds through seven major sections, each building toward a comprehensive, cross-culturally grounded account of musical temporal organization.

The Conundrum of Rhythm, Meter, and Tempo in Music Perception demonstrates how these three dimensions of timing are so readily conflated in both professional analysis and everyday listening. Because they interact dynamically in shaping what I term “musical motion,” we must first understand the sources of this confusion before attempting to disentangle the structures themselves.

Problems Defining Rhythm and Meter maps out the conceptual landscape: how rhythm, meter, and beat have been defined differently across musicological traditions, where those definitions succeed and where they fail when applied cross-culturally. The section identifies the narrowness of tactus-centered, bar-oriented models and proposes alternative approaches grounded in structural function and cultural use.

Defining Meter and Rhythm through Beat establishes beat as the common reference point for all three dimensions. Drawing on Russian metrical theory and the integralist school's multifactorial approach, it argues for understanding structures through their semantic functionality and idiomatic use rather than through durational categories alone.

Types of Beat and Their Range of Durational Values catalogs the empirical diversity of beat-sources: syllabic, breath-based, motion-based, instrumental-technique-based, and unitary or binary periodicities. Each beat-type brings its own constraints on temporal grouping, favoring particular metrical organizations and characteristic tempo ranges.

The Issue of Ametrical Music reconceptualizes traditions commonly labeled “ametric” or “arrhythmic” in Western analytical literature. When these musics are understood through their actual beat-sources and grouping principles rather than through a Western tactus-centered lens, they reveal sophisticated temporal organization.

The Origins and Evolution of Temporal Organization in the Western Tradition traces how rhythm, meter, and tempo emerged sequentially in the Western tradition, in conjunction with developments in versification, notation, and music pedagogy.

The Origins of Temporal Organization in non-Western Traditions applies the comparative framework to non-Western repertoires, examining breath-based, syllabic, and motion-based systems in diverse cultural contexts.

The *Conclusion* synthesizes these strands and proposes a provisional evolutionary timeline (Figure-7) mapping major metrical and tempo typologies against landmark prehistoric and historic events.

The Conundrum of Rhythm, Meter, and Tempo in Music Perception

Rhythm, meter, and tempo are often treated as distinct dimensions of musical organization. In listening, however, they interact in shaping a broader impression of how the music moves—“musical motion.” Because these dimensions jointly contribute to that impression, listeners often conflate them. The following examples illustrate how changes in rhythm, meter, and tempo can produce similar impressions of acceleration, deceleration, continuity, or rupture, while doing so by different means.

Listeners often conflate fast surface rhythmic activity with fast tempo, and sparse rhythmic activity with slow tempo, even when the underlying beat level suggests a different interpretation (McKinney & Moelants, 2006; Repp & Bruttomesso, 2009).

Audio-1. *Alap in raga*. Listen for the contrast between the slow, unmeasured unfolding of the vocal line over the drone and the dense ornamental activity within individual phrases. For listeners unfamiliar with the style, such surface density can create an impression of rapid motion even though no fast underlying tempo is established.

Conversely, accent structure can shift the listener’s sense of the beat level itself: strongly marked downbeats and relatively light intermediate events may lead listeners to hear a slower, higher-order pulse, so that rapidly recurring beats are reinterpreted as subdivisions within a more moderate tempo framework (McKinney & Moelants, 2006; Parncutt, 1994).

Audio-2. Beethoven - Pastoral Symphony, 3rd movement, *Allegro*. Notice how the accent structure can encourage the listener to adopt a higher metrical level as the main pulse. What first seems like a rapid stream may be reinterpreted as triplet subdivision within a moderate tempo.

Switching to shorter rhythmic values can sound like a tempo change for a faster motion despite the beat rate staying the same.

Video-1. Greek wedding dance *Tranos*. The cursor tracks the downbeats of the 7/4 meter. Notice that the intervals between the downbeat markers remain constant, even though the instrumental ritornello sounds faster and more agitated. The effect comes from rhythmic diminution: the singers’ half-note motion is replaced by the quarter-note motion in the instrumental *ritornello* and the 8th-notes on the drums (Notopoulos, 1956).

Appearance of rhythmic subdivisions in the accompaniment usually projects the impression of acceleration – even if the melody remains slow.

Audio-3. Bahama chanteys are characterized by incremental rhythmic accelerations that sound like tempo acceleration. Slow hymnal phrases (2-4 sec) open the music and start receiving the rhythmic accompaniment of clapping—at first syncopated quarter-notes (0.7 sec), then regular 8th-notes (0.31 sec) and, finally, added 16th-notes (0.15 sec). An initially calm motion appears to be speeding up.

The same rhythmic pattern can be performed at a gradually increasing tempo and be accompanied by metrical acceleration.

Audio-4. Hebrew Yemenite ceremonial drum-song. The music accelerates steadily from $\text{♩}=85$ to $\text{♩}=107$. Compared to rhythmic acceleration (Audio-3), tempo acceleration sounds less busy and agitated. At 46.8 s, the meter modulates $3/8 \rightarrow 2/8$, reaching $\text{♩}=191$ for a final push that terminates the musical motion (Kolinski, 1949).

The musical motion can appear unbroken despite changes in tempo, if the meter remains unchanged.

Video-2. Bashkir military *uzun-kuy* combines two styles in one song (Lebedinsky, 1965). Its slow verse expresses the warrior's nostalgic feelings, while its lively chorus calls his horse to take him from the battlefield intact. Despite the sharp tempo contrast (*rubato* MM=37 versus *giusto* MM=104), both sections retain the same meter, which helps preserve a sense of underlying continuity even as the affect shifts dramatically.

Conversely, continuity can be disrupted when both tempo and meter change, even if the same melodic-rhythmic theme is retained.

Video-3. Yakut children play-song. Its genre, *chyychaakh*, combines two traditional vocal styles: *dyieretia yrya* (relaxed motion in 4/4) for verses and *degeren yrya* (busy rhythmic motion in 2/4) for the choruses, both sharing the same theme (Alekseyev, 1964). Although both sections are built from the same thematic material, the alternation of meter and tempo makes the movement seem to break and restart, reinforcing the playful call-and-response character. The score (Alekseyev, 1990) presents a different rendition of the same song.

Evidently, switches of rhythm, meter, and tempo can each produce the impression of change in pace, energy, coherence, and pattern of musical motion—each in their own way. Rhythmic acceleration through the subdivision shift (e.g., 8th → 16th notes) temporarily saturates the motion while retaining its pace. Metrical acceleration through subdivision of grouping (4/4 → 2/4) steadily hastens the motion while retaining its character (e.g., *Allegretto*). Tempo acceleration through abrupt change alters the motion's character along with pace. Rhythm, meter, and tempo therefore need to be distinguished analytically, even though in practice their perceptual effects are tightly interdependent.

Problems Defining Rhythm and Meter

Meter is difficult to define, because it does not refer simply to durations as such, but to the structured organization of beats into recurrent patterns of relative strength and weakness. While rhythm and tempo are comparatively uncontroversial, the concept of meter has generated far more disagreement, especially regarding whether it is a property of the sounding signal, a cognitive schema imposed by the listener, or an emergent relation between the two.

Any attempt to define meter must first distinguish it from rhythm. Many Western theorists have emphasized this distinction and shown how readily the two interact and are conflated in analysis and perception (Berry, 1987; Cone, 1968; Cooper & Meyer, 1963; Gjerdingen, 1989; Hasty, 1997; Kramer, 1988; Lerdahl & Jackendoff, 1985; London, 2012; Rothstein, 1989; D. Temperley, 2004; Toussaint, 2020; Yeston, 1976). However, much Western theory still treats meter through categories shaped by the historical experience of European art music. Thus, the *Grove Dictionary* defines meter as: “the temporal hierarchy of subdivisions, beats and bars that is maintained by performers and inferred by listeners which functions as a dynamic temporal framework for the production and comprehension of musical durations.” This definition ties meter to “bars” and risks treating a graphic convention of Western notation as if it were a universal property of music. Bars are the divisions of notated music by means of bar-lines to display the tactus (reviewed below). In cognitive and psychological literature, the terms tactus, pulse, and beat are often used loosely or interchangeably.

My concern is not with metrical hierarchy as such, but with defining meter through tactus and bar-oriented periodicity, both of which are too culture-specific to serve as universal criteria. From that standpoint, temporal systems based on uneven beat groupings or non-conducted pulse structures are often labeled “irregular”, “asymmetrical”, “ametical,” and discussed under the rubric of rhythm rather than meter. I do not adopt that usage. A seven-beat dance meter, for example, may be perfectly regular if its grouping and accentual

organization are stable and culturally shared. In such cases, the problem lies not in the music's supposed lack of meter, but in the narrowness of the model used to identify it.

Like symmetrical meters, asymmetrical meters afford complex salient structures, securing error-correction between multiple performers even in very fast music (Polak et al., 2016).

Video-4. Bulgarian dance *Sedi donka*. Even exceedingly complex asymmetrical metrical structures can secure effective synchronization among multiple performers. This round dance has 25 beats, subdivided in 7+7+11, which in turn are subdivided in 3+2+2, 3+3+2, and 2+2+3+2+2. This grouping corresponds to 3 + 3 + 5 dancing steps, where repeated pairs of side steps (3+3) contrast a succession of two small forward steps, squat, hop, and stop (+5) (Tzonev, 1955). I have marked these steps in the score. Notice how this recurrent “chunking” supports tight synchronization between dancers and musicians.

Even if we leave the pragmatics of timing aside, the modern use of the bar-line to symbolize recurring metrical grouping was conventionalized relatively late in Western notation. Broad distinctions between stronger and weaker positions long predated regular barring, but staff notation incorporated bar-lines only in the 17th century, and regularly spaced barring became standard only in the 18th. In that later usage, bar-lines were more than a merely graphic convenience: they came to project a particular interpretation of metrical grouping and accent. This is why re-barring could alter not just readability but perceived metrical expression. The best illustration of the structural and semantic importance of bar-lines is the evidence of composers re-barring their compositions after realizing that their initial choice of barring contradicted the metrical expression of the musical motion they originally had in mind.¹

Concepts of bar-line and tactus are useful beyond the Common Practice Period music in for many Western repertoires, especially those shaped by score-based coordination and regularized time-keeping. But this does not mean that a tactus-centered model is the cross-cultural default basis of meter. In orally transmitted traditions, and especially in repertoires not organized through conducting or bar-oriented notation, the assignment of beat levels and bar-lines is often far less self-evident than tactus-centered theory can suggest.

Ethnomusicologists have long confronted this difficulty in transcription. Experimental studies of transcription reliability showed substantial divergence when multiple musicians transcribed the same recording (Alekseyev, 1990; England, 1964; List, 1974). Such discrepancies do not show that these traditions lack temporal organization. Rather, they suggest that their metrical regularity may be projected through principles that do not map neatly onto a single tactus-centered, bar-oriented representation and the barring strategy reflects a cultural bias. Thus, in Alekseyev's study, expert-jurors were able to identify the native music culture of some transcriber-subjects based on their transcription of a Koryak dance-song. For this reason, the systematic definition of meter should not be based on bar-oriented periodicity.

Obviously, theories and practices that distinguished between meter and rhythm existed earlier, when music was not divided into hierarchical bars (Allen, 1973; Aristoxenus, 1990; Dale, 2010; Devine et al., 2008; Maas, 1962; Ophuijsen, 1987; Plutarch et al., 1967; Quintilianus, 1983; Raven, 1968; West, 2013). Metrical and rhythmic theories also existed outside Europe (Arnold, 1905; Clayton, 2000; Dr. Sharma, 2007; Rangacharya, 1996; Rowell, 2015; Tarlekar, 1991). Evaluating them retroactively according to a principle that played no role during their lifetime distorts the historical reality.

However, many Western musicologists, from Sachs and Bartók to Clayton and London, consider asymmetrical meters “exotic” and beat “unitary,” despite the fact that, amongst all known music systems, it is the symmetrical meter that is exceptional and recent, and it clearly evolved from the asymmetrical meters. The Ancient Greeks

¹ Some of such cases are documented: Mozart's *Bei Männern* from *Die Zauberflöte* K620/7 and *Allegretto* from *Piano Concerto* K459; Schubert's choral *Frühlingsgesang* D709→D740 and lied *Täuschung* D732/11→D911/19; and Chopin's *Tarantella* op.43. There are also cases when composers misjudged the anacrusis in their barring: Adam's *Marche de vigneron* from *Giselle* or Field's *Air Russe Varié* for piano 4-hands.

and Romans measured pulses by unequal parts in fixed ratios, generating asymmetrical structures. In practice, their “beat” was *binary*—consisting of short and long pulses (Afonasin et al., 2015; Allen, 1973; Dale, 2010; Halporn et al., 1980; Kholopov, 1999; Quintilianus, 1983; Rowell, 1979; West, 1992). Theorists did observe a smallest abstract “unitary” unit of duration—*chrónos* or *mora*. But they treated it as a scholastic measuring device rather than as a bearer of musical meaning, much as Greek harmonic theory measured larger, musically salient intervals such as the *límma* and *tónos* by means of the smaller and theoretically useful but not itself musically salient “atomic” *diesis* within the tetrachord (Barker, 2004; Euclid, 1991; Hagel, 2009; Mathiesen, 1999; West, 1992).

Both kinds of binary organization—of pitch and of time—have persisted in the same broad geographic area. Popular Greek and Macedonian/Thracian folk dances, for example, organize beat through binary groupings embedded in larger metrical structures, some of which preserve features reminiscent of ancient practices (Holden & Vouras, 1965; Hunt, 1996; Kremenliev, 1952; A. Singer, 1974). Some scholars argue for the historical continuity of this dance tradition (David, 2006; Djoudjeff, 1955; Kazarova, 1935). Thus, Djoudjeff points out that the trans-Balkan genre of *horo* (hora) is derived from the Greek *χορός* and the art of *χορεία* that was based on construction of asymmetrical compound structures by addition of binary and ternary feet. This very much resembles what is observed in the orchesography of present-day Bulgarian dances.

The continuity between the binary typology of temporal intervals in Greek/Balkan folk, art, and ecclesiastical melodies and the Ancient Greek *melopoeia* is well-established (Gertsman, 1986, 1988; Ioannidou, 2009; Katsanevaki, 2005, 2011; Kholopov, 2006; Nikolsky, 2016a, 2021; Richter, 1998; Skoulios, 2012; Troelsgard, 1988; Wright, 1969; Zannos, 1990, 1994). Western music also often employs uneven metrical structures in composite meters. Uneven metric pulse is not confined to the Greco-Roman tradition: it is used in remote territories, from Central Africa to China and India (Arom, 2006; Brailoiu, 1951; Brandel, 1973; Chekanowska, 1988; Clayton, 2020; Harris, 2008; Kholopova, 1971, 1983; Magill & Pressing, 1997; Stone, 1985; Vinogradov, 1984). Such wide distribution suggests that there are underlying cognitive reasons for the genesis of binary metrics.

“Metrical” ≠ “metric”: binary units may offer an advantage over unitary timing systems when open-ended information must be segmented and transmitted efficiently. Perceptual contrasts between two time-units could provide perceptual advantage like the semitone/tone contrasts in the division of heptatonic scales compared to uniformed whole-tone or semitonal divisions (Mazel, 1952; Nikolsky, 2015; Shepard, 2010). Contrasting chunks, in turn, facilitate further chunking, achieving even higher compression rates. Complex asymmetrical meters are most common in fast dances and improvised virtuosic vocal/instrumental music, where timely synchronization between the participants is crucial for the continuity of performance. Binary encoding is not limited to music. It appears in many information-dense signaling systems (Table-1).

Table-1. Common applications of binary timing besides music. This table lists some common forms of transmission that implement binary time-coded signaling based on the duration contrast between two different pulse lengths: short and long. “Atomic unit” here serves a purely technical need to relate “shortness” to “longness” and carries no semantic load.

Application:	“Atomic” unit:	Short unit:	Long unit:
Versification Greek	χρόνος πρώτος	βραχύς	μακρός
Versification Latin	mora	brevis	longa
Versification Sanskrit	mātrā	laghu	guru
Versification Arabic	‘arūḍ	sabab	watad
Typography	half-unit	em	en
Morse code telegraphy	tick	dot	dash

Pulse-width (IR remotes)	on/off	short	long
1-Wire serial bus (Dallas)	bit time slot	1 (short-low)	0 (long-low)

There are three primary reasons why Western meter became increasingly “monistic”—i.e., privileging one principal beat hierarchy at a time—and progressively more symmetrical, favoring regularly recurring bars and proportionate subdivisions (Apel, 1949; Berger, 2005; Christensen, 2008; DeFord, 2015; Hoppin, 1978; Houle, 1987; Kharlap, 1978; Kramer, 1988; Lester, 1986; Sachs, 1953):

- 1) linguistic shift in medieval vernacular prosody from quantity to accent;
- 2) ecclesiastical resistance to asymmetrical meters in liturgical contexts and emergence of large-scale polyphonic practice, which encouraged standardized durational relations and symmetrical time-keeping for choir-masters coordinating multiple parts;
- 3) invention and spread of notation, which increasingly transferred the organization of musical time from purely auditory transmission to visually stabilized proportional representation.

The Church Fathers rejected Greco-Roman rhythmic/metrical styles as frivolous, sensual, effeminate, and liturgically undignified. Thus, Athanasius and Gregory of Nyssa derided Sotadean-like rhythm, connecting it to Salome’s dance and playing (West, 1982).

In 15th-century Western Europe, the term *tactus* entered music theory in reference to coordination of notated polyphonic time (DeFord, 2015). In 16th-century theory, *tactus* was explicitly defined as the continuous motion of the directing hand, linking it to practices of time-beating in coordinated performance. Thereafter, *tactus* has become historically salient within Western score-based practice. However, in cognitive and psychological literature, *tactus*-like beat levels are often treated as if they provided a culturally neutral model of meter.

Indeed, beat perception and synchronization are biologically grounded (Merchant et al., 2015). But from the perspective of systematic musicology, *tactus* is neither identical with beat nor with meter—it refers to one privileged timekeeping beat level within a metrical framework—the level most readily tracked in counting, tapping, or coordinated ensemble performance. Hence, *tactus* is “larger” than *beat* but “smaller” than *meter*.

Tactus is a subject of preference. It is quite common for different conductors to employ different *tactus* in conducting the same composition (Earhart, 1946; Rozhdestvensky, 1974; Rudolf, 1980). This is yet another distinction from beat and meter, which in musicological literature usually refer to the objective properties of a music composition rather than the performer’s choice of interpretation.

Cultural specificity of *tactus* matters particularly in cross-cultural comparison, because temporal organization need not always be projected through the same privileged beat level, nor through the bar-oriented assumptions of Western notation. As compound meters became common during the 16-17th centuries, time-beating became *hierarchical*—marking different beats by different gestures and weight (Spitzer et al., 2001). In contrast, metrical perception of indigenous music-users tends to be *heterarchical*—based not on subdivision of bars (*subordination*) but on linear addition of metrical units (*coordination*), whose number per line can vary (see “syllabic meters” below). Heterarchical meters present a single dominant pulse that listeners can track directly, whereas *tactus*-based meters require selecting one privileged level from several simultaneously salient ones.

Tactus-like hierarchical perception of meter is related to music schooling (Alekseyev, 1976, 1986; Arom, 1984; Jacoby et al., 2024; Jacoby & McDermott, 2017; Kharlap, 1972, 1986; Niemi, 1998, 2009; Polak, 2010). The figure below models the *tactus*-centered conception of meter characteristic of Western score-based performance, where meters more complex than simple binary contain different subordinated beat levels, explicitly shown by the conductor’s hand.

Figure-2. The hierarchical structure of tactus. “*Tactus*” shows the standard conducting scheme for double, triple, quadruple and sextuple meters. The arrow with “I” indicates the downbeat direction. “*Meter*” displays the corresponding notation and beat numbers. Dotted bar-lines mark the compound structures. “*Weight*” indicates the relative metrical stress designated to the beats: the downbeat (↓) the heaviest; the onbeat—i.e., the compound downbeat (→)—heavy; the upbeat (↑) medium-heavy; the backbeat—i.e., the compound upbeat (↖)—medium; the beat (i.e., regular beat)—light, and in 6/4, the second regular beat is the lightest. “*Hierarchy*” indicates subordination of beats by arrows from “master” to “servant”: solid for primary and dashed for secondary (in compounds). Hierarchy can engage up to 4 levels (12/8 is quite common).

Notation-based schooling seems to influence beat induction—i.e., the cognitive ability to extract a regular pulse from a stream of musical events, even when rhythm and dynamics do not explicitly mark it (Honing, 2012). Although the capacity for beat induction seems to have a biological basis (Bergeson & Trehub, 2006; Merchant et al., 2015), explicit selection and representation of the appropriate beat level develop much later: classroom and experimental work alike show that young children often struggle to decide whether a musical pattern is best grouped in twos or threes (Bamberger & DiSessa, 2003; Hannon & Johnson, 2005; Uptis, 1987). Heterarchical meters may be tracked more directly, whereas hierarchical meters place greater demands on beat induction and rely more heavily on prior stylistic experience. Although basic metrical-hierarchy perception is accessible to most listeners without formal training, the number of hierarchical levels to which listeners respond and their detection accuracy increase with age and music training, suggesting the contribution of learning (Drake et al., 2000). In music with a greater number of simultaneously relevant metrical levels, listeners are more likely to diverge in their choice of beat level (Martens, 2011; McKinney & Moelants, 2006; Parncutt, 1994). One reason for the survival of heterarchical meters in some monophonic traditions might be their capacity to promote greater convergence amongst participants in genres that carry social or ritual weight.

Professional classical musicians can perceive more pulse levels in rhythmic divisions, hypermetric grouping, and different expressive aspects of music, such as harmonic changes, articulation grouping, phrasing, and thematic development. However, greater scope results in greater divergence of tactus interpretation: different

musicians often choose different pulses to illuminate in their performance. Thus, classical master-performers often create shifts of beat level in their interpretation of the score (Musin, 1967; Rozhdestvensky, 1974): they change pulses from “common” to “split” time or to single-beat time within the long movement scored in the same time signature to increase contrasts between sections of music form.² Naturally, performers diverge in their mapping of such “beat modulations”: at which point to start and end a new pulse. Capacity to effectively engage these modulations is considered a top skill amongst professional classical musicians. Comparable phenomena are described in English-language musicology as “metric reinterpretation,” “hypermetrical transition,” or “shift of beat level” (Love, 2016; Rothstein, 1989; D. Temperley, 2008).

Within contemporary Western listening culture, heterarchical and hierarchical forms of beat induction appear to be diverging more sharply. From the mid-20th century, music literacy started declining due to cuts in music training in general school curricula, replacement of active amateur music-making by passive consumption of music records, and the overwhelming popularity of jazz, rock, pop, rap, and electronica that rely on oral transmission rather than notation (Berliner, 1994; Botstein, 1992; Butler, 2006; Dahl, 2009; Daubney et al., 2019; Gracyk, 1996; Green, 2002; Krims, 2000; Parsad, 2012; Schachter, 1977). Hence, sensitivity to elaborate tactus hierarchies becomes increasingly concentrated among listeners with substantial exposure to, or training in, Western notated music. This does not imply that beat induction itself is wholly learned; rather, it suggests that complex hierarchical meter depends more heavily on enculturation and practice compared to basic pulse extraction. Arguably, the prevalence of drum-sets and drum-machines in popular music worldwide habituates audiences to the tactus beat. But listeners with less experience in notated multi-layered repertoires might blindly follow the loudest drum beat rather than paying attention to beat density, extra pulses, or hypermeter carried by the other parts.

To increase confusion, the concepts of meter and rhythm became inverted throughout the course of Western history: what the Ancient Greeks called meter is now considered rhythm and vice versa (Barker, 1991; Goodell, 1902; Kharlap, 1978; Nagy, 1994; Rowell, 1979; West, 1992). So, scholars of antiquity and modernity talk over each other’s heads. To reduce misunderstandings, it would be beneficial to:

- define meter and rhythm in terms broad enough to travel across historical and cultural repertoires,
- distinguish the structures themselves from the labels used to describe them,
- identify rhythmic and metrical structures in relation to their musical function and use.

Defining Meter and Rhythm through Beat

Opposing rhythm/meter as event/schema will hold across all metrical typologies, if the concept of beat is expanded to include binary and loosely-periodic pulses – as it is done in Russian musicology. Because of its theoretical and cultural ties to Greek tradition, metrical diversity of Russian versification (that includes asymmetrical meters), generous funding for ethnographic research, and thousands of indigenous musicologists studying their native music, Russian metrical theory from the 19th century reflected temporal organization beyond tactus (Afonina, 2002; Alekseyev, 1976, 1986; Arkadyev, 1992, 2012; Beliayev, 1971; Chekhovich, 2011; Kharlap, 1971, 1972, 1978, 1986; Kholopova, 1971, 1980, 1983, 2002; Losev, 1995; Mazel, 1952, 1979; Mazel & Tsukkerman, 1967; Milka, 1982; Zemtsovsky, 1975, 1987c).

Also, the Russian integralist school adopted a multifactorial method of analyzing melody and harmony together with rhythm, meter, tempo, articulation, dynamics, texture, and register (see Appendix-1). Rather than treating

² Such shifts are especially plausible at formal junctures where thematic contrast invites a broader pulse. In sonata-form movements, performers may therefore re-hear the secondary subject at a higher-order beat level than the principal subject—even if the score does not indicate a new time signature (recordings of the first movement of Chopin’s *Sonata* in B-flat minor, Op. 35, illustrate this possibility.)

these parameters separately, it identified recurrent *idiomatic patterns*—configurations of expressive features conventionally associated with particular meanings and uses within a genre/style. Such patterns acquire certain structural stability through their functional reuse: accompanying dance, coordinating labor, marking cadences, projecting transitions, intensifying climaxes, articulating recitations, etc. These functional correlates put in place semantic correlates: the expressive or generic meaning associated with a function, e.g., marching, dancing, lamenting, ludic, etc.

This idiomatic approach allows one to track a specific structure by its characteristic semantic and pragmatic features across historical changes in theoretical terminology, rather than relying on labels alone. By the same token, it enables identification of structural typologies by comparing how the same structure is used in different applications. For example, the same triple meter may express different things in a waltz, mazurka, or sarabande—once tempo, accentuation, articulation, phrasing, and texture are taken into account. Or, a dotted rhythm can signify very different things depending on its broader idiomatic setting: in one context it may project march-like regularity, in another French-overture grandeur, and in another expressive hesitation. Where a purely durational description records the same rhythm, an idiomatic analysis explains why listeners and performers do not hear these cases as equivalent. Unlike approaches that classify meter primarily through durational regularity or bar structure, the idiomatic approach asks how a pattern is articulated, grouped, accented, and used within the genre and performance practice. It therefore distinguishes structures that may look similar on paper but function differently in listening and performance.

Together with the integralist perspective, the idiomatic approach proved especially useful for the study of meter, whose perception often depends on articulation, accent, tempo, texture, and register no less than on durational pattern itself.

Yet another reason for specifying semantic descriptors for each analyzed structure is that in its transmission, receivers reproduce the same structure differently, depending on their understanding of it, contributing to its significant transformation over multiple iterations (Nikolsky & Benítez-Burraco, 2024). This is most pronounced in oral transmission, but is noticeable in notated traditions too. Classical musicians reproduce the same notated pattern differently from one another, depending on how they understand its expressive character and formal function—understandings shaped in part by prior exposure to performances by others (Nazaikinsky, 1972). Here, semantics – i.e., what kind of expression or genre-association a pattern conventionally projects – interacts with pragmatics – i.e., how that pattern is actually used in performance, coordination, ritual, dance, or transmission.

In folk music transmission, a performer tends to exaggerate those structural traits that appear more important for conveying a perceived musical expression, causing radical changes. Alekseyev (1986) describes cases when an authored limerick-like poem in cross-rhymed trochee turned into Russian folk hendecasyllabic distich and then Yakut heptasyllabic distich. These changes are not merely the result of accidental “miscopying.” Rather, repeated retransmission tends to reshape a pattern in the direction of structures that are more idiomatic, meaningful, and functionally usable within the receiving tradition. This reshapes not only specific music pieces, but entire rhythm-metric typologies. When genres enter a new cultural environment, receivers often adapt them to locally familiar expressive and coordinative patterns. The following pair of examples illustrate how the same genre can become unrecognizable via cross-cultural transmission.

Audio-5. Polish mazurka. Originating as a folk dance in Masovia, it later became a major genre of European 19th-century art music, associated with an energetic, buoyant, yet proud gait. It is characterized by triple meter, accentuation of all three beats, dotted rhythm (often on the downbeat), moderate tempo, and homophonic texture.

Audio-6. Martinique mazurka. Brought by French colonists, the European mazurka merged with the local *beguine* and lost its dotted rhythm, acquiring instead heavy sub-beat syncopation and cross-rhythms in both melody and accompaniment. The tempo became livelier. The texture became polyphonic. The relation between

the Polish original and its Martinique offspring can hardly be recognized by ear alone. It requires tracing their social use and historical transformation of their characteristic musical structures.

Each transmission act involves learning, and receivers routinely simplify and regularize complex patterns according to their experience. Adaptation increases when receivers are less competent than transmitters. A single simplification can considerably reshape an original structure.

Knowing (or guessing) what the received pattern “is for” (semantically and/or functionally) shapes the internal representation of what becomes transmitted (Akinbo, 2021; Jacoby & McDermott, 2017; Kleeman, 1985; Lumaca et al., 2018; Lumaca & Baggio, 2018; Mehr et al., 2019; Ravignani et al., 2018). Additional formative influence comes from the emotional nature of musical semantics. Music encodes musical emotions, understood here as conventionally recognizable affective qualities or expressive character projected by musical structure - whether or not they coincide with fully felt emotion in the listener (Cespedes-Guevara & Eerola, 2018; Juslin, 2013, 2019; Kallinen, 2006; Krumhansl, 1997, 2002; Peretz, 2013; Perlovsky, 2010; Reybrouck & Eerola, 2017). Although music admits analytical and rational modes of understanding, its conventional idioms are most immediately grasped through their affective and expressive force.

Importantly, listeners’ emotional responses affect their judgments of music (Ansani et al., 2019; Bezdek & Gerrig, 2008; Bhattacharya & Lindsen, 2016; Logeswaran & Bhattacharya, 2009; Palazzi et al., 2019; Vieillard et al., 2012; Zhou et al., 2022). This applies to temporal organization as well. Emotional response does not simply override rhythmic-metrical structure, nor is it fully independent of it. Rather, musical structure triggers and directs the listener’s affective response, and that response then feeds back into temporal perception, biasing judgments of pace, duration, salience, and metrical tension (Droit-Volet et al., 2013; Droit-Volet & Gil, 2009; Keller & Schubert, 2011; N. Singer et al., 2023; Stupacher et al., 2013; Trost et al., 2014; Witek et al., 2014; Wöllner & Hammerschmidt, 2021).

Hence, musical transmission is shaped by musical emotions insofar as listeners and performers tend to preserve or amplify rhythmic features that carry stronger affective and kinetic appeal. Thus, in popular-music studies, syncopation has repeatedly been associated with pleasure, happiness, and groove (Keller & Schubert, 2011; Witek et al., 2014). In oral traditions, performers do not merely reproduce transmitted patterns mechanically. Because reproduction is shaped by embodied enjoyment, groove, and expressive preference, rhythmic features associated with stronger excitement or pleasure are often intensified or expanded in transmission: e.g., the growing structural prominence of syncopation over time (Berlin, 1984; D. Temperley, 2021).

Prolonged transmission, especially across generations, can radically reshape conventional rhythmic-metric idioms as their social use changes. Thus, the 17th-century gavotte proceeded in leisurely 2/2, with punctuated downbeat and prevailing quarter-note motion; later, as the genre became detached from active dance and was experienced in concert settings, it started running in excited 4/4 by continuous 8th-notes, without dotted rhythm (Little, 2001). Shifts in social function, bodily use, and performance context influence the affective profile of a genre, reshaping its conventional temporal organization.

This is why rhythm-metrical analysis should not be separated from semantics. The rhythm-meter-tempo complex must be viewed within the *genre* context (Briner, 1955; Dumesnil, 1949; Nazaikinsky, 2013; Sachs, 1953; Sokhor, 1968, 1971; Tarasova, 2021; Tsukkerman, 1964; Zemtsovsky, 1985). Rhythm has a *textual functionality*, superimposed on meter, which executes a *stylistic functionality* generalized from many textual applications and fixed via public conventions (Milka, 1982). Abstraction of rhythm-metrical forms from their semantic and syntactic context can distort their structural attributes and lead to inadequate generalizations (Afonina, 2002; Zemtsovsky, 1985, 1987c, 1997, 2002). Thus, *Lombardic rhythm* and *Scotch snap* are often considered “the same,” whereas they only *look* identical in *notation*, while their sound is articulated, grouped, timed and paced differently in their respective performance practices, depending on the musical context and

genre/style (Flett & Flett, 1966; Hammond, 1983; Haynes, 1997; MacGregor, 1968; N. Temperley & Temperley, 2011).³

Video-5. Scotch snap and Lombardic rhythm in four idiomatic settings. These four excerpts show that the same reverse-dotted configuration can belong to distinct rhythmic idioms once articulation, tempo, grouping, texture, and genre function are taken into account. **1) Instrumental Scotch snap** in the highland Strathspey reel: rough and wild, dance-driven, marcato articulation, with frequent repetitions of the same pitch, and streaked in lively tempo. **2) Vocal Scotch snap** in the 19th century lyric songs: more graceful expression of folk sincerity, simplicity and vigor, introducing short syllabic legato while maintaining the other characteristics. **3) Early Lombardic rhythm** in the 16-17th century Italian vocal and organ music: an expressive intensifier and climactic device, a voice-marker in polyphonic textures, legato, relaxed tempo, no wide leaps and repeated pitches. **4) Galant Lombardic rhythm** in the 18-19th century vocal/instrumental music: exclusively melodic ornamentation in homophonic texture, the same articulation, but lost stress and tension and livelier tempo. Taken together, these cases show that notational identity does not guarantee idiomatic equivalence.

Such cases, when unrelated semantic and pragmatic characteristics are assigned to the same basic structure constitute musical *homographs* and *homonyms* (Zemtsovsky, 1974). Extra-structural emic information is indispensable for their accurate semiotic identification.

The primary source for accurate beat extraction is the genre characteristics of the music in question. Genre application suggests a conventional range of pace for a metrical pulse and its grouping (e.g., binary for walking). Different metrical types tend to acquire recurrent kinetic and expressive associations, shaped by customary pace, grouping, and bodily usage. The following table summarizes these broad associations heuristically for common meter types (Table-2).

Table-2. General typology of meters and their characteristic expressions in classical and folk music. This table summarizes broad connections between the meter type, beat value, and expressive-kinetic profile. Shorter bar lengths tend to intensify metric activity through closer downbeat recurrence, whereas greater compound complexity tends to differentiate beats and invite greater rhythmic variety. Greater asymmetry tends to simplify rhythm and strengthen the downbeat. Common time signatures are marked bold.

	Duple	Triple	Quintuple	Septuple
Common feet	iamb/trochee	dactyl/anapest/ amphibrach	paeonic genus	epitrite genus
Foot's ethos	urgent, purposeful, direct, sharp, stepping	elevated, rolling, pleasant, swaying, flowing	praising, solemn, ritual, ideal, pastoral, rustic	exalted, disturbed, restless, complex, conflicting
Simple	2/16, 2/8, 2/4 , 2/2*	3/16, 3/8 , 3/4 , 3/2	5/16, 5/8 , 5/4	7/16 , 7/8 , 7/4
Compound	4/16, 4/8, 4/4 , 8/8	6/16, 6/8 , 6/4 , 9/16, 9/8 , 12/16, 12/8 , 24/16	10/16, 10/8, 15/16	14/16, 14/8
Composite	3+1, 3+2+2 , 3+2+3, 3+1+2+2	2+1 , 1+2 , 3+2+1, 2+2+2+3 , 3+2+2+2 , 2+2+3+2, 3+3+2+2+2	3+2 , 2+3 , 2+2+1, 4+1	2+2+3 , 3+2+2
Alternating	2/4-3/4, 3/4-2/4 ,	4/4-3/4 , 3/4-4/4, 6/8- 3/4 , 3/4-6/8	4/4-5/8	4/4-7/8

* The beat value functions as a modifier of the expression: x/16 blistering, x/8 brisk, x/4 casual, x/2 solemn – across the variations of the same pulse (e.g., 3/16, 3/8, 3/4, 3/2).

³ Although earlier musicologists (Quantz, Burney) did not distinguish between Scotch and Lombardic idioms, the multi-factorial approach of the integralist analysis reveals their structural and semantic differences. Such theoretical updates are common in musicology, because the theoretical recognition of a musical idiom in common practice often requires some historical distance.

Outside musicians' circles, it is less widely recognized that rhythmic figures are not expressed independently of beat level. The same durational ratio may be performed differently depending on the metrical level at which it occurs (Figure-3). That level's salience, together with the listener's experience, helps shape the perceived affective and kinetic character of the rhythmic figure (McAuley & Semple, 1999; Bouwer & Honing, 2015; Katz et al., 2015; Nave-Blodgett et al., 2021; Hammerschmidt & Wöllner, 2020).

The figure is a 3x3 grid of musical notation. The columns are labeled 'I. Syncopé (2:1:1)', 'II. Triplet (2/3)', and 'III. Puncture (1:3)'. The rows are labeled 'A', 'B', and 'C'. Each cell contains a short musical excerpt in 4/4 time, marked 'Andante' with a tempo of 76. Red numbers (1, 2, 3, 4) are placed above the notes to indicate beat positions. Red squares are drawn around specific rhythmic figures within the notation. Row A shows supra-beat level examples, Row B shows beat level examples, and Row C shows sub-beat level examples.

Figure-3. Beat level conditions the expression of rhythmic figures (listen to the corresponding audio examples Nos. 6-8). The figure compares 3 durational configurations at supra-beat, beat, and sub-beat levels, showing how their kinetic and expressive character changes with metrical placement. **Ia) 2:1:1 supra-beat**—no syncopation, smooth flow. **Ib) beat**—classic syncopation disrupts the flow. **Ic) sub-beat**—lower-order syncopation increases fluidity. **IIa) Irregular 3-in-place-of-2 supra-beat**—a higher-order triplet disrupts the flow. **IIb) beat**—a common triplet smoothens the flow pulse. **IIc) sub-beat**—a lower-order triplet embellishes the flow. **IIIa) Dotted rhythm supra-beat**—smooth flow. **IIIb) beat**—pronounced bouncing energizes the flow. The word “bounce” (or, “snap”) is common in reference to the dotted beat-level rhythm in dance literature. It denotes the kinetic impression of a springing or rebounding motion commonly associated with moving to this rhythm. **IIIc) sub-beat**—no bouncing, ornamented flow. Red numbers indicate beats. Red squares encapsulate the reviewed rhythmic figures.

Beat-dependence is well-researched for syncopation (Berlin, 1984; Longuet-Higgins & Lee, 1984; Sioros et al., 2014; D. Temperley, 2021; VanderStel & Temperley, 2022), but not for dotted rhythms and triplets. Although dotted figures and triplets might also participate in syncopation, they have their own distinctive expressive and performative profiles. Their dependence on beat level has been reported mainly in performance practice and oral pedagogy. The following examples illustrate how the same durational ratio changes its expressive and kinetic character when projected at different beat levels (Audios-7-9).

Audio-7. Syncopation and beat level. Three excerpts based on the same thematic material and meter are presented consecutively. Each uses the same durational ratio (2:1:1), with the longer note carrying the accent. In the first excerpt, the longer note spans two beats and, according to the textbooks, does not constitute syncopé—it sounds smooth. In the second, the longer note equals one beat and constitutes a classic syncopé—it disrupts the beat. In the third, the longer note is shorter than the beat and constitutes the 2nd-order syncopé—it smoothens the motion by linking beats into longer chains.

Audio-8. Triplet and beat level. Again, three excerpts project the same figure at different metrical levels. In the first, the triplet division spans two beats and strongly disturbs the beat, an effect performers often intensify by stressing all three notes more equally. In the second, the triplet is contained within one beat and tends to smoothen the motion in comparison to regular division; performers often stress the first note and glide over the rest. In the

third, the triplet subdivides half-a-beat and sounds like light ornamentation, akin to a mordent or shake; performers often lighten all three notes further.

Audio-9. Dotted rhythm and beat level. The same dotted ratio (1:3) is projected at different metrical levels. In the first excerpt, the longer note exceeds the beat and creates a leisurely leaning effect; performers may shorten it slightly to smoothen the rhythmic contrast. In the second, the longer note is shorter than the beat and produces a more vigorous, bouncing character; performers often overdot it in such contexts. In the third, the longer note is shorter than half-a-beat and sounds like ornamentation; performers commonly shorten it further to make the melodic motion appear more fluent.

The foregoing discussion suggests that the expression of meter, tempo, and rhythm depends on the listener's ability to infer a beat from the musical stream. In this sense, rhythm may be understood as the perceived pattern of durational relations among musical events as these are heard against an inferred beat; meter, as the hierarchical organization of inferred beats into recurrent patterns of relative strength and weakness; and tempo, as the perceived *characteristic* pace of those beats. The qualifier "characteristic" reflects that tempo is ordinarily experienced not merely as rate, but as a mode of musical motion with affective and kinetic qualities. In Western art music, the association of tempo with affective character has been a hallmark of tempo categorization since the introduction of verbal tempo indications by Luys Milan (1536). Throughout the 18th century, the array of tempo indications across Europe became categorized in tempo classes, referenced by the Italian terms (e.g., *Largo*, *Adagio*, *Andante*, *Allegro*, *Presto*), each distinguished by its own character (Epstein, 1995; Marty, 1988; Rosenblum, 2007a). By Mozart's time, a system of tempo modifiers became established, each modifier distinguished by pace and character (e.g., *Allegro maestoso* was slower and more natural than the restrained pace of *Allegro moderato*). This system was thoroughly described by Hummel, Mozart's pupil (Hummel, 1828).

Types of Beat and Their Range of Durational Values

The next issue to resolve before discussing the origins of rhythm is the typology of beat. Beats differ not only in grouping, but also in degree of temporal strictness. Some are relatively regular, whereas others are temporally flexible and permit occasional deviations, pauses, or halts. Even the tactus, understood here as the relatively steady pulse level that anchors metric orientation, routinely fluctuates or momentarily pauses in expressive performance (see Table-3). In breath-based (recitation) and motion-based (worksong) metric organizations, caesuras often arise for physiological reasons. Subsequently, the operative beats occur primarily within caesural boundaries, excluding the caesuras' duration.

Before examining the distinguishing features of different beat types, it is essential to identify what all forms of beat share in common. All beats, regardless of their source or cultural context, serve a fundamental function: they provide recurring temporal reference points that allow participants in music-making—whether performers, dancers, or listeners—to coordinate their timing, anticipate upcoming events, and segment the musical flow into processable units. Whether the reference is a footfall, a syllable boundary, a breath-group, a stroke of an instrument, or a cycle of bodily motion, each provides a temporal anchor around which rhythm, meter, and tempo are organized. What distinguishes one beat type from another is not this basic coordinative function but rather the source of its periodicity and the specific constraints that source places on grouping, tempo ranges, and the resulting metrical typologies.

It is not uncommon for scholars to consider music with frequent pauses (caesuras) and suspensions (fermatas) unmeasured, irregular, or even ametrical. This is a byproduct of an uncritical reliance on Western textbooks of elementary music theory that present the tactus-based concept of meter, adopted by Western classical composers and theorists of the 18th-19th centuries, as though it is a universal rule. In practice, even in Western classical music, some genres use frequent pausing/suspending (chorale, operatic recitatives, melodramas). In Western folk music, long caesuras are routine for slow vocal and instrumental music. In non-Western music, pausing at the phrasal ends is common even in fast genres. The presence of metrically free cadences does not make the

entire music work ametrical – just as the presence of tempo-free cadenzas does not strip a Western classical concerto of its time signature. The category of beat is broader than the tactus-centered pulse assumed in many Western theoretical accounts.

English-speaking musicology centers on the bipedal model of beat – “foot,” salient in dances, processions, and songs with rhymed lyrics. However, this is not the only known metrical etiology. Beat can emerge from:

- Syllables of the lyrics/vocables;
- Breath-groups and formulaic repetitions;
- Instrumental technique;
- Patterned motion accompanying vocalization;
- External periodic sounds.

This listing presents an idealized typology: in practice, beats rarely originate from a single source. Most living musical traditions combine several sources simultaneously—the most common admixtures include dance-song (motion + syllables), procession-song (locomotion + breath-groups + text), ritual chant (breath + formulaic vocables), worksong (motor pulse + syllables), and extended textless collective vocalizations (breath + group entrainment). The distinctions drawn in what follows are analytical rather than exhaustive; they isolate the dominant source shaping each form of beat, not the only source at work.

These sources of beat are not functionally equivalent. Each brings with it its own constraints on temporal segmentation and grouping, thereby favoring particular types of meter and characteristic tempo ranges. The following sections examine these sources of beat one by one.

In theories of syllabic versification, the basic counting unit is the phonetic syllable, with larger groupings articulated by caesura and rhyme (Attridge, 1995; Cornulier, 1995; Fabb & Halle, 2008a; Gasparov, 1996; Kharlap, 1986; Navarro Tomás, 1983). Traditions shaped by syllabic poetry, including a number of Spanish and French repertoires, often feature asymmetrical structures: free (Spanish *saeta*, *martinete*, *debla*, *carcelera*, *trilla*, *taranta*; Brittany’s *gwerz*; Limousin and Auvergne’s *complainte* and *chansons à rythme libre*), patterned (quintuple *zortzico*, *rueda*, *charrada*, *villancico*; Brittany’s *gavotte*), and alternating/composite (*Musique mesurée*).⁴

In musical traditions shaped by syllabic versification, temporal organization often follows prosodic and syntactic segmentation rather than a continuously iterated tactus. Such music often appears irregular or metrically polyvalent. Here, the actual organizing unit is the syllable as a unit of poetic segmentation. This can take at least two forms: in some traditions, flexible surface timing masks an underlying isometric syllabic structure; in others, the same syllabic framework supports more than one metrical realization. The following two examples illustrate these possibilities.

Video-6. Nganasan song of the reindeer Urdu. The melody is loosely quantized into three rhythmic values within a 6-syllable verse pattern typical of Nganasan song and governed by the prosodic rules of speech (Dobzhanskaya, 2014). From the standpoint of Western tactus-based theory, such a melody may appear “unmetrical” because of its flexible timing and weak periodic accentuation. Yet this classification would be misleading. The lyrics and melodic strophes display a consistent isometric organization, and the rhythmic contour of the melody tends to recur throughout the song (Niemi, 1998). For a Nganasan speaker, syllabic patterning provides the principal cue for anticipating the next metric unit, since the rhythm is based on conventional idiomatic phrases.

⁴ Although the proliferation of *Musique mesurée* (or, *Vers mesurés*) was brief in the last third of the 16th century (in music by Le Jeune, de Courville, Costeley, and Maudit), its influence lasted well into the 17th century, celebrated by such authorities as Du Caurroy and Mersenne. Later French composers kept using similar structures notated as the “alternating meters” common in operatic and oratorical music: Boieldieu in *La Dame Blanche*, Berlioz in *L’Enfance du Christ*, Gounod in *Mireille*.

Video-7. Russian folk dance-song *Kamarinskaya*. This clip contains three variations on a short melodic formula with lyrics. Its rhythmically simple 11-syllable structure, characteristic of Russian folk song, is metrically deceptive. The same formula may be sung with a dactylic orientation in 3/4, played with an iambic orientation in 2/4, or danced with a trochaic orientation in 2/4, in “three steps” (Rudneva, 1994). Here the syllabic framework remains stable, but the meter is polyvalent: it is realized differently depending on whether the determining frame is vocal declamation, instrumental accompaniment, or dance motion.

Ambiguity is especially common for dance-songs, where syllabic and dance-step groupings often mismatch. Orchesography segments music differently: changing directions at the end of a dance-pattern often generates metrical stress, whereas exhalation at phrasal ends tends to soften cadences. Also, for dance-steps, the right-left alternation evens up the asymmetrical meters by generating binary compound units (arsis + thesis)—often repeated—directed towards a longer ternary step that is used like a “downbeat” to demarcate dance figures (Djoudjeff, 1945; Ilieva, 2007; Tzonev, 1955; Velcheva, 2007). Syllables do not support such “figure-making.” Prosodic rise/fall in poetic speech lasts longer than stepping right-left in a social dance, and prosodic fall is stressed stronger than a right step, promoting longer vocal spans and wave-like compound structures.

These differences, however, seem to characterize relatively advanced layers of musical culture. In studies of archaic strata of folk tradition, song and dance are often reconstructed as sharing the same or closely related metrical organization (Alekseyev, 1986; Alpatova, 2019; Bowie, 2011; Kharlap, 1986; Kvitka, 1971; Sachs, 1965; Sipos, 2001). Such reconstructions are typically based on comparative analysis of genre stratification, textual archaism, melodic formulae, performance context, and the functional coupling of motion and vocalization in traditional practice.

Orchesography, like versification, often evolves from systems organized primarily by durational quantity to systems organized primarily by accentual contrast. This does not mean that quantitative organization lacks agogic accentuation, but only that duration rather than stress provides its primary structuring principle. Quantitative rhythmicity is one manifestation of the metric reforms that characterize Bronze Age civilizations (Nikolsky & Benitez-Burraco, 2024). Ancient Greek and Indian dances, in their formalized traditions, presented a visually salient succession of expressive poses like a slide-show - each pose (*schēma*), briefly sustained and separated from the next pose by a swift transition-point (*periodos*) (Ivanov, 2003; Kharlap, 1986; Mathiesen, 1985; Peponi, 2017; Quintilianus, 1983). Kharlap compares this *schēma-periodos* pairing (equivalent to pairing the arsis-thesis into a foot) with chess, where a move consists of two half-moves by each player. Such static “ceremonial” dancing gradually acquired greater fluidity, because unlike vocalized verses, changes of poses did not physiologically require pausing. Contemporary dance-based meters are usually fluid yet still incremental, albeit on a smaller scale – they run like frames in a motion-picture.

In contrast, syllable-based meters are not always incremental. In many tribal traditions, syllables are grouped flexibly into short and long classes, yet without the stable measurable ratios expected in quantitative metrics, so that from the standpoint of Western tactus-centered theory the resulting flow may reveal no clearly discernible metrical grid (Niemi, 2009). Phrasal and group boundaries might also be smoothed, with minimal accentuation. Alekseyev and Kharlap qualify such syllabic style as “coordination of beats.” In some cultures, it survives in the archaic sung genres (usually, epic songs and religious chants), while other genres develop compound organization. In advanced civilizations, syllabic versification can acquire a sophisticated hierarchical organization—even within monosyllabic languages like Chinese, where fixed syllable counts interact with line pairing, tonal patterning, and parallel couplet structure (Davis, 1975; Fränkel, 1976; Hui & Stock, 2023; A. Wang, 2023; B. Wang, 2025; Zhang & Song, 2013).

Another common beat-model comes from breath-groups. Breath-group-based organizations usually evolve from syllable-based meters through melismatic elaboration, stress-based grouping of unequal syllabic spans (“sprung rhythm”), aesthetic preference for smoothness, expressive solo delivery, or fast tempo. Alternatively, they emerge in textless vocalizations (Audios-22-25).

The distinction between syllable-based and breath-based beat hinges on grain size and articulation. In syllable-based organization, each phonetic syllable provides an incremental cadential unit; meter is counted syllable-by-syllable within a line, with caesura and rhyme demarcating larger groupings. Breath-based organization, by contrast, takes the entire breath-phrase—the span between two inhalations—as its primary unit, and the rise-and-fall contour of that phrase, rather than any internal syllable count, carries the metrical weight. The transition from syllabic to breathing grouping typically proceeds through increasing “vocal runs”: as syllables are drawn out across multiple pitches, the listener’s attention migrates from tracking syllables to tracking the arc of each breath-phrase. In many lamenting, ritual, and choreographic applications, a few syllables may extend across an entire breath-phrase, so that syllable-counting becomes secondary to phrase articulation.

Kharlap (1966, 1978, 1986) proposed the concept of “intonational rhythm” – i.e., free and asymmetrical alternation of tension/relaxation and arsis/thesis, usually accompanied by rise/drop in pitch – as a widespread form of versification in archaic folklore. Intonational rhythm is grouped into “intonational feet,”—breath-groups about 3–4 seconds long, variable in syllable count but durationally regularized by melismas, usually paired by the contrast between feminine and masculine endings, that is, cadences ending respectively on an unstressed or a stressed syllable. Grouping can not only be binary, but ternary and can include varied repetitions, forming complex contrasting relations between the breath-groups. Their segmentation can vary from barely noticeable to well-stressed and might complement or contradict the syntactic divisions of lyrics. Responsorial settings can bind breath-groups across parts by overlapping the phrases of soloist(s) and choir.

Kharlap’s intonational foot is not a metrical foot built from syllables but a cadential unit articulated by the breath, combining intonational arsis and thesis at the phrase scale rather than the metrical syllable scale. Subsequently, a breath-phrase in the text-based music uses substantially fewer syllables than a strophe in the syllable-based music (see Video-10).

Intonational feet are adjusted for specific genre applications: dance, lament, story-telling, prayer/invocation – which are usually syncretic (fusing versification, melopoeia, and locomotion). Songs often imply specific gestures that influence timing. Thus, Kodály noted that versions of the same song performed by the same person possessed different rhythms, when one performance was recorded in natural field conditions, where the performer freely moved, as opposed to singing in a fixed still position (e.g., sitting in front of the recording device).

Video-8. Yakut *Song of a Knight’s Horse* from the olonkho *Er Sogotokh*. Singing here is influenced by the dance, and in contrast to purely syllabic meters, syllables do not form a stressed pulse. The melodically smooth formula provides the only means of looking ahead. After a brief introduction, the 4-syllable formula kicks in. Its semi-strophe (notated as a bar) serves as a regular metrical unit—about 3-sec long (MM=20). Occasional 3- or 5-syllable words are fit into this formula by rhythmic contraction or expansion, adjusted to the style of a popular round-dance, the *osoukhai* (Aleksyev, 1996). Most breath-groups form a 6-sec-long binary “foot.”

Breath-groups can be consistently unequal and in slow tempo project the impression of stillness and absence of metrical pulse. This is quite common for solo odic or religious singing. Often, metrical regularity becomes noticeable only after a few minutes of listening.

Video-9. Tuvan *Kyzyl taiga*, a song about the red forest by Kaigal-ool Khovalyg, videoed by Theodore Levin. The music expresses the magnificence of the wide open space that encompasses a singer. The meter consists of two consistently alternating phrases: short (3-4 sec) and twice longer (4-8 sec). This formula can be regarded as an “intonational foot”.

Intonational feet can form compounds. Groups of feet are separated by hierarchical caesuras, whose duration reflects the complexity of compound structures and stresses strophic uniformity. Each strophe starts actively, anticipating a climax, and ends passively, fulfilling the expectation according to the strophe’s mean size. Such meters often implement strict formulaic structure to compensate for intra-strophic rhythmic flexibility (see Figure-5).

Once “intonational feet” are established in vocal traditions, their articulation may be transferred to instrumental practice. A historical analogue is found in psalmody shaped by *parallelismus membrorum* (Lowth, 1787/1969)—i.e., the segmentation of the text in Hebrew sacred poetry into balanced members that invites rhythmical articulation beyond purely melodic means. Parallelism may operate not only at the level of words, syntax, or meanings of verses, but also at the level of sounds and rhythms within and across verses as well as in larger, complex structures (Jakobson, 1966). Kharlap (1978) qualified *parallelismus membrorum* as a form of “intonational feet” and used it as an example of cultural transfer from vocal to instrumental music: 1) Sacred Hebrew psalms contained “intonational feet”; 2) their translation into Latin retained the intonational rhythm but lost the prosodic connection in psalmodic melodies, therefore delegating the intonational rhythm to the instrumental accompaniment; 3) after Gregory I abolished the instrumental accompaniment for psalms, the patterns formed during the practice of rhythmical accompaniment became autonomous of singing and followed its own course of development in instrumental music.

Kharlap’s theory was further elaborated by Russian ethnomusicologists, musicologists, and linguists (Alekseyev, 1976, 1986; Arkadyev, 1992, 2012; Chashchina, 2018; Gasparov, 1999, 2000; Kholopova, 1980, 1983, 2002; Zemtsovsky, 1967, 1987c). Similar theories of meter as a product of joining some structured prosodic units (“intonation unit,” “phonological phrase,” “breath unit,” or “rhythmic phrasing”) were proposed by Western specialists in prosody/versification (Attridge, 1995; Fabb & Halle, 2008b; Hanson & Kiparsky, 1996; Hartman, 1996; Hayes, 1989, 1995; Nespor & Vogel, 2007; Pinsky, 2000).

Collective labor provides yet another source for periodic pulse – similar to steps in dances but slower, if motion involves the entire body and is loaded. Worksongs accompany regular movements and reflect their characteristic patterning and timing to accommodate all participants (Banin, 1971, 1971; Bücher, 1924; Chijavadze, 2020; Gioia, 2006; Kyrgys, 1992). Their meter caters to the weakest participants.

Labor-intense songs often employ uneven pulse defined by their work-cycle and can gradually decelerate or accelerate as performers become tired or more enthusiastic. Thus, Georgian *Naduri* (hoeing) and *Elesa* (loading rocks), start very slowly with alternating antiphonal shouts accompanying the leader’s chant (Chijavadze, 2020).

Audio-10. Georgian worksong *Naduri* features a complex metrical pattern designed for hoeing. The soloists’ formulaic chant initiates the antiphonal response that consists of one long (5 sec.) and another short (3 sec) shouts. The latter overlaps with the leader’s solo. A longer cadence (8 sec) marks the end of the working cycle, which is repeated over. The song accelerates as it progresses, reaching its climax after 20-30 minutes.

Also, instrumental techniques provide metrical reference in some indigenous cultures. Thus, Chukchi and Eskimos model meter and melody on the regular tambourine strikes at a heart rate, divinizing the tambourine as a living creature who sets the order (Dobzhanskaya, 2016a; Sheikin, 1996, 2002, 2018). Other Siberian ethnicities use similar metrical modeling, by “sacred” canes, twigs, and musical logs. Such reference can be “de-constructive”: in shamanic *kamlaniye*, the tambourine beat might deliberately mismatch singing for the success of the shaman’s mission (Nikolayeva, 2006).

Audio-11. Nganasan bear *kamlaniye*. The tambourine pulse is deliberately modulated to disrupt singing. The tambourine is believed to serve as a shaman’s reindeer or horse in his ride to the underworld, while sung motifs usually represent souls of spirits or dead or live people. Metric modulations are supposed to bring a shaman from one encounter to another in his journey (Nikolayeva, 2006).

Some instruments, like bull-roarers (Baal, 1963; Fischer, 1986; Gourlay, 1975; Gow, 1934; Hagens, 2005; Kumbani et al., 2019; Morley, 2005; Schlatter, 1985) and big self-tolling bells (Burdorf, 2019; Kovacic, 2009; Price, 1983; Rombouts, 2014; Swager, 1993; Williams, 1985) set pulse through their mechanism of sound generation (Fletcher et al., 2002; Meneghetti & Rossi, 2010; Roger & Aubert, 1999; Woodhouse et al., 2012).

Bull-roarers have been used both solo and in ensembles in many parts of the world since prehistoric times, and bells since the Bronze Age. Ratchets, damarus, cabasas, and crotales generate periodic sounds too.

Audio-12. Bororo *aije*. This ritual uses bull-roarers and voices to represent evil spirits in the enactment of a burial to scare women and children, who must hide in homes (Canzio, 1989). Bull-roarers set a flexible pulse to provide a background for the faster pulse of vocal shouts. Similar ensembles with similar semantics are used by indigenous ethnicities of Siberia (Sheikin, 2002).

Finally, environmental sounds can provide the metrical pulse for singing. Horses' clip-clop, reindeers' click-clack, and harness-bell ringing accompany "road-songs" of Yakuts, Chukchi, Buryats, Mongols, Tuvans, Dolgans, Nenets, and Nganasans (Dobzhanskaya, 2016b; Dugarov, 1980; Illarionov, 2021; Sodnom, 1976; Tatarintsev, 1998; Vensten-Tagrina, 2008).

Audio-13. Tuvan *Xoomei* on horseback. Anatoli Kulaar and Kaigal-ool Khovalyg demonstrate how herders break into spontaneous *xoomei* (throat-singing) while riding horseback, so that their singing becomes synchronized to the horse's trot (Levin, 1999).

Different types of beats are not interchangeable. Different etiologies of beat do not merely favor different grouping principles; they also constrain the durational range within which a pulse can remain usable. Figure-4 summarizes these ranges across physiological, locomotor, musical, and work-related periodicities.

Figure-4. Durational ranges of common beat sources and musical pulse-types (based on experimental data and charts by Nazaikinsky (1972)). This figure compares the tempo ranges associated with physiological periodicities, locomotor rhythms, musical tempo categories, and selected functional song types, showing that different beat sources support different usable pulse ranges. **A)** The ranges of breathing and heart rate. **B)** The ranges of walking and running rates. **C)** The ranges of tempo in classical and folk music. **D)** Slow versus fast tempos as defined by professional classical musicians. **E)** The alternative distinction between “slowest,” moderate and “fastest” tempos,

according to classical musicians. **F)** The tempo ranges of rowing songs, scything worksongs, church bell-tolling, and articulations of speech. The curves reflect the relative frequency of distribution, where peaks mark the most common rate values – expressed in beats per minute.

Nazaikinsky (1972) discards the experimental findings of MM=38 (Bolton, 1894) and MM=20 (Stetson, 1905) as the slowest music pulse perceivable by humans, because both Bolton and Stetson used unmusical stimuli, whereas in music, long beats are always filled with salient acoustic changes of dynamics and timbre even in sustained sounds of a solo vocal performance. These changes not only attract listeners' attention and provide timing reference but trigger emotional response in listeners, which is known to affect their perception of duration and make “musical time” experientially and systemically different from “real-world time” (Arkadyev, 1992, 2012; Losev, 1995).

In practice, music is rarely restricted to purely monophonic setting—much more common are heterophony and monody. The former presents a single melody via a nexus of brief accidental deviations by different performers, whereas the latter supports the melody by dubbing it with a melodic instrument (e.g., lyre or lute) or accompanying it by a rhythmic instrument or clapping. In both cases, the long tones of a leading melody receive concurrent auditory changes from other parts that provide timing reference (plucking instruments, whose sound quickly decays, have to keep repeating the same pitch to retain their dubbing of the melody).

Bolton's and Stetson's experiments did not account for such typical musical settings, so their findings are only indirectly related to perception of beat in music. Two other often-cited studies of slow threshold also employed unmusical stimuli – electronic tones presented without any texture (Duke, 1989; Warren et al., 1991), which questions their validity for music. The third often-cited study by Parncutt (1994) inferred the threshold mathematically, without any empirical testing.

The often-cited range of usable tempos by Westergaard (1975)—MM=42-168—seems to be too conservative. Nazaikinsky (1972) reports that in his experiments at the Moscow Tchaikovsky Conservatory, expert conductors could sustain tempo within the range of MM=30-250 by resorting to special techniques in extremely slow and fast tempos. Some of Nazaikinsky's subjects conducted imagined music and reached MM=14-17.

Active generation of long periodicities might operate differently than *reflective* reproduction (tapping to the presented stimuli), tested by Bolton (1894), Stetson (1905), and Duke (1989). Warren's experiments (1991) were based on *passive* identification of familiar tunes and had no relation to rhythm-, timbre-, syllable-, and motion-based music. In contrast, Elkin's (1962) subjects (non-musicians) *actively* reproduced 5-second intervals (MM=12) with a 0.18-second mean error, whereas some musicians had no errors.⁵ Real or imagined subdivision is known to extend the tactus beat to slower rates (McAuley & Jones, 2003; Jones & Large, 1999; Repp, 2005; Repp & Su, 2013; Madison, 2006). Musical timing is never metronomic (see below). Perhaps, imagined or real “filling” of long sounds with some changes enables super-slow periodicities.

Worksongs often synchronize to complex movements of the entire body, thereby obtaining unevenly-timed patterns within every motion cycle. Rowing exemplifies the simplest uneven cyclic pattern: drive-recovery (1:2 ratio). The site *britishrowing.org* cites 18-24 strokes per minute as a typical rate for beginners and recreational rowers, which corresponds at its slowest margin to 3.3 sec per stroke. At the stroke rate of 3 sec, the drive-recovery ratio is 1:2, but at 1.5 sec rate, it shortens to 1:1.5. Recreational rowers are usually coached to row at MM=18-24. Purser (2024) analyzed Gaelic chanteys in relation to the typical rowing pace of Scottish boatsmen and inferred MM=25-30.

Breath-based meters in meditative genres often reach even slower tempos (MM=5).

⁵ Emil Gilels had an error of 100 msec reproducing “super-long” time intervals of 10, 15, and 30 sec. Mikhail Fichtenholz made no error reproducing 10 sec intervals, and erred just like Gilels in reproductions of 15 and 30 sec intervals.

Audio-14. Tibetan Tantric choir of Gyoto monks. Each phrase is 13 sec long (MM=5). This exceedingly slow tempo is sustained nearly perfectly for 8 minutes by all the participants. The solo of the priest leads the monks' responsorial. Participants seek to reach the state of bliss and enmesh with the deity Guhyasamaja. Their collective slow breath-based vocalization seems to carry a symbolic meaning of unification with the deity.

The breathing rate of slow Western folk singing commonly approximates MM=10-12 (Bernardi et al., 2017). Playing large wind instruments averages MM=6-12 per breath, and for oboe reaches MM=2 (Bouhuys, 1964). This gives an idea of how slow breath-based music can be. A good example is Russian "drawn-out" song that does not break into discrete rhythmic units/patterns other than verse and chorus (Zemtsovsky, 1967). I measured the durations of phrases in three LP albums of field recordings of Russian "drawn-out" (*protiazhnaya*) song. The median duration was about 6 sec – i.e., 10 breaths per minute. *Protiazhnaya* is the principal genre of Russian folk music that sets the timing style for many other lyrical genres.

Video-10. Russian "drawn-out" song *Nightingale, don't you sing*. A soloist sings the opening 11-syllable phrase on one breath (10 sec). The choir joins with the 10-syllable phrase (9 sec). The second verse is contracted to nine syllables (7.5 sec), but the chorus is extended by a varied repetition (9.5+9 sec). This genre is characterized by flexible aperiodic rhythm based on the "slowed down" pronunciation of syllables, compared by performers to "a flowing river with curvatures between hills" (Zemtsovsky, 1967). Syllabic articulation is smoothed to stress melodic continuity, initiated by the opening sing-out. It receives diverse elaboration throughout the song. The metric notation here is always arbitrary: bar-lines are placed at phrasal breaks of the lyrics and/or caesuras, and time signatures are often not indicated at all (Alekseyev, 1990).

Slowness and flexibility do not prevent multiple participants to stay in perfect sync. There is evidence that slow breath-based music can also induce entrainment (Will et al., 2015). Ethnographers report that listeners respond to breath-based songs by synchronizing their breathing to music—as long as their phrases share the same boundaries. The perception of breath-based music should be tested experimentally on listeners familiar with the relevant tradition and compared with responses of culturally naïve listeners.

Yet another etiology for breath-based meters is syllabic acceleration. Thus, Yakut introductions to *olonkho* epics often run at 400-500 syllables per minute, about as fast as *chabyrgakh*—tongue-twister song (Alekseyev, 1976, 1996). Turkish *tekerleme* is similar (Başgöz, 1998). Blistering speed calls for slower time-referencing units capable of measuring quick prosodic changes in the lyrics and accelerating or decelerating as needed. Breathing rate supports this flexible regularity.

Video-11. Yakut introduction from the *olonkho Er Sogotokh*. Traditionally, Yakut epics open with musicalized speech that differs from prosaic speech by exceedingly fast delivery, gesticulation, and use of melodic formula (usually ditonic) with prevalent ternary syllabic subdivision. Textual accents sometimes interfere with this formula. One syllable corresponds to one note. In this example, breath-groups last 15, 8, 8, 6, 2, 5, 6, 3, 12 sec (some extend the formula via inter-phrasal fragmentation), generating a nervous motion.

Audio-15. Yakut *chabyrgakh yryata*. Excited formula-based talking from time to time erupts into singing. Compared to the *olonkho* introduction (Video-11), here, breath-groups are shorter (8, 5, 4, 4, 4, 4, 2, 4, 5, 6 sec), have binary syllabic subdivision, are shaped into a tritonic formula, and feature gradual acceleration – all projecting a more active tempo than that in the *olonkho*.

Lightning-fast breath-rates of vocal music find their way into instrumental genres. Japanese *Kuchi-shōga*, Korean *Samulnori*, and Chinese *Kuaiban* drumming traditions use syllabing to attain virtuosic speeds, often featuring tongue-twisters (*ràokōuling*). Indian and African drumming traditions also employ additive syllabing to teach and practise virtuosic performance. Thus, Ewe use syllable-based "drum language" (Kwami, 1998; Locke & Agbeli, 1981) and reach speeds of about 750 strokes per minute (Polak, 2018).

The Issue of Ametrical Music

Most cases of ametrical music cited in the literature belong to syllabic, breath-based, and labor-accompanying meters. Their metrical organization will be evident, if:

- 1) we accept the ethnomusicological data on genre typology – since the same pattern of timing is transposed from one performance to another within a genre, it must feature some form of meter;
- 2) we apply to ethnic traditions the same tolerance for deviations that we adopt for Western music.

Even Western *tactus* – the tightest-controlled metrical system – is, in practice, never metronomic. Listeners find metronomic performances unmusical, and performers simply cannot play without expressive timing (Repp, 1990, 1995, 1998a, 1998b, 1999b).

Experimental research suggests that expressive timing is largely constrained by biological properties of human auditory perception and, therefore, is cross-cultural and arises as a function of musical structure. However, its variations in *shape* (modulation patterns) are influenced by cultural factors, as is evident in historical transformations of specific idioms (e.g., the practice of overdotting in Baroque vs Romantic music). Variations in the *extent* (amplitude) of expressive timing, by contrast, are driven primarily by individual differences among performers in production and among listeners in their sensitivity/tolerance for such deviations, although cultural conventions also help establish norms for acceptable timing deviation.

The relevant question, therefore, is not whether local durations vary, but how much variation listeners tolerate before rhythm, meter, or tempo is heard as having changed. Table-3 summarizes these approximate stability ranges from performance and experimental literature.

Table-3. Approximate stability ranges in temporal organization (Clarke, 1987; Dodson, 2002; Drake & Palmer, 1993; Fabian et al., 2014; Friberg, 1995; Friberg et al., 1985; Friberg & Battel, 2002; Goebel et al., 2004; Levitin & Cook, 1996; Madison & Merker, 2002, 2004; McAuley, 2010; Ravnani & Madison, 2017; Rector, 2021; Repp, 1998a, 1999a; Yang, 2022). This table summarizes the extent of local fluctuation within which a specific rhythm, meter, and tempo are usually perceived as remaining the same: for rhythm, at the scope of a few successive notes (the same vs different values); for meter, successive beats within a bar (weakly differentiated, as in simple meters, vs strongly differentiated, as in compound meters); for tempo, successive bars within a musical motion (bar groups containing similar vs different thematic content). Slower tempos decrease rhythmic precision and increase fluctuations.

Duration of:	Rhythm (notes)	Meter (beats)	Tempo (bars)
Homogenous units	+/- 6%	+/- 3%	+/- 8%
Contrasting units	+12% -8%	+13% (50%*)	+/- 20% (50%**)

* in specific genres (e.g., waltz); ** in cadential segments of the Romantic style music

Although research on expressive timing in non-*tactus* meters is scarce, estimates from recordings suggest that its range may approximate the limits within which *tactus*-based meter and tempo are still perceived as remaining the “same,” that is, as metrically regular. The tolerance for such deviations must be established empirically for each type of meter; let us call this the “metricity range.”

Irregularity must be distinguished both from expressive timing within a stable metric framework and from temporal modulation within a single musical work. The distinction depends on whether local durational deviations remain anchored to one ongoing beat organization. In beat systems with discrete recurring units, bounded deviation can be measured against those units directly. In breath-group or intonational organization, the task is more difficult, but the same principle applies: one must determine whether local contractions and expansions form a coherent modulation within a persistent phrase-pulse, or whether they instead involve genuinely shifting beat relations. Only in the latter case should the result be called irregular. The distinction will require comparison of adjacent phrase-internal durations and changes in breathing rate, in reference to the typical reactions of competent music-users.

Table-4. Common idioms of temporal modulation in rhythm, meter, and tempo. This table lists the conventional expressive means of classical music, which have capacity to alter the expression of a previously used rhythm, meter, or tempo. Rhythmic idioms are shown in notation (relative to a quarter-note beat). Metrical idioms refer to changes in barring structure. Tempo idioms refer to changes in pace and character of a musical motion.

Expression:	Rhythm (note groups)	MM =	Meter (measures)	Tempo (motion)
Activation	Beat-level short-long		Subdivision in >3 metrical levels	<i>Tempo giusto</i> (no <i>rallentando</i>)
	Sub-beat dotting		Composite meter	<i>Piū mosso</i>
	Reverse dotting		Asymmetrical meter	A faster tempo
	Double-dotting		Ongoing anacrusis	<i>Accelerando</i>
	Sub-beat syncope		Anacrusis becomes shortened	Frequent brief caesuras
	Roll/tremolo/trill		Shorter phrases	
Relaxation	Beat-level 'long-short'		Pronounced compound pulse	<i>Meno mosso</i>
	Straight subdivision		Pronounced hypermetric pulse	A slower tempo
	Super-beat dotting		Anacrusis becomes enlarged	<i>Rallentando</i> (easing up)
	Figuration		Ongoing groove	<i>Allargando</i> (growing bigger)
	Suspended syncope		Longer phrases	Rare long caesuras
Undulation	Hemiola		Alternating meter	<i>Tempo rubato</i>
	Sub-beat triplet		Combined meter	
Disruption	Beat-level syncope		Multi-part syncopation	<i>Ritenuto</i> (holding back)
	Beat-level triplet		Multi-part irregular divisions	<i>Colla voce</i>
	Off-beat		Periodic off-beats	<i>Tempo reggiato</i>
Conflict	Polyrhythm		Polymeter	<i>A scatti/Saccadé</i>
	Syncopation chain		Syncopation at >2 metrical levels	
	Cross-rhythm		Variable meter	
Release	Fermata		Pause/Caesura	<i>Tempo libero</i>
	<i>A piacere</i>		<i>A cadenza</i>	<i>Ad libitum</i>
	<i>Tenuto</i>		<i>Recitativo/Parlando</i>	

Reliable proxies of metrical organization are collective music-making and meaningful lyrics. Metrical coordination inevitably emerges whenever two or more performers must synchronize their parts in reproduction of the same kind of music – especially in monophonic music due to its transparency. Once synchronization arises in one genre, music-users become accustomed to it and apply to other genres. This can be subconscious, yet generate a perceptible “beat” in spontaneous interactions within a group, even when voiced vocalizations are purely verbal (Bowling et al., 2013). The example below illustrates how even spontaneous non-generic vocal interaction can generate a shared tonal center and pulse.

Video-12. Six Mongols playing dice (*shagai karvakh*) in Mandalgovı, Gobi desert. This is not a song or musical genre, but a spontaneous vocal interaction between players who are accustomed to the culture of “personal music” (Nikolsky et al., 2020) and impulsively vocalize throughout their daily life. The initial discrepancy of pitches reflects the differences in players’ mindsets and incentives. A sudden ascending leap of a player who threw the dice is gradually matched by sympathetic contenders. The disappointment of that player causes his pitch to glide down, prompting his fans to do the same. Their avid anticipation of the results of the next, more successful, dice-throw transpires into spontaneous raising of the pitch. The emerging tonal organization centers on E and exhibits a binary pulse at approximately MM=60.

In larger groups, voiced vocalizations become subjected to entrainment that gradually aligns participants around a shared pitch center and a shared beat.

Video-13. Crowd prayer. I ran the IBT/INESC Beat Tracker by Marsias in Sonic Visualizer and observed the emerging entrainment of both pitch and meter as the audio progressed. The crowd noise gradually converges toward B-flat and stabilizes at MM=75. A prolonged voiced interaction among a large number of people in an enclosed space is likely to generate similar pitch convergence and metric stabilization.

Spontaneous “metricization” (London, 2012) proceeds beat-to-beat, generating binary or ternary grouping. Bolton (1894) also reported a quaternary grouping, explaining the increase by faster tempo, greater attention, and richer experience of listeners. Listening to poetry also evokes subjective metricization in various groupings, determined by acculturation (Attridge, 1995; Fabb & Halle, 2008b). There is no reason to believe that non-tactus and non-syllabic meters cannot support metricization.

Syllabic metricization is omnipresent. There are no documented human languages whose structure prevents versification, and poetry is found in every known culture (Fabb & Halle, 2008a). Versification always exploits certain dimensions of language— syllables, morae, stress, tone, intonation, parallelism—to generate metrical structures. Some scholars have described Biblical Hebrew poetry as nonmetrical, but closer inspection reveals the prevalence of alternating stressed and unstressed syllables as staged by verse lines despite the absent lineation (Dobbs-Allsopp, 2015). Lineation and spacing, commonly used to distinguish poetic and prosaic speech, are just conventions of reading poetry from the scripted text and are unimportant for oral transmission. Some earliest manuscripts of Greek poetry have no lineation. Biblical metrics are organized by regular injection of pauses after every 2-3 (4) stressed syllables, where the intervening unstressed syllables are squeezed in-between the stressed ones. This results in a characteristic style of shaping the rhythms, which contrasts with narrative prose. Instead of symmetry of *feet*, fundamental for Western poetic tradition, the Ancient Egyptians and Canaanites developed a symmetry of *units* (Preminger, 2015).

Similarly, music traditions often characterized as “ametical” turn out to actually contain a metrical pulse, albeit flexible. Gregorian chant, for example, in living and historically informed performance traditions often exhibits a recurrent phrase-level pulse, occasionally lengthened by lexical stresses and interphrasal pauses (Biezen, 2016; Cardine, 1982; Van Kampen, 2022; Vollaerts, 1960). Whether this pulse was realized identically in early medieval performance remains debated, but many modern performances and some current reconstructions treat chant as pulse-bearing rather than ametical. I measured the tempo of Gregorian chant between phrasal caesuras in the soundtrack ‘Stetit Angelus’ (1998), performed by the Schola Gregoriana of Cambridge, an ensemble known for historically informed chant performance. Excluding pauses, the mean tempo was MM = 105.6, with a median deviation of about 27.9%, biased toward slowing. The extent of these fluctuations is comparable to that of many performances of Chopin (see Table 3).

Even liturgical recitative, classified by the Church as “reading” rather than chant, carries metrical organization, reflected by its *recto tono* (Fig.-5) – a one-strophe melodic formula used to fit the text according to the vocal capacities of a reader (Apel, 1958; Grigoryev, 2001; Hoeg, 1935; Troelsgard, 1988; Vladyshevskaya, 2006; Wellesz, 1961).

Audio-16. Apostolic recto tone. This supposedly ametrical recitation is organized by a relatively stable pulse of breath-phrases, each functioning as a strophic unit with proportionally distributed syllabic durations. Breath-phrases decelerate and then accelerate: 2.5-2.2-2.6-2.9-2.0-2.8 sec (MM=24-27-21-30-21)—forming the double wave. The formula always equals one strophe, and its duration is determined by one breath. Syllables are contracted or stretched to make the vocal phrase end on a period, comma, or the beginning of a new idea in the text. Apostolic tones require simple, strict, sustained, and stern delivery, stressing the pauses and assigning them different values based on their importance. Accents should fall on the tone most stable in pitch (Grigoryev, 2001).

Audio-17. The same recto tone, performed by a lower voice, featuring a different phrasing. The tempo here is consistently stretched: 2.4-2.9-3.3-4.0-4.4 s (MM=25-14), producing a more solemn impression than Audio-16, more suitable to the bass timbre. Both examples demonstrate how the same text can be parsed into different phrasal rhythms according to the vocal and registral characteristics and the performer’s understanding of the text and its mood. The differences include some phrases starting on the thesis while others on the arsis, and some phrases featuring a climax or a run-through towards the following phrase, while others are relaxing and halting.

Figure-5. Formulaic breath-based organization in liturgical and epic recitation. A) The waveform and spectrogram of the 2nd phrase from the Apostolic recto tone, taken on a single breath (from Audio-16). B) A simple recto tone for common liturgy, in the Kievan chant notation (Bogdanov, 1891). The formula is supposed to be voiced on a single breath. C) A standard formula for psalm tones in Gregorian chant and Jewish cantillations (including Persian, Yemenite, Babylonian, Sephardic and Ashkenazic varieties), likely following the recitative practice in Akkadian/Amorite poetry and later epics (West, 1997). I re-notated West’s example to show separately the 1st (half-close) and 2nd (full-close) strophes, each performed on a single breath. All three panels demonstrate structural similarity in breath-based metrical organization of the “intonational rhythms.” This organization is more flexible than foot-based meters and reserves space for improvisational “sprung rhythm,” but its formulaic repetitiveness does impose metrical regularity.

Such formulas are genre-specific, being reserved for specific types of texts in Catholic, Orthodox, and Jewish liturgies and notated in canonic codices by special paleographic signs next to the lyrics. Before their canonization these formulas were probably transmitted orally like the present-day epic Eurasian poetry and ancient Vedic texts (Jeffery, 1995; Karp, 1998; Lord, 2000; Saulnier, 2017; West, 1981). They all share formulaic structure and “intonational rhythm” faceted by caesuras.

In essence, any tradition of reciting voiced text is likely to feature some form of metrical organization – as with any tradition of collective music-making. This leaves little space for genuinely ametrical genres. Still, many clearly unmeasured forms of music are structured in reference to metrical music and are more accurately characterized as “*counter-metrical*.” These include unmeasured preludes/introductions to multi-movement suites. Quite a number of them only appear metrically free to an outsider unfamiliar with their cultural conventions, whereas, in reality, performers observe beats and either count them in a very slow tempo or distribute the beats between different parts. Such are ultra-slow yet counted Korean *jinyangjo* used to start *sinawi*; Chinese *manban*, where the time interval between words can last up to 5 min; and Japanese *tōgaku*, where biwa, koto, shō and taiko each mark different beats of the same metrical flow.

Semantically, these introductions rely on the next movement with the pronounced metrical organization, regarded as “principal,” both movements often interconnected. When a “principal” movement features asymmetrical meters, Western listeners might interpret an entire suite as “irregular” (e.g., *Nubah*). But for enculturated listeners, such introductions prepare, crystallize, warm up, offset, or build anticipation for the upcoming metrically expressive movement, thereby semantically relying on its metrical expression (“ethos”). Their temporal organization is better understood not as absence of meter, but as a deliberate suspension or withholding of metric articulation. The table below summarizes some common cases across different cultures (which suggests that the contrast between metrical freedom and order is a cross-cultural phenomenon). Calling such introductions “ametrical” seems unjustified, just as it would be misleading to describe a tonally indeterminate opening of an otherwise tonal composition as “atonal” merely because its harmonic center is initially withheld.

Table-5. Introductory genres whose metrical freedom is semantically defined in relation to the following measured movement. This table lists traditions whose opening movements are often described as ametrical or free-metrical but are followed by metrically definite sections to which they are semantically and structurally related (Alkai & Küssner, 2021; Feldman, 1993; Harich-Schneider, 1954; Hastano, 1985; Kahla, 2025; Kassebaum, 1987; Nettl, 1992; Sárosi, 1986; Wichmann, 1991; Widdess & Wolpert, 1981; Yamaya, 1998).

Culture	Free Introduction	Expression of the Introduction	Next Movement
Arabic	<i>Taqṣīm</i> or <i>Layālī</i> *	Self-reflective, introspective, creative meditation	<i>Muwashshah</i>
Andalusi	<i>Istikhbār</i> or <i>Mʻshaliya</i> *	Exploration of the mood of the upcoming movement	<i>Tuṣīya/Mizān</i>
Turkish	<i>Taksim</i> *	Emotional depth in dramatic development of an ambiguous mood	<i>Peşrev</i>
Persian	<i>Darāmad</i>	Preparing the mood of the next movement	<i>Gushe</i>
Hindustani	<i>Alap</i> * (→ <i>Jor</i>)	Contemplative conversing with the raga, setting its atmosphere	<i>Jhālā</i>
Carnatic	<i>Ālāpana</i> *	Unfolding the raga, often in stages, starting from afar	<i>Tānam</i>

Indonesian	<i>Pathetan</i> (→ <i>Buka</i>)	Introducing the mode and mood of the next movement	<i>Merong</i>
Chinese	<i>Sǎnbǎn</i> *	Generation of heightened drama to highlight the subject of lyrics in the upcoming vocal movement	<i>Manban/Yuanban</i>
Japanese	<i>Netori</i> or <i>Chōshi</i> *	Tranquil warming up, preparing the next movement	<i>Tōgaku</i>
Flamenco	<i>Toque libre</i> *	Dreamlike or explosive improvisation, contrasting the steady next movement	<i>Compás</i>
Hungarian	<i>Lassu</i>	Somber, brewing, stately or passionate, contrasting the next movement	<i>Friska</i>
Baroque	Unmeasured prelude	Anticipation of something important, crystallization of meter from rhythm	Allemande/Toccata

* Breath-based types of introduction.

Some virtuosic introductory solo preludes (*taksim*) can constitute independent compositions called to demonstrate technical proficiency and creativity. However, they usually retain the same syntax of gradual coalescence and the same preparatory function that they have within the suite.

Even on a broader scale, ametrical styles are often defined through metrical styles. In religious recitations, unmeasuredness stresses the metaphysical and supernatural origin of holy texts—in contrast to hymns based on “human” feet. Likewise, in animal spells, healing charms, protective conjurations, and ritual incantations, unmeasuredness is associated with unpredictable outcomes – in contrast to a predictable regular beat. In pastoral musicking (e.g., *kulning*), unmeasuredness signals safety and comfort to domestic animals—contrasting the stimulating effect of metrically regular music.

Audio-18. Kulning. A Swedish herdsman is calling her cows to return home from pasture. She alternates variations on the same melodic formula in a relaxed free timing with onomatopoeic imitations of dog barking to attract the cows’ attention and invoke associations with home. Besides the function of signaling safety, such vocalizations were supposed to deter predators and avert bad fortune (Nikolsky, 2020b).

As we see, semantically, the absence of (metrical) principle becomes a (metrical) principle.

Stand-alone (autonomous) ametrical traditions are rare and designed to convey some "metaphysical" content—to purge music of the "physical" associations with human traits (stepping, breathing, working, playing). The song in the example below deliberately avoids metrical predictability because its ritual function is to keep participants “in the dark” about the shaman’s actions.

Audio-19. Siberut song *Nangnangin* – i.e., a secret word, meaningless to Mentawai speakers, known only to shamans (*kerei*). Such shamanic songs are used to communicate with spirits during rituals, preparing medicines and collecting forest plants. These songs do not have rhythmic patterns. Singers (maximum of 5-6), who are apprentices, follow the unknown to them shaman’s melody, lagging behind. The melody differs from regular songs. Many words are archaic, deliberately distorted (epinthesis) to differ from regular speech, or are borrowed from little-known neighboring dialects. Siberut music culture is “personal” (like North-Eurasian and American indigenous music) – before colonization, choral singing was totally unknown (Persoon & Schefold, 2017). This song uses a complex formula made of three phrases: 8+13+15 sec (+/-1).

Deliberate avoidance of metrical predictability and regularity makes sense in genres expressing disorientation, helplessness, and dependence on external powers—usually religious or magic.

The most notable large-scale departure from metrically articulated practice is found in certain strands of postwar Western avant-garde composition (e.g., serialism).⁶ From Webern onward, some composers retained traditional western rhythmic notation chiefly as a technical means of coordinating ensemble performance, while deliberately avoiding audible patterns likely to project a beat. The trend of avoiding audible metrical pulsation emerged in the 1940s and started paralleling the earlier trend of avoiding harmonic structures capable of suggesting tonality (see Nikolsky (2019) for the historical review of ametrical avant-garde music). In this respect, such music appears historically exceptional rather than representative of long-term musical evolution. Its distribution has depended primarily on institutional support, specialist training, and score-based reproduction rather than on broad spontaneous uptake in everyday music-making. Moreover, the suppression of salient beat, genre markers, and recurrent surface cues may reduce ease of recognition and weaken their long-term transmission through ordinary social imitation. By the late 1990s, many of the principal adherents of serialism had publicly acknowledged its diminishing compositional viability. For these reasons, it seems better understood as a highly specialized modern aesthetic than as a durable alternative to the metrically organized traditions that dominate most musical cultures.

The Origins and Evolution of Temporal Organization in the Western Tradition

Having clarified the concepts and typologies of meter, rhythm, and tempo, we can now turn to plausible scenarios for the emergence of musical timing. The best documented and most extensively theorized case is the Western classical tradition, so it provides the most convenient starting point. This tradition ultimately derived from Sumerian and broader Near Eastern foundations and was later crystallized across the Near East, Southern Europe, North Africa, and the Caucasus, becoming associated with Christianity and accompanying its global spread. In its popularized forms, it now dominates much of the world's music. The earliest surviving account of its rhythmic theory comes from Aristoxenus (4th century BCE), and its metrical theory from Hephaestion (2nd century CE). Greek musical notation did not indicate duration, because ancient Greek was a quantitative language: vowel length was phonologically contrastive, and speech itself therefore generated clear rhythmic patterns.

Audio-20. Demodokos' song from *The Odyssey* (ca 8-7th centuries BCE). This reconstruction by Hagel and Danek (1995) illustrates a quantity-based temporal organization in which the epic text is fitted to regular repetitions of the same four-pitch formula, tuned to the accompanying 4-string lyre and rhythmized according to succession of long and short syllables. Such formulaic text-setting is characteristic of many Indo-European epic traditions, as well as some non-Indo-European ones.

From the 5th century BCE onward, verbal rhythms were grouped according to the kinetic principle. They were categorized into *arsis* and *thesis*—the upward and downward segments of time-beating using one's foot—and these were marked in musical notation (West, 1992). Feet and rhythms were assigned a specific *ethos* (character) based on the associated genres. Rhythmo-metrical units were grouped to form composite structures and composite semantics. *Agoge* (tempo) was a fixed attribute of characteristic rhythms.

The concept of *ethos*—the characteristic affective quality associated with particular melodic (*harmoniai*), metrical (*pódes*), or rhythmic (*rhythmoî*) models—is not unique to classical Greek theory. Analogous doctrines appear in Indian *rasa* theory (Rowell, 2015), Arabic *maqām*-based affect systems (Touma, 1996), Chinese modal characterologies (DeWoskin, 1982), Japanese *gagaku* modal associations (Garfias, 1975), Javanese *pathet* theory (Becker, 1980), and Ethiopian chant classifications (Shelemay et al., 1993). In the Mesopotamian theoretical tradition, terms for tuning scales, such as *išartum* and *qablītum*, appear to designate not merely

⁶ Free jazz is often brought up as an example of “meter-free” music. However, free jazz occupies a different position than classical music avant-garde, since even highly unmeasured passages often remain tethered to jazz performance habits in which percussion and ensemble interaction readily reintroduce pulse. Even where musicians start their music in a deliberate ametrical manner, as they become inspired and switch to faster tempo, drummers start using periodic patterns—voluntarily or involuntarily—due to techniques they acquired accompanying the conventional metrical forms of jazz.

abstract pitch collections but standardized melodic models associated with specific ethos (Dumbrill, 2005). West (1994) explicitly treats the Akkadian tuning names as functional analogues of Greek *harmoniai*.

The Greek music system was influenced by the Babylonian, which originated in Sumer (Crickmore, 2009a, 2009b; Franklin, 2002; Hagel, 2005; West, 1994). The extent of this influence is still debated, but the continuity between Sumerian and Greek music cultures in relation to organology, tuning, and modal theory is generally recognized by all specialists. At the most skeptical end of the debate, Hagel (2005) allows only a Hurrian influence on Greek music in the 2nd millennium BCE, after which Greek music theory took a different evolutionary path.⁷

Cuneiform tablets from Ugarit, containing Hurrian texts and Akkadian notation, describe the pitch aspect of Babylonian music theory. The durational aspect of Ugaritic was determined by a quantity system built on three vowel qualities, each contrasting in short and long form, as evidenced by the aleph-signs, cross-semitic comparisons, known vowel contractions, and Akkadian syllabic transliterations of Ugaritic words (Sivan, 2001). Akkadian, which remained a *lingua franca* of Mesopotamia throughout the 25th-8th centuries BCE, likewise had a quantity system based on four vowel qualities, each contrasting in short and long form, as revealed by syllabified cuneiform spelling (Hugenberger & Erickson, 2022).

Akkadian versification was based on counting not syllables but probably accentual peaks, where 4-accent periods with binary subdivision were standard, albeit featuring occasional deviations (West, 1997). Other metrical traits included balancing words and phrases within a verse, placing long syllables in the penultimate position, binary/quaternary grouping, and couplet repetitions. Poetry was sung to the accompaniment of a string instrument. Ugaritic poetry was more hierarchical than Akkadian: verse-lines consisted of 2-4 accentual “verse-units” and formed binary/ternary groups that functioned as an autonomous prosodic entity (West, 2003). Junctures must have been marked by vocal pauses and/or intonation to indicate varying degrees of completion – this possibly being formative for chanting.

In Ancient Egypt, the Demotic language probably contained long and short vowels. Loprieno (1995) argues that the Earlier Egyptian (3000-1350 BCE) opposed short and long vowels not phonologically but syllabically. Although Egyptian scripts did not indicate vowels, Coptic and Greek transcriptions of Egyptian words reflect their vocal system traceable to the New Kingdom. Coptic always stressed long (double) vowels and used rhymes in versification, and Demotic poetry was translated into Ancient Greek in three meters (Peust, 1999). Changes in vowel height, combined with alternation of short/long vowels, must have made Egyptian speech and lyrics inherently metrical, influencing instrumental music via vocal accompaniment—as is evident in copious images of musical time-beating.

Egyptian musicians played in bands (up to 12 participants), often accompanying dance, and were conducted by a music-master or cheironomist (25th century BCE, the earliest iconography). Multiple images with hieroglyphs indicate that hand gestures, clapping, stick-beating, clappers, and sistra were used for synchronization in banquet music, dancing, and ritual processions (Duchesne-Guillemin, 1981; Emerit, 2013; Garcia-Ventura et al., 2018; Hickmann, 1951; Kinney, 2008; Manniche, 1975, 1991). Egyptian music was probably shaped by Mesopotamian theory and practice via the importation of instruments, performers, and ensemble-settings.

All in all, the origins of metrical organization in versification and band music are traceable to the late 3rd millennium BCE. Spoken rhythm certainly preceded poetic meter. Speaking in verse is anomalous in ordinary communication because it imposes a conspicuous stylization on speech. Intonational rhythm might have existed even earlier, perhaps as far back as the 5th millennium BCE. Phonologists reconstruct quantitative vocal

⁷ Hagel, however, repeatedly stresses that theoretical systems and notational practices do not coincide automatically with musical practice, which remained shaped by different performance cultures in the Greek and Near Eastern worlds.

systems in Proto-Indo-European and Proto-Semitic (Blevins, 2007; Honeybone & Salmons, 2017; Huehnergard, 2019; Meier-Brügger, 2013). Contrasts of long/short vowels generate persistent rhythms.

The “time-beating” Egyptian and Mesopotamian instruments—sistrum and bells— also find rhythmic ancestors. Cowbells and horse-bells were used in prehistoric pastoral societies for magical, protective, purificatory and apotropaic purposes (Castelluccia & Dan, 2014; Eckardt & Williams, 2018; El-Hamid, 2015; Garfinkel, 2025; Kolltveit, 2008; Sterckx, 2000)—probably way before they earned their place in palace/temple orchestras. Jingle-ringing that accompanied the animal’s stepping must have revealed rhythmic capacities of the bells and suggested their musical use. There is evidence that circa 5th century BCE Zhou charioteers strived to drive steadily so that the harness bells rang harmoniously to please *Tian* (Heaven) (Sterckx, 2000). Many ancient civilizations understood music as reflecting or sustaining a larger cosmic order (Nikolsky, 2016c). Likewise, human necklaces, girdles, bracelets, and anklets, designed to rattle to steps, were used at least from the 14th century BCE to promote order, good luck and avert chaos and bad fortune (Barnes, 2015; Capel et al., 1996; Kenoyer, 1991).

Taken together, the available evidence suggests that metrical theory in the Bronze Age Near East arose from the convergence of three principal domains: linguistic patterning (vowel quantity, parallelism, and recitational formulas), locomotive patterning (dance steps, walking, and riding accompanied by jingling devices), and musical ensemble coordination. In the temple-palace cultures of Mesopotamia and Egypt, ensemble performance was subject to institutional supervision and was often understood as reflecting a religiously sanctioned order rather than mere practical convenience. Once stabilized in ritual and court practice, such principles of temporal organization diffused outward into solo repertoires and vernacular traditions through the imitation of high-status models within a strongly stratified social order.

Tempo, although known in Antiquity, was not understood as an autonomous aspect of expression. It was observed as the characteristic of rhythm: rapidity associated with prevalence of short notes, slowness with long notes. Most documented music of the Bronze Age was vocal and text-governed, and its temporal organization remained semantically referenced to speech rate, though with fewer accelerations and decelerations and with greater leisureliness than ordinary prose. According to West (1992), when the Greeks wanted slow music, they composed lyrics without short syllables. In a few instrumental genres they used, like the entrance of a choir to the stage in tragedy, the tempo of the procession had to match the expression of the upcoming singing. Compared to common speech rates, musical tempo was paced slightly slower and steadier (tempo *giusto* as opposed to the *parlando* of speech) due to the slight elongation of long syllables to increase their contrast to short syllables as a style of expressive timing. Each rhythm possessed an ethos that limited the range of appropriate tempos. This coherent Hellenic rhythm-metrical system began to disintegrate as medieval Latin and Greek lost phonological quantity.

A new metrical system emerged circa the 11th century in secular instrumental and vocal music in the accent-based vernacular European languages, first clearly attested in troubadour repertoires such as Occitan song and later elaborated in the rhythmic modes of the 12-13th centuries (Waite, 1954). As the Church sought to attract broader congregations, it increasingly admitted rhythmically patterned practices popular in vernacular song and conductus-like repertoires (Roesner, 2009). Secular versification influenced the Notre-Rame music theory, contributing to its growing metricalization (Fassler, 1987). Growing spread of musical notation and sight-reading was a chief contributing factor that distinguished the Western music tradition (Treitler, 1984). The growing importance of polyphony made modal rhythm indispensable for synchronizing parts that carried different melodies. Some ecclesiastical polyphonic genres (organum) retained the metrical freedom of earlier monophonic chant, whereas others (conductus) adopted the modal rhythm (Sanders, 1980). Different rhythmic modes were combined synchronously (polymodality) and sequentially, forming the so-called rhythmic “transmutations” (Corrigan, 1998). All in all, *Ars Antiqua* introduced systematic measurement of rhythm, setting a new impetus to apply quantifiable temporal succession to extended passages of music (Roesner, 1990).

Western music theory served primarily ecclesiastical genres, where *cantus firmus* (extracted from canonic chant) formed the backbone of multi-part composition. The need to stress canonic citations by longer rhythmic durations made composition inherently divisive, in contrast to the additive Greco-Roman composition. In the compositional practice, long notes of *cantus firmus* in tenor (from *tenere* – “hold”) were scored first, subsequently filled by shorter notes in other parts, where tenor supported them like a skeleton, and rhythmic divisions progressively diminished from the lowest tenor to the highest *motetus* (Clark, 2018; Leach, 2011; Yevdokimova, 1983). So, the higher parts were running against the slow steps of the lowest tenor. The multi-level rhythmic autonomy posed the need for a uniform time reference unit—and around 1260, Franco of Cologne codified *tempus* as the measure of sounded time and rest.

Another factor that marked the tenor was isorhythm. Throughout *Ars Nova*, the compositional technique for writing tenor used cyclic repetitions of a rhythmic formula (*talea*) to overlap the repetitions of the melodic formula (*color*). Isorhythm grew out of the earlier polymodal rhythm by expanding the repeated modal rhythmic patterns in the tenor (Harbinson, 1966; Hoppin, 1978; Lanford, 2011). Taruskin (2009) characterized *talea* as “maximodal” in distinction from the earlier modal rhythm. Early-15th-century motet abandoned the isorhythmic technique but retained the “bottom-to-top” rhythmic acceleration for the 4-part scoring (Cumming, 1999), which became a major compositional paradigm for sacred polyphony. However, throughout the 16th century, the *cantus firmus* technique became replaced by pervasive imitation, where repetitions were distributed between all the parts, making all parts rhythmically diverse.

The emergence and flourishing of *Musica Reservata* (Meier & Dittmer, 1956; Palisca, 1959) in the 16th century encouraged finer rhythmic division in the service of textual and affective expression (e.g., Janequin’s *La Guerre* (1528)). This trend culminated in the introduction of *passaggi* (Collins, 2001)—rapid ornamental note-divisions and runs—reconceptualized by Monteverdi (1638/2011) into the rhythmic idiom for heightened emotional excitement within his *Stile concitato* (“agitated style”). Its growing popularity resulted in adoption of more mobile note-division and more differentiated expressive verbal indications of character and motion. The prevalence of shorter note-values and the declining practical use of very long ones (*longa, maxima*) helped shift notational convention. Music printing, introduced in Europe in the late 15th century—beginning with liturgical books such as Ulrich Han’s *Missale Romanum* (1476)—also contributed to the stabilization and dissemination of revised mensural practice (Boorman, 2005). Musical publishers eventually changed the rhythmic notation from “white” (long notes) to “black” (short notes) by adopting the “brevis” (previously the shortest rhythmic value) as the longest note.

Further divisions, up to *semifusa*, shifted the rhythmic nomenclature towards further acceleration. The older *semibrevis* came to function as a new reference unit, equated with the “whole note” and adopted as the duration of the normative measure of so-called “common time.” This standard of measuring the music flow by dividing it into series of normative units was reflected in the emergence of the concept of *tactus*. It was understood as the recurring temporal pulse by reference to which note-values were proportioned, not a single invariant note-duration across all repertoires, though in many Renaissance contexts it was closely associated with the semibreve and likened to the pulse of a man breathing normally (DeFord, 2015). Tempo was considered slower, when longer notes prevailed, and faster when shorter divisions were prominent.

Duple and triple mensurations both remained important, and their distribution cannot be reduced to a simple opposition between secular and sacred practice, especially given the large body of orally transmitted dance and song repertoires outside learned notation. Even so, the mensural conception of a “normative *tempus*” and “proportional tempo” gradually weakened and disappeared in the late-18th century. Then, *tempos* became defined by their affective character in relation to the *tactus* beat suitable for a given genre (Chekhovich, 2011; Mattheson & Harriss, 1981; Quantz, 2001; Rothchild, 1979; Sachs, 1953). Musicians had to know the conventional expression of common genres to properly implement *tempos*.

Subsequently, composer's choice of note values became determined by the tempo: the faster the tempo, the longer the rhythm values; and vice versa (Dahlhaus, 1961; Kharlap, 1971; Kirnberger, 1776/1982). Chekhovich (2018) introduced the term “rhythmic tessitura” to refer to this dependence: high tessitura for the preference of short durations versus low tessitura for long durations. Hence, the choice of the beat value for the time signature started carrying semantic information (Table-2) related to the conventional tempo characters. Thus, Telemann in his *Gulliver's Travel Suite* TWV 40:108 (1728) humorously scored the *Lilliputsche Chaconne* in 3/32 (Baroque chaconne was renowned for its serious noble character) and the *Brobdingnagian Gigue* in 24/1 (gigue was a fiery commoner's dance). C.P.E. Bach's *L'irresolue* H.111 (1761) contains alternations between 3/8 and 3/4 to represent indecisiveness. Concerns for a better semantic correspondence between the beat value and the implied motion's character motivated composers to revise the denominator in their original time signature: e.g., 2/4→2/2 in Beethoven's *Klage* WoO 113 and *Ninth Symphony*, 2nd movement trio; or, 3/4→3/8 in Beethoven's *Fifth Symphony*, 2nd movement; 4/4→2/2 in Bach's *Prelude* BWV 893. Chekhovich (2018) proposed the term “tempo transposition” to refer to such modifications.

By the late 18th century, tempo indication operated through a shared conventional hierarchy. There was a shared core classification of tempo labels presented in a compact system of about 3-5 basic classes by music theorists and more finely graded ladder of 6-11 categories by pedagogues (Breidenstein, 2019; Crotch, 1831; Kharlap, 1971; Koch, 1802; Marty, 1988, 1988; Noorduyn, 2016; Rosenblum, 2007b; Rousseau, 1767; Sulzer, 1771/2013). But this orderliness turned out to be short-lived, becoming obsolete in the late 20th century. Already in the 19th century, many distinguished composers started writing tempo indications in their native languages instead of traditional Italian terms. In the 20th century, the usage of Italian terms (*Allegro*, *Adagio*, *Largo*) earned the reputation of implying neoclassical, academic, or historically authentic styles for the newly composed music, otherwise being outdated. Modern-day popular and light music notation resorts to metronome markings and instructions in English (or other native languages) that imply no conventional semantics.

Currently, conventional Italian tempo terms no longer function as the exclusive international code of musical expression that they were in the 18th and 19th centuries, although they remain widely used in notation and are still retained on modern metronomes. In this respect, Nazaikinsky (1965, 1972), elaborating on Garbuzov's (1950) experimental work, argued that musicians perceptually differentiate tempo not as a continuum but as a set of zones, whose number tends to remain around twelve. The historical Italian tempo vocabulary should not be equated directly with these perceptual zones, but the correspondence is suggestive: a finite conventional system of tempo names may well reflect a finite perceptual segmentation of the practically usable tempo range.

The latest evolutionary development of tempo in the Western classical tradition was its transformation from mere “musical speed” into a *function* of musical speed. The perceptual consequence is that identical pulse rates can project different tempo-characters when bar-length and metrical weight change (Video-14). In the late-Baroque, Classical, and 19th-century European repertory—especially in the tactus-based music of the Viennese classics—musicians estimate tempo by considering not only actual beat rate, but also the agogic “weight” of the beat and the number of beats per measure, that is, “bar density” (Chekhovich, 2011, 2020; Kharlap, 1971, 1978, 1997; Nazaikinsky, 1965, 1966; Ostrovsky, 1987; Sakhaltuyeva & Nazaikinsky, 1970). Kharlap (1971) first articulated this especially clearly in relation to Beethoven's rhythmic system, while Chekhovich (2011) argues that the broader conceptual shift can be traced back to the late 18th century and calls it a “New European tempo, inseparably linked with accented meter”. Arkadyev (1992) qualifies it as a part of the “New-European chronoarticulation system” that contrasts the preceding mensural system as much as the latter contrasted the quantitative system. Within this novel framework, stressing the beat requires slowing the pace to preserve the same conventional tempo-character (e.g., *Andante* should sound leisurely walking). Likewise, switching to longer measures requires a compensatory increase in pace.

Video-14. Expression of bar-length in tactus-based music. This example shows that perceived tempo-character changes when bar-length increases even when pulse rate remains constant. To isolate the expressive contribution of

different bar-lengths to the same pulse, I composed four excerpts using the same thematic material, texture, and harmonic style, locked to the same metronome speed and ternary pulse. **1)** 3/8 sounds busy and vigorous; **2)** 6/8 eases up but remains energetic; **3)** 9/8 loses momentum; **4)** 12/8, sounds rather relaxed—contrary to the tempo indication *Allegretto* (that worked well for the 1st excerpt). As the measure becomes longer, the same pulse begins to feel less active, so greater momentum at the downbeat is needed to sustain the musical motion.

The need to compensate for note-weight and bar-length was noted by many prominent 20th-century performers in the Western classical tradition. Kharlap argues that the cultivation of *tactus* introduced a new perceptual parameter of “virtual mass,” determined by metrical hierarchy and by the distribution of rhythmic durations within the bar. In his publications, he shows that 18th- and 19th-century composers and performers came to conceive tempo as a kind of “momentum,” that is, as the quantity of motion measured by the product of velocity and virtual mass. Metrical stress hierarchy is not the only factor shaping that mass: Nazaikinsky (1972) also includes dynamics, timbre, register, textural pulse density, harmonic rhythm, and phrase length.

In the mature Western *tactus* tradition of the 18-20th centuries, performers consider all these factors—including room acoustics and the response of particular instruments—when choosing an optimal tempo for a given composition, and the ability to do so is regarded as a high interpretive skill. Earlier pre-*tactus* repertoires, by contrast—whether chant, modal rhythm, mensural practice, or oral-traditional metric systems not governed by bar-based accentual *tactus*—did not require the same kind of compound estimation and were probably less individualized and more convention-bound.

Summing up, in Western tradition, theories of rhythm emerged first, followed by theories of meter and—much later—tempo theories that remain fragmentary, ambiguous, and far from consensual. The abstraction of tempo to the point where a composition can be transcribed into a different meter while preserving its perceived tempo—for example, recasting a march from 2/4 into 6/8—is a distinctive feature of Western compositional thought. Nevertheless, many Western tempo idioms (Table-4) have functional equivalents in other musical cultures within their own syllabic and quantitative metric systems.

The Origins of Temporal Organization in non-Western Traditions

Looking beyond the Western tradition is necessarily more conjectural. Ancient versification was preceded by undocumented folk versification, later overshadowed by the socially prestigious, literacy-based poetry and music of the first civilizations (Nikolsky, 2016b). One important route to reconstructing early temporal organization is therefore through folk poetry. Yet language does not exhaust the possible sources of temporal patterning: any such reconstruction must also consider bodily and social foundations. Songs are often linked to dance or characteristic bodily movement, making it difficult to disentangle the respective contributions of versification and locomotion to the formation of meter. Moreover, such major sources of metrical organization as bipedal locomotion and caregiver–infant interaction almost certainly predated the emergence of language. The reverse direction — possible influence of music on language — is also worth consideration, but falls outside the present article’s focus on musical timing. One possible case is the influence of Jaw-harp traditions on vowel harmony in northern Eurasia (Nikolsky, 2020a), but this influence concerns articulatory/timbral organization and morphonology rather than rhythm, meter, and tempo proper.

Folk versification follows its own evolutionary pathway, shaped by oral transmission but influenced by literacy-based arts. It usually proceeds from syncretic intonational rhythm to syllabic, quantitative, syllabo-tonic (accentual-syllabic), and tonic organization: first counting syllables, then distinguishing long and short syllables, then combining syllable count with regular stress placement, and finally organizing verse primarily by the number and distribution of stresses. Syllabic versification provides the general framework for the emergence of metrical theories, whether explicit in city-states or implicit in folk traditions.

The rhythms of the lyrics generated musical rhythms. Alekseyev, Zemtsovsky, and Kharlap studied this genesis in folk music in detail and concluded that the rhythmic syntax of the text forged rhythmic idioms in music, and metricized rhythm directly generated differentiation in pitch, forming recurrent pitch categories as well as metrical groupings. A pitch category that fell more frequently in metrically strong position acquired an anchoring function. Other pitch categories then became defined in relation to this anchor, forming a pitch-based musical mode. Such modes were associated with specific types of expression—for example lamenting or lulling—and conserved in conventionalized genres. The diagram below summarizes how verbal rhythm and phrase-organization can shape melodic grouping and initiate specifically musical semiosis that leads to music’s relative autonomy from lyrics.

Figure-6. From poetic phraseology to musical idiom (loosely based on the chart by Alekseyev (1976)). The arrows indicate parent-child relation. The grey rectangle encloses those aspects of organization that shape musical structures and influence their grouping. Neither the semantic, nor syntactic characteristics of the lyrics determine the syntactic and semantic characteristics of musical idioms. In fact, they often mismatch (a verbal phrase might be broken by a musical phrase, and sad lyrics might accompany a lively tune). Verbal intonation often mismatches melodic intonation. This is especially common for tone languages. Musical structures obtain their meaning, autonomous from lyrics, *after* melodic intonations become formulated and assigned to specific musical genres. Verbal rhythm forges melodic rhythm, initiating the musical semiosis (Zemtsovsky, 1983, 1987b, 1987c).

The Nivkh music tradition—one of the most archaic and best preserved in North Eurasia—offers an instructive example of how musical intonation can arise from speech-derived rhythmic organization (Mamcheva, 2012). Nivkh musical practice implements a set of rhythm-formulas extracted from sacred words and phrases associated with the Bear Festival, the most important annual ritual. These words accompany ritual drumming on the sacred log in a strict one-strike-per-syllable relation. At times, consonants are vocalized, producing a lighter syllable. Each strike reflects prosodic intonation, lexical accent, and salient phonological contrasts between syllables by varying the speed, force, angle, striking implement, and hand combination (e.g., stick against stick). These formulaic strike-patterns form parallel and rhymed strophes where the formulae are recombined and varied. The first strophe contains shorter rhythms, whereas the second—especially toward its close—longer

rhythms. This contrast metrically segments the flow of music. The resulting structures differ from those of ordinary Nivkh speech and have distinct expressive value. Nivkh genres are distinguished by these intonational rhythms and feet, while their expression often differs from the meaning of the prototypical sacred words.

Audio-21. Nivkh rhythmo-formulas on the sacred log. This example illustrates how speech-derived sacred formulas can be transformed into rhythmically organized strike-patterns that acquire distinct musical expression and genre-marking function.

Once intonational rhythms and feet become stabilized as genre markers, they open the way for tempo to acquire genre-specific expressive meaning. In folk music, tempo emerges as an affective distinction between the characteristically “happy” (lively) versus “sad” (slow) genres. This can occur within syllabic versification. Syllables often acquire quantitative differentiation, which puts in place a variety of tempos subserving the rhythmically contrasting genres. Versification can become entirely quantitative and build typologies of tempo. Neighboring traditions often borrow such typologies despite speaking non-quantitative languages (e.g., Turkic borrowings from the Arabic tradition). Remote traditions often escape such influences, keeping their tempos unscalable—optimized and bound to specific genres. Thus, Kodaly (1987) described Hungarian peasants not recognizing the very same tune used in slow sacred and lively secular songs, even when hearing them side by side. Evidently, the peasants did not “conserve” tempo as an autonomous entity. Their syllabo-tonic tradition fixed tempo to genre, so, to them, changing the tempo changed the genre, making a song “different.” Balkan epic singers stumble and lose their place if asked to repeat a song at a slower tempo (Lord, 2000).

In advanced civilizations, tempo typologies become theorized and abstracted, allowing the same metro-rhythmic structure to be rendered at different tempo levels. The Indian, Chinese, Korean, and Japanese traditions reached this stage earlier than Western classical music (Clayton, 2000; Malm, 2000; Provine, 2001; Rangacharya, 1996; Repetto & Serra, 2016; Wichmann, 1991). The Hindustani tradition comes closest to Western tactus. Hindustani music theory—like Western music theory—followed an evolutionary path from ancient asymmetrical meters based on quantitative versification to syllabo-tonic symmetrical meters. Like the Western tradition, it retained older asymmetrical genres and styles, albeit reserving for them much wider cultural space. Likewise, Hindustani music passed through a stage of “mensural” reference to a standardized beat-value before arriving at a more flexible temporal reference. However, in India, the concept of tempo was theorized earlier than in Europe, already in the *Nāṭyaśāstra* (2nd century BCE–2nd century CE). Like Western classical musicians, Indian musicians infer tempo by selecting the appropriate metrical level for the character of the music to be performed (i.e., the ethos of the *rāga*) and factor in the beat density and the ensemble setting. However, Indian musicians neither estimate the metrical weight of beats and subdivisions, nor observe anything like the “bar density.”

If syllabic and quantitative organization arise from language, breath-based and step-based organization may have followed a different route. Some of the earliest forms of meter must have depended less on text than on bodily coordination and social entrainment.

Bipedal walking is one of the strongest proxies for the emergence of meter. Modern-day indigenous gatherers sing while foraging to increase social cohesion for the new group participants. Collective walking induces beat-entrainment, which contributes to feeling togetherness, regularity, and predictability – turning rhythmized vocalizations into a safety signal (Chittar et al., 2023; Hayward, 2014; Jordania, 2008). Such walking vocalizations might have predated language. Furthermore, in hunter/gatherer societies, gathering is a female occupation, and women carry little children along, thereby exposing them to step/beat entrainment and securing trans-generational transmission of metrical perception. Also, mothers’ bipedalism probably contributed to the genesis of meter indirectly, via natural selection. Transforming infants’ feet from the grasping into weight-supporting organs reduced infants’ ability to cling to mothers, creating the need for motherese that involves metrically regular vocal and motor behaviors, like lulling, clapping, and moving the infant’s body parts (Larsson & Falk, 2025). Thereby, motherese can be linked to bipedalism.

Yet another meter-inducing application of bipedalism is the practice of deterring predators by loud sounds during foraging (Jordania, 2011, 2017, 2024; Knight & Lewis, 2017; Lewis, 2009; Salali, 2017). Crossing open spaces in the wild poses a risk of predatory attack, and loud collective vocalization may function as a deterrent by signaling coordinated group presence and making ambush less attractive. African gatherers often give this reason for their singing. Conversely, noise-driven “beat hunts” – from Patagonian ambushes (8th millennium BCE) to Mughal *shikargah* and Manchurian/Mongolian battue hunting – engage a crowd of beaters to direct the prey towards the hunters (Belardi et al., 2021; Parpia, 2016; Sasaki, 2015). Both hunting and deterrence must have generated metrical regularity via entrainment.

A parallel line of development may be represented by vocal traditions that are not organized by verbal text.

Not all vocal music appears to have developed through the progressive metricization of text. Obviously, syllabic music grew from languages. Breath-based traditions, however, might have preceded languages. Textless singing exists among Kartvelians, Abkhasians, Chuvash, Udmurt, Saami, Inuits, Udege, Ainu, Nanai, Nivkhs, Papuans, and Amerindians.⁸ Such wide distribution suggests that at least some textless genres may preserve vocal dispositions that predate later cultural differentiation. This possibility is compatible with theories of “musilanguage” (Brown, 2000) which posit an early communicative stage combining affective vocalization, prosodic organization, and expressive phrasing before the full divergence of language and music (Brown, 2017). Textless singing is commonly associated with animism/totemism via its magic, legendary, onomatopoeic, or ludic applications.

Audio-22. Inuit *katajjaq*. This example shows how regular metric pulse can emerge from competitive, textless, intonationally shaped vocalization rather than from the reproduction of a fixed texted structure. Two women maintain long regular rhythmized throat vocalization in a competitive game whose immediate aim is to see who can outlast the other. Similar games are found among Ainu, Chukchi, Koryak, Yupik, Yukaghir, Even, and Itelmen peoples. Here, regular pulse emerges from humorous, intonationally shaped phonation—often onomatopoeic—rather than from the reproduction of a fixed structure designed to convey a specific musical affect. Such games are usually not considered “singing” and are distinguished from “songs” in indigenous traditions. Their binary pulse gives some idea of meter in prelinguistic proto-music.

Audio-23. Ainu *rekuhkara*. Sonically and behaviorally similar to *katajjaq*, it differs in sound generation: one woman uses another woman’s mouth as a resonator, with the help of her hands that close and open. It has been explicitly connected to magic (Mamcheva, 2025). Here, the pulse is generated by the ritualized hand and body motions. This particular *rekuhkara* features a triple pulse.

Textless singing can carry regular metrical pulse, generated by breath-grouping, or be metrically free.

Audio-24. Ainu *sakehau* song. Such songs are performed solo during feasts in a deep throat voice (*raunkuttom*), associated with magic, with highly valued tremolo, and accompanied by foot-stamping and hand-swaying. *Sakehau* makes extensive use of vocables—timbral words or repeated syllables—which may constitute the entire song, as in this example (Mamcheva, 2025). Melodies use gliding pitch, contrasting registers, and metrically free organization. Sometimes, they are punctuated by isolated female exclamations of “au”.

Another source of textless singing is choreographic motion: from shouted dance accompaniment to expressive gestures paired with onomatopoeic imitation of animal calls. Such songs usually feature a motion-based regular metric pulse and may be supported by metronomic drumming or clapping.

Video-15. Koryak Seagull (*yakyakh*) dance-song. Koryaks use throat-singing to imitate animal calls and accompany textless singing with expressive motions representing these animals (*k’aring’ain’etyk*), in groups or solo (Zhornitskaya, 1983). Seagull imitation is especially popular. Similar practices are found across a wide

⁸ This list does not reflect the solfège-like syllabic singing traditions dedicated to teaching drums (India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Japan, Korea, Africa) or showing off the virtuosity of singers in solo episodes of music compositions (India, Turkey, Alpine yodeling). These traditions represent later evolutionary stages, when musical occupation becomes professionalized, and technical proficiency is rewarded.

region from the Arctic Ocean to Sakhalin among Yukaghirs, Chukchi, Eskimos, Ainu, Nanai, Ulchi, Evenki, and Itelmens.

Sung-out interjections, motoric laryngeal phonations, sonic games, and incantations/spells may preserve traces of prelinguistic proto-genres of music (Bowra, 1962; Marr, 1936; Sheikin, 1983, 2002; Werner, 1923; Zemtsovsky, 1983). Sheikin calls them “proto-singing” – i.e., vocalization unstructured by cultural conventions and “natural” in its psycho-physiological response patterns determined by anatomy (like animal calls or infant crying).

Wordless “personal song,” used like a personal name to identify individuals and track their ancestry and place of origin, might be another pre-linguistic link to animal territorial calls (Nikolsky & Benítez-Burraco, 2024).

Audio-25. Nivkh personal wordless song, performed while doing chores at home. Many Siberian and North American indigenous ethnicities retain the custom of representing a person by a specific melodic formula that reflects that person’s kin or place of origin. Singing such melodies is distinguished from singing conventional songs. Owners of “personal songs” often sing them without words to accompany their everyday activities (Nikolsky et al., 2020). When sung without words, formulas sound rhythmically vague and often interpolate improvisatory fragments. This gives some idea of rhythm in prelinguistic proto-music.

Audio-26. Nivkh personal song with words, performed by the same person for gathering berries. The same motif as in Audio-25 receives its rhythms from the syllables of the lyrics and follows the breath-based meter: phrases average about 5 sec, and their syllables serve as beats, about 0.8 sec long. Evidently, addition of text increases the metricity.

Personal song is not a “genre” in strict sense of this term. Personal songs lack functional, and thematic specification, are cross-cultural, and are not oriented toward the communication of musical affect or genre-specific affect, theme, or narrative content. Their structures are, at largest, only kin-specific. Their performance settings and reproduction framework are non-specific. Furthermore, their transmission is often short-chain, private, or one-time (accidental or just between two parties), which limits the regularizing effects of repeated communal reproduction across many performers and generations. This does not mean that they lack social function or evolutionary significance; rather, it means that they are not yet stabilized as genres for the communication of specifically musical affect and meaning. Ethnographic data suggest their functional range wider than that assumed in some communication-centered proto/musilanguage models. This ethnographic evidence should not be forced into the mold of any single musilanguage model. Rather, such models must be broad enough to account for vocal practices whose primary function is identificatory, ludic, or self-directed rather than the communication of codified musical affect.

Dance-songs, like *yakyakh*, are also not strongly delimited by culture-specific musical structures. Their sounds and motions are widespread across distant traditions not because a specific musical genre diffused intact across Eurasia, but because similar onomatopoeic and choreographic responses to a salient natural model can be recreated independently with relatively little culture-specific formal constraint. Such dance-songs are better qualified as a “proto-genre.” By the same token, widespread onomatopoeic imitation of domestic animals across many languages does not in itself constitute a folklore genre, since what is reproduced is primarily the natural model rather than a culturally stabilized form.

Yet another non-linguistic metrical source comes from tool-based sound production. Percussive sounds of phono-instruments – i.e., musically used common utilitarian objects, such as knappers, scrapers, rattles, grinders, etc. – likely attracted attention to rhythm and suggested its grouping (Blake & Cross, 2008; Bombardieri, 2019; Brown, 2024; Duffy, 2024; Montagu, 2004; Sheikin, 1996; Yesipova, 2008). Comparison of available archaeological evidence with stone tool-making practices among Australian Aboriginal groups suggests that production was often carried out on a substantial scale, with many knappers working together, dividing labor, and manufacturing tools for intertribal trade (Tibbett, 2005). Such ongoing collaboration was likely to entrain individual strokes, generate pulse, and promote the emergence of worksongs. Another possible source for the discovery of metrical regularity may have been fire-making, which is documented from the Early

Middle Pleistocene. Audible periodic scraping was reported in the Aboriginal sawing method of fire-making (Davidson, 1947). All of these are plausible proxies for the emergence of meter.

More broadly, the emergence of instrumental practice probably transformed musical evolution at several levels: it not only foregrounded pulse, grouping, and entrainment, but also introduced instrument-based sonic models for vocal and collective music-making, stabilized preferred timbres and pitch references, and eventually prepared the way for more explicit intervallic and metric standardization (Beliayev, 1990; Garcia-Ventura et al., 2018; Jenkins, 1983; Lawergren, 1988; Montagu, 2017; Morley, 2013; Rault & Brenton, 2000; Sachs, 1940; Vertkov et al., 1963; Zemtsovsky, 1987a). The course of the prehistoric evolution of music can be modelled as the succession of three stages, each characterized by cultivation of its own approach to sound grouping: 1) the “anthropophonic intonation,” determined by the anatomical capacities of the vocal apparatus and bodily sounds (clapping); 2) the “naturophonic intonation,” based on vocal imitations of the environmental sources, decoys, and phono-instruments; and 3) the “organophonic intonation” that adopts the sound of a specific musical instrument as a default model for melody-making, including vocal music, promoting the ensemble performance and establishing music cultures (Nikolsky & Benítez-Burraco, 2024).

Comparative evidence from animal communication helps delimit which components of temporal organization are broadly shared and which appear more specifically hominin. Meter is generally recognized as a human trait, uncharacteristic for animal communication. Thus, monkeys are sensitive to rhythm but not beat (Honing et al., 2018). A few species deter predators by vocalizations (gibbons and some mobbing birds), but even fewer coordinate their calls by structural interlocking (plain-tailed wren), so the emergence of synchronized deterrence chorusing sets hominins apart from other species (Fitch, 2024). Likewise, although tool use is widespread in the animal kingdom, tool manufacture is much rarer (among some apes, corvids, parrots, beavers, and elephants), and rhythmic use of tools appears restricted to apes only (Shumaker et al., 2011). These comparisons suggest that the conjunction of beat-based coordination, rhythmic tool use, and socially synchronized vocalization is unusual outside the hominin lineage.

The same applies to caregiver–infant interaction. Non-human primate mothers generally rely on gestural and tactile communication, rarely employing infant-directed vocalization (Amici & Liebal, 2025; Falk, 2004; Oller et al., 2019; Wegdell et al., 2025). The nearest analogues to motherese occur in macaques and marmosets, whose communication shows turn-taking and, importantly, some capacity for vocal learning through parental feedback, although it lacks the stable rhythmic regularity characteristic of human caregiver–infant interaction (Koda, 2008; Sclafani et al., 2023; Takahashi et al., 2017; Whitham et al., 2007). Vocal learning is itself a rare and important capacity in the animal kingdom, and it likely played a major role in the cultural evolution of human rhythm. Even so, the specifically hominin conjunction of bipedal foot-based pulse, motion-based caregiver entrainment, breath-based deterrent chorusing, and technique-based instrumental pulse remains distinctive.

Certain archaeological, anatomical, and behavioral proxies are sufficiently well-dated to allow a rough estimate of the major evolutionary landmarks relevant to the emergence of temporal organization in music. Fire-making became widespread 400 Ka. Anatomical capacity to sustain voiced sounds, enhanced breath control, and musical auditory capacities evolved around the same broad period. The Oldowan stone-tool industry spread between 2.4–1.7 Ma. Bipedalism became obligate by 3.6 Ma. Together, these dates suggest a timeframe for the genesis of meter (Figure-7). Rhythm is widespread across the animal kingdom, hence meter appears to be a later hominin specialization built upon rhythm.

Tempo emerged as a conventional autonomous aspect of musical expression no earlier than about two millennia ago. Ontogenetic development appears to follow the same general order in the acquisition of temporal organization in music: rhythm → meter → tempo. Available experimental findings, together with evidence from early music education—Dalcroze, Kodály, Orff, Suzuki, Yamaha, Gordon, and state ear-training programs in the

former USSR—suggest that children typically manifest rhythmic skills soon after birth, metrical skills around ages 3–5, and tempo-related skills around ages 5–9.⁹

Figure-7. Provisional timeline for the evolution of temporal organization in human music. The dates above the thick arrow and the text below it specify the landmark events in the evolution of rhythm (inherited from animal communication). The italic text enclosed in boxes names the aspects of musical timing related to the landmark events above. Curved arrows indicate the parent-child relation, dotted for the proxy connections. “Serial rhythm” is the only form of ametrical organization that has no “parent”: all other ametrical forms emerge either from pre-linguistic vocalizations or in counter-distinction to metrical forms. The text below the lower division line specifies how the landmark events (above) influenced the temporal organization. Three colors distinguish three evolutionary periods: 1) proxies of temporal organization (where the direct evidence for its presence is not available), 2) praxis of temporal organization (where there is some evidence of its practical use), 3) theory of temporal organization (the documented means of temporal organization).

In light of the foregoing discussion, I propose this provisional timeline as a starting point for its collective revision in musicologically precise terms. My aim is not to present a definitive model, but to invite multidisciplinary scrutiny, refinement, and correction. Such dialogue may help reduce the persistent gap between scientific and musicological accounts of musical timing, where shared terminology often masks substantially different conceptual frameworks.

Conclusion

This article has argued that the study of rhythm and its origins in human music requires a more precise musicological methodology than is common in current interdisciplinary research. In particular, rhythm, meter, and tempo must be treated as distinct aspects of temporal organization; their typology must be broadened beyond the tactus-based assumptions of Western classical theory; and their evolution must be reconstructed not from isolated structures, but from the interaction of structure, genre, function, transmission, and user competence.

⁹ The subject of ontogenetic evolution of time-related music skills needs a separate discussion. It is exceedingly common for educators and specialists in developmental psychology to describe patterns of “metrical” organization as “rhythmic” organization, to interpret fast “rhythms” in slow meters as fast “tempo,” or even to defy such concepts as compound meters (e.g., Edwin Gordon and his followers). Looking into the findings of such publications requires careful examination of the musical stimuli used in educational exercises and experimental studies, the presentation procedures, and the response of children. Only then does it become possible to correct the instances of misapplication of musical terms and to draw terminologically accurate conclusions from these publications. This task is tedious but can be very valuable for establishing the developmental patterns in musical timing. I review this issue in detail in my upcoming book “From Vocal Play to Tonal Systems: A Developmental Musicology of Childhood” (Nova Science Publishers).

From this methodological standpoint, the currently available evidence suggests a broad developmental sequence in which rhythm preceded meter, and meter preceded the full abstraction of tempo. Animal communication provides the preconditions for rhythm. Early hominin proto-genres: motherese, tool-making, and predator deterrence or hunting—made rhythm semiotically functional and likely prepared the ground for the emergence of first stabilized genres (e.g., lullaby, work song, hunting call, lament, prayer, and chant). Breath-groups, patterned motion, and intonational rhythm, cultivated within these genres, probably provided the earliest source for metrical organization. Stabilized and conventionalized metrical patterns likely found their way into other applications, such as totemic dances, funeral lamentation, chant/spells, and personal songs.

Emergence of language certainly added a new metricization source—at first through vocables, then timbral words, and finally text-based lyrics. Technological development added instrumental sources of pulse and grouping, while the growth of folklore and versification greatly expanded the range of metrical patterns and encouraged their classification. Literacy, canonization, professionalization, notation, ensemble coordination, and mathematically oriented theory then made metrical theories increasingly explicit, rational, and systematic, and eventually supported the abstraction of tempo as an autonomous aspect of musical expression. Even so, not all musical cultures treat tempo autonomously, and in some it remains tightly bound to genre.

Musical timing cannot be understood apart from the socially transmitted entities in which it is embedded. Music exists within cultures through the continuous circulation of recurrent musical entities—songs, dances, chants, recitations, and other conventionally recognized expressive units—within a community of music-users. The structures of these entities are shaped by the functions of their use via social conventions. Common functions that remain relatively stable over time become conserved into genres. Prolonged usage generates semantic qualia for the characteristic traits of common genres, thereby forming genre idioms. Generations of music-users learn genre idioms implicitly through continued participation, as these idioms keep changing together with the genres in their adaptation to environmental changes.

Ongoing transmission shapes the structural features of musical entities according to how they are understood by receivers. Receivers' competence depends on experience, skill, and attention. To maintain a musical tradition, receivers must know which structural features matter for a given function. Attention to genre-insignificant features, by contrast, introduces structural distortion into what is transmitted. Any account on musical evolution therefore requires tracing the synchronic and diachronic propagation of specific structures together with their semantic and pragmatic functions. Studying structures in isolation increases the risk of mistaking one structural type for another.

The structures of musical timing are no exception: like other musical structures, they are transmitted socially and require interpretation. Biological universals govern only the most basic level of temporal perception, its “atomic” layer. Higher, “molecular” levels are shaped by cultural convention through the semantic and pragmatic dimensions of communication. Experimental study and musicological analysis of musical timing therefore require examining structures together with their syntactic and semantic functions, in accordance with the conventions shared by their typical users. Using incompetent subjects in empirical studies or ignoring genre information in analysis may compromise the conclusions.

Furthermore, because affective engagement is central to most musical traditions, adequate emotional responsiveness in subjects and sufficient vitality in the chosen samples are imperative: beeps or MIDI melodies may fall short of eliciting ecologically valid responses. The choice of experimental stimuli is equally critical for the study of meter. Meter is multifactorial by design: its perception incorporates not only rhythm, but also dynamics, timbre, register, phrasing, texture, and harmonic pulse. Experimental stimuli that suppress these dimensions make beat extraction less reliable.

Understanding musical genres is important for any study of music. Most music exists through genres. Genres interact: an idiom created in one genre often penetrates other genres and receives a different development, acquiring an extra meaning. One genre can become canonized (e.g., religious or epic) and preserve archaic idioms, while another (social dance) rapidly changes due to accelerated transmission and professional competition in expressiveness, causing radical transformation of its idioms. The older a musical tradition, the greater historical shifts in its theoretical notions. Thus, the concepts of rhythm and meter in Western classical tradition reversed, leaving some genres conserved and some renovated. This creates confusion. Musicologists zoom into novel forms, whereas historians and metricians—into ancient forms, using the same terms to refer to different phenomena.

Tracking diachronic and synchronic changes in a music system requires careful translation of emic data into etic in all relevant genres:

- 1) identifying key structural features responsible for genre functionality,
- 2) establishing how these features are used by competent users,
- 3) inferring semantic characteristics ascribed to these structural features,
- 4) re-categorizing these structural features from emic to etic terms based on their functionality.¹⁰

For musical timing, this means that rhythm, meter, and tempo must be redefined as three autonomous aspects of temporal expression broad enough to cover all forms of music that organize durations in ways meaningful to their users. Tactus is only one such mode of organization. Developed historically within the Western literate tradition of notated composition and performance, tactus selects one recurring pulse in the metrical grid and marks it by bar-lines. Such practice was conducive to the emergence of tonality, because repeated metrical stress on certain pitch categories helped stabilize them as anchors against which other pitch categories were functionally defined. Users of orally transmitted music, alternative systems of notation, and non-literate consumers of Western music therefore often perceive tactus differently from schooled musicians—simplifying its hierarchical organization and missing much of its expressive characteristics (e.g., beat density and bar length). For this reason, evaluating pre-tonal meters by reference to tactus makes no more sense than analyzing ancient pitch systems in terms of “tonic,” “subdominant,” and “dominant.”

Those surviving forms of music that originated in non-tactus meters should be approached according to their original rhythm-metrical conventions, translated into modern etic terminology. This applies to foot-counted meters in lyric/epic poetry and dance, breath-phrases in religious chants, dance-figures in orchesography, and motion-cycles in worksong. Their beats can be isochronous, durationally contrasting (binary), or quasi-isochronous (agogic). Their tempo can be much slower than the tactus-tempo. Many genres considered ametrical by Western musicologists are, in fact, organized according to such meters. Perception of their timing should be carefully studied using appropriate recordings of music and competent subjects. Earlier research literature should be re-examined to identify misnomers involving meter, rhythm, and tempo. What is needed is a new synthesis of the available evidence, capable of redrawing the evolutionary pathway of temporal organization in human music.

The need for renewed synthesis is not only retrospective, but also prospective. The evolution of musical timing continues as new modes of transmission emerge, such as modern-day digital streaming. Their effects may become evident only over extended historical timescales. Transmission formats and rates, along with their conventions, efficacy, and mechanisms of error correction, play a central role in both the preservation and transformation of musical systems of tonal organization—especially temporal organization, which appears to depend on a broader range of shared reference models than pitch. Accurate and consistent categorization of patterns of temporal organization is therefore indispensable for maintaining continuity in the study of music

¹⁰ It is impractical and hardly possible to rely on the emic terminology in cross-cultural and evolutionary studies while adhering to the scientific method. See the opening table in my paper “The pastoral origin of semiotically functional tonal organization of music.”

across historical periods, geographic contexts, and disciplinary traditions. This paper aims to contribute to a more coherent accumulation of knowledge by providing a framework that supports such continuity.

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Bibliography

- Acevedo, S., Temperley, D., & Pfordresher, P. Q. (2014). Effects of Metrical Encoding on Melody Recognition. *Music Perception, 31*(4), 372–386. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2014.31.4.372>
- Afonasin, E., Afonasina, A., & Schetnikov, A. (2015). *ΜΟΥΣΙΚΗ ΤΕΧΝΗ: The essays on history of ancient music [Очерки истории античной музыки: Очерки истории античной музыки]*. RHGA.
- Afonina, N. (2002). Problems of analyzing rhythm [Проблемы ритмического анализа]. In N. Afonina (Ed.), *Rhythm and Form: Collection of Essays* (pp. 10–38). Artists Union.
- Akinbo, S. K. (2021). The Language of Gángan, A Yorùbá Talking Drum. *Frontiers in Communication, 6*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2021.650382>
- Alekseyev, E. Ye. (1964). The new in traditional styles of Yakut music folklore “dyiretii yrya” and degeren yarya’ [Новое в традиционных стилях якутского музыкального фольклора ‘дъиэрэтии ырыа’ и ‘дэгэрэн ырыа’]. *Proceedings of the VII International Congress, 7*, 319–337.
- Alekseyev, E. Ye. (1976). *Problems in the genesis of musical mode (on the example of Yakut folksong): Analysis [Проблемы формирования лада (на материале якутской народной песни): Исследование]*. Muzyka.
- Alekseyev, E. Ye. (1986). *Musical intonation in the earliest forms of folklore. The aspect of pitch [Раннефольклорное интонирование: Звуковысотный аспект]*. Soviet Composer.
- Alekseyev, E. Ye. (1990). *Notation of folk music: Theory and practice [Нотная запись народной музыки: Теория и практика]*. Soviet Composer.
- Alekseyev, E. Ye. (1996). On musical embodiment of olonkho [О музыкальном воплощении олонхо]. In N. V. Yemelyanov & R. B. Nazarenko (Eds.), *Yakut heroic epos “Mighty Er Sogotokh” [Якутский героический эпос “Могучий Эр Соготох”]* (Vol. 10, pp. 42–72). Nauka.
- Alkaei, Z., & Küssner, M. B. (2021). Taqsim as a Creative Musical Process in Arabic Music. *Frontiers in Psychology, 12*, 640409. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.640409>
- Allen, W. S. (with Internet Archive). (1973). *Accent and rhythm; prosodic features of Latin and Greek: A study in theory and reconstruction*. Cambridge University Press. <http://archive.org/details/accentrhythmpros0000alle>
- Alpatova, A. (2019). *Folk music culture. Archaic traits [Народная музыкальная культура. Архаика]* (2nd ed.). Yurait.
- Amici, F., & Liebal, K. (2025). Comparative perspectives on mother-infant communication in primates: Are humans unique? *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews, 176*, 106271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2025.106271>
- Ansani, A., D’Errico, F., & Poggi, I. (2019). ‘You will be judged by the music I hear’: A study on the influence of music on moral judgement. *Web Intelligence, 17*(1), 53–62. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WEB-190400>
- Apel, W. (1949). *The Notation of Polyphonic Music, 900-1600*. Mediaeval Academy of America. <https://www.amazon.com/Notation-Polyphonic-Music-900-1600/dp/0915651300>
- Apel, W. (1958). *Gregorian chant*. Indiana University Press.
- Aristoxenus. (1990). *Elementa rhythmica: The fragment of book II and the additional evidence for Aristoxenean rhythmic theory* (L. I. C. Pearson, Ed.). Clarendon Press.
- Arkadyev, M. A. (1992). *Temporal structures of European music of Modern Era. An attempt for phenomenological exploration [Временные структуры новейшей европейской музыки. Опыт феноменологического исследования]*. Muzyka.

- Arkadyev, M. A. (2012). *Fundamental problems of musical rhythm and the “inaudible”. Time, meter, notation, articulation. [Фундаментальные проблемы музыкального ритма и «незвучащее». Время, метр, нотный текст, артикуляция]*. Lambert Academic Publishing.
- Arnold, E. V. (with Robarts - University of Toronto). (1905). *Vedic metre in its historical development*. Cambridge, University press. <http://archive.org/details/vedicmetreinitsh00arnouoft>
- Arom, S. (1984). The Constituting Features of Central African Rhythmic Systems: A Tentative Typology. *The World of Music*, 26(1), 51–67.
- Arom, S. (2006). The Aksak Rhythm: Structural Aspects Versus Cultural Dimensions. In M. Baroni, A. R. Addressi, R. Caterina, & M. Costa (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference of Music Perception and Cognition* (pp. 1882–1883). University of Bologna.
- Attridge, D. (1995). *Poetic Rhythm: An Introduction*. Cambridge University Press.
- Baal, J. (1963). The cult of the bull-roarer in Australia and Southern New Guinea. (Met 2 platen en 2 figuren). *Bijdragen Tot de Taal-, Land- En Volkenkunde*, 119(2), 201–214. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90002136>
- Bamberger, J. S., & DiSessa, A. (2003). Music as embodied mathematics: A study of a mutually informing affinity. *International Journal of Computers for Mathematical Learning*, 8(2), 123–160. <https://doi.org/10/fhvzzf>
- Banin, A. (1971). *Work artel songs and refrains [Трудовые артельные песни и пруневку]*. Soviet Composer.
- Barker, A. (1991). [Review of *Review of Elementa Rhythmica, Aristoxenus*, by L. Pearson & Aristoxenus]. *Music & Letters*, 72(1), 71–74.
- Barker, A. (Ed.). (2004). *Greek Musical Writings: Volume 2, Harmonic and Acoustic Theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- Barnes, A. (2015). *Barnes On The Old Testament: Albert Barnes' Notes On The Whole Bible*. Baker Books.
- Başgöz, İ. (1998). *Turkish Folklore and Oral Literature: Selected Essays of İlhan Başgöz*. Indiana University.
- Becker, J. O. (1980). *Traditional music in modern Java: Gamelan in a changing society*. University Press of Hawaii.
- Belardi, J. B., Bozzuto, D. L., Fernández, P. M., Moreno, E. A., & Neme, G. A. (Eds.). (2021). *Ancient Hunting Strategies in Southern South America*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61187-3>
- Beliayev, V. M. (1971). *On musical folklore and ancient script systems [О музыкальном фольклоре и древней письменности]*. Soviet Composer.
- Beliayev, V. M. (1990). Modal systems in the traditional music of the USSR [Ладовые системы в музыке народов СССР]. In I. Travkina (Ed.), *Viktor Mikhailovich Beliayev [Виктор Михайлович Беляев]* (pp. 223–377). Soviet Composer.
- Berger, A. M. B. (2005). *Medieval Music and the Art of Memory*. University of California Press.
- Bergeson, T. R., & Trehub, S. E. (2006). Infants Perception of Rhythmic Patterns. *Music Perception*, 23(4), 345–360. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2006.23.4.345>
- Berlin, E. A. (1984). *Ragtime: A Musical and Cultural History*. University of California Press.
- Berliner, P. F. (1994). *Thinking in jazz: The infinite art of improvisation*. University of Chicago Press.
- Bernardi, N. F., Snow, S., Peretz, I., Orozco Perez, H. D., Sabet-Kassouf, N., & Lehmann, A. (2017). Cardiorespiratory optimization during improvised singing and toning. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 8113. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-07171-2>
- Berry, W. T. (1987). *Structural Functions in Music*. Dover Publications.
- Bezdek, M. A., & Gerrig, R. J. (2008). Musical emotions in the context of narrative film. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 31(5), 578–578. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X08005323>
- Bhattacharya, J., & Lindsen, J. P. (2016). Music for a Brighter World: Brightness Judgment Bias by Musical Emotion. *PLOS ONE*, 11(2), e0148959. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148959>
- Biezen, J. van. (2016). *Rhythm, Meter and Tempo in Gregorian Chant*. Lancelot Andrewes Press.
- Blake, E. C., & Cross, I. (2008). Flint Tools as Portable Sound-Producing Objects in the Upper Palaeolithic Context: An Experimental Study. In P. Cunningham, J. Heeb, & R. Paardekooper (Eds.), *Experiencing Archaeology by Experiment* (pp. 1–19). Oxbow Books.
- Blevins, J. (2007). *Evolutionary Phonology: The Emergence of Sound Patterns*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bogdanov, E. (1891). *A manual for ecclesiastical reading based on the traditional Ancient Church reading, transcribed intelligibly into music notation [Пособие к церковному чтению, положенное для вразумительности чтения на ноты на основании обычного древне-церковного чтения]*. Synod Publishing.
- Bolton, T. L. (1894). Rhythm. *The American Journal of Psychology*, 6(2), 145–238. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1410948>
- Bombardieri, L. (2019). Prehistoric Soundscapes: Mill Songs and the Music of Work in the Ancient Mediterranean and Near East. *American Society of Overseas Research (ASOR)*, 7(11).
- Boorman, S. (2005). *Studies in the Printing, Publishing, and Performance of Music in the 16th Century*. Ashgate.

- Botstein, L. (1992). Listening through reading: Musical literacy and the concert audience. *Nineteenth Century Music*, 16(2), 129. <https://doi.org/10/gf5t3t>
- Bouhuys, A. (1964). Lung volumes and breathing patterns in wind-instrument players. *Journal of Applied Physiology*, 19(5), 967–975. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappl.1964.19.5.967>
- Bouwer, F. L., & Honing, H. (2015). Temporal attending and prediction influence the perception of metrical rhythm: Evidence from reaction times and ERPs. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01094>
- Bowie, E. (2011). *Archaic and Classical Choral Song: Performance, Politics and Dissemination*. Walter de Gruyter.
- Bowling, D. L., Herbst, C. T., & Fitch, W. T. (2013). Social Origins of Rhythm? Synchrony and Temporal Regularity in Human Vocalization. *PLoS ONE*, 8(11), e80402. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0080402>
- Bowra, C. M. (1962). *Primitive song*. The World Publishing Company.
- Boyd, R., & Richerson, P. J. (2024). Cultural evolution: Where we have been and where we are going (maybe). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(48), e2322879121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2322879121>
- Braïloiu, C. (1951). Le rythme Aksak. *Revue de Musicologie*, 33(99/100), 71–108. <https://doi.org/10.2307/926002>
- Brandel, R. (1973). *The Music of Central Africa: Former French Equatorial Africa the Former Belgian Congo, Ruanda-Urundi Uganda, Tanganyika*. Springer Netherlands.
- Breidenstein, H. (2019). *Mozart's Tempo-System: A Handbook for Practice and Theory* (L. Friend, Trans.). Tectum Verlag.
- Briner, A. (1955). *Der Wandel der Musik als Zeit-Kunst*. Universal Edition.
- Brown, S. (2000). The “Musilanguage” Model of Language Evolution. In S. Brown, B. Merker, & N. L. Wallin (Eds.), *The Origins of Music* (pp. 271–300). MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e533412004-001>
- Brown, S. (2017). A joint prosodic origin of language and music. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8(OCT), 1894. <https://doi.org/10/gchkg7>
- Brown, S. (2022). Group dancing as the evolutionary origin of rhythmic entrainment in humans. *New Ideas in Psychology*, 64, 100902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.newideapsych.2021.100902>
- Brown, S. (2024). Beading for Beating: Body Percussion and the Interpersonal Origins of Rhythm. In J. Jordania (Ed.), *Defense Strategies in Early Human Evolution* (pp. 39–49). Logos.
- Bücher, K. (1924). *Arbeit und Rhythmus*. E. Reinicke.
- Burdorf, S. (2019). Alerting the Masses: An Inquiry into Buddhist Communication through Bells in Song Dynasty (960–1279) China from the Perspective of Material Culture and Sound. *Monumenta Serica*, 67(2), 319–361. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02549948.2019.1665826>
- Butler, M. J. (with The Archive of Contemporary Music). (2006). *Unlocking the groove: Rhythm, meter, and musical design in electronic dance music*. Indiana University Press. <http://archive.org/details/unlockinggroover00butl>
- Cameron, D. J., Bentley, J., & Grahn, J. A. (2015). Cross-cultural influences on rhythm processing: Reproduction, discrimination, and beat tapping. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00366>
- Canzio, R. (1989). *Brazil: Bororo World of Sound* (p. 14). UNESCO. D 8201
- Capel, A. K., Markoe, G., & Spanel, D. (with Internet Archive). (1996). *Mistress of the House, Mistress of Heaven: Women in ancient Egypt*. Hudson Hills Press. <http://archive.org/details/mistressofhousem00cape>
- Cardine, E. (1982). *Gregorian semiology*. Abbaye Saint-Pierre.
- Castelluccia, M., & Dan, R. (2014). Caucasian, Iranian and Urartian Bronze Bells. *Ancient Civilizations from Scythia to Siberia*, 20(1), 67–104. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15700577-12341261>
- Cespedes-Guevara, J., & Eerola, T. (2018). Music Communicates Affects, Not Basic Emotions – A Constructionist Account of Attribution of Emotional Meanings to Music. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 215. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00215>
- Chashchina, S. (2018). “Free” or “Intonation” Rhythm: To the Issue of Methodological Approaches in Contemporary Musicology [«Свободный» или «интонационный» ритм: К проблеме методологических подходов в современном музыкознании]. *The Journal of Russian Society for Theory of Music*, 2(22), 26–52.
- Chekanowska, A. (1988). *Etnografia Musiczna: Metodologia i Metodyka*. Pomorze.
- Chekhovich, D. O. (2011). On the evolution of the concept of tempo during the 18th-early 19th centuries. [К эволюции представлений о темпе в XVIII — начале XIX в.]. In S. V. Grokhotov (Ed.), *From Baroque to Romanticism. Musical epochs and styles: Aesthetics, poetics, performance interpretation. [От барокко к романтизму. Музыкальные эпохи и стили: Эстетика, поэтика, исполнительская интерпретация]* (Vol. 1, pp. 306–345). Moscow State Tchaikovsky Conservatory.
- Chekhovich, D. O. (2018). Rhythmic tessitura and tempo transposition [Ритмическая тесситура и темповая транспозиция ритма]. *Journal of Moscow Conservatory*, 32(1), 54–83.

- Chekhovich, D. O. (2020). Difficulties in comparing tempos and a new approach to their measurement [Лерко ли сравнить темпы?]. *Journal of the Society of Music Theory*, (1(29)), 44–86. <https://doi.org/10.26176/otmroo.2020.29.1.004>
- Chijavadze, O. (2020). *Worksongs in West Georgia [Shromis simgherebi dasavlet Sakartveloshi]*. Folklore State Centre of Georgia.
- Chittar, C. R., Jang, H., Samuni, L., Lewis, J., Honing, H., Loon, E. E. V., & Janmaat, K. R. L. (2023). Music production and its role in coalition signaling during foraging contexts in a hunter-gatherer society. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1218394>
- Christensen, T. (Ed.). (2008). *The Cambridge History of Western Music Theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- Clark, A. V. (2018). Tracing the Tenor in Medieval Motets. In J. C. Hartt (Ed.), *A Critical Companion to Medieval Motets* (1st ed., pp. 61–76). Boydell and Brewer Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781787442542.005>
- Clarke, E. F. (1987). Levels of structure in the organization of musical time. *Contemporary Music Review*, 2(1), 211–238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07494468708567059>
- Clayton, M. (1996). Free Rhythm: Ethnomusicology and the Study of Music Without Metre. *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies*, 59(2), 323–332. <https://doi.org/10/fwh3r9>
- Clayton, M. (2000). *Time in Indian Music: Rhythm, Metre, and Form in North Indian Rag Performance*. Oxford University Press.
- Clayton, M. (2020). Theory and Practice of Long-form Non-isochronous Meters: The Case of the North Indian *rūpak tāl*. *Music Theory Online*, 26(1). <https://doi.org/10.30535/mto.26.1.2>
- Collins, T. A. (2001). “Reactions against the Virtuoso.” Instrumental Ornamentation Practice and the Stile Moderno. *International Review of the Aesthetics and Sociology of Music*, 32(2), 137–152. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1562263>
- Cone, E. T. (1968). *Musical Form and Musical Performance*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Cooper, G., & Meyer, L. B. (1963). *The Rhythmic Structure of Music*. University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/R/bo24515499.html>
- Cornulier, B. de. (1995). *Art poétique—Notions et problèmes de métrique*. Presses universitaires de Lyon.
- Corrigan, V. (1998). Modal Transmutation in the Thirteenth Century. In D. Halperin (Ed.), *Orbis Musicae: Essays in honor of Hans Tischler* (Vol. 12, pp. 83–106). Tel Aviv University.
- Crickmore, L. (2009a). A possible Mesopotamian origin for Plato’s World Soul. *Hermathena*, 186(186), 5–23.
- Crickmore, L. (2009b). The tonal systems of Mesopotamia and Ancient Greece: Some similarities and differences. In R. Dumbrell & M. Marcetteau (Eds.), *The Archaeomusicological Review of the Ancient Near East* (Vol. 1, pp. 1–16).
- Crotch, W. (1831). *Substance of Several Courses of Lectures on Music: Read in the University of Oxford, and in the Metropolis*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cumming, J. E. (1999). Motets with a Tenor Cantus Firmus c. 1430–1450. In *The Motet in the Age of Du Fay* (pp. 206–227). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511481789>
- Dahl, P. (2009). The rise and fall of literacy in classical music: An essay on musical notation. *Fontes Artis Musicae*, 56, 66–76.
- Dahlhaus, C. (1961). Zur Entstehung des modernen Taktsystems im 17. Jahrhundert. *Archiv Für Musikwissenschaft*, 3/4(18), 223–240.
- Dale, A. M. (2010). *The lyric metres of Greek drama* (2nd ed). Cambridge University Press.
- Danek, G., & Hagel, S. (1995). Homer-Singen. *Wiener Humanistische Blätter*, 37, 5–20.
- Daubney, A., Spruce, G., & Annetts, D. (2019). *Music Education: State of the Nation. Report by the All-Party Parliamentary Group for Music Education, the Incorporated Society of Musicians and the University of Sussex*. All Party Parliamentary Group for Music Education.
- David, A. P. (2006). *The Dance of the Muses: Choral Theory and Ancient Greek Poetics*. Oxford University Press.
- Davidson, D. S. (1947). Fire-Making in Australia. *American Anthropologist*, 49(3), 426–437.
- Davis, A. . . R. . . (Ed.). (1975). *The Penguin book of Chinese verse* (R. H. Kotewall & N. L. Smith, Trans.). Penguin Books.
- DeFord, R. I. (2015). *Tactus, Mensuration and Rhythm in Renaissance Music*. Cambridge University Press.
- Devine, A. M., Stephens, L. D., Devine, A. M., & Stephens, L. D. (2008). *The Prosody of Greek Speech*. Oxford University Press.
- DeWoskin, K. J. (1982). *A song for one or two: Music and the concept of art in early China*. Center for Chinese Studies, University of Michigan.
- Djoudjeff, S. (1945). *Bulgarian folk choreography with a few examples from Macedonian folklore [Българска народна хореография съ няколко примъри изъ Македонския фольклоръ]*. Ministry of Folk Education.

- Djoudjeff, S. (1955). *The theory of Bulgarian folk music [Теория на Българската народна музика]* (Vols. 1–4). Science and Art [Наука и Изкуство].
- Dobbs-Allsopp, F. W. (2015). The Free Rhythms of Biblical Hebrew Poetry. In F. W. Dobbs-Allsopp (Ed.), *On Biblical Poetry* (pp. 95–177). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199766901.003.0003>
- Dobzhanskaya, O. E. (2014). *The singers and Songs of the Avam Tundra: Musical Folklore of Nganasan [Певцы и песни Авамской тундры. Музыкальный фольклор нганасан]*. Арекс.
- Dobzhanskaya, O. E. (2016a). Shamanic tambourine: A musical instrument or a riding reindeer of the shaman? [Шаманский бубен: Музыкальный инструмент или ездовой олень шамана?]. *Tomsk Journal of Linguistic and Anthropological Research*, 2(12), 81–90.
- Dobzhanskaya, O. E. (2016b). The Living Has Sound; The Dead Is Silent. *Anthropology and Archeology of Eurasia*, 55(1), 7–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10611959.2016.1263485>
- Dodson, A. (2002). Performance and Hypermetric Transformation: An Extension of the Lerdahl-Jackendoff Theory. *Music Theory Online*, 8(1). https://www.mtosmt.org/issues/mto.02.8.1/mto.02.8.1.dodson.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Dr. Sharma, P. L. (2007). *Sangitaratnakara of Sarngadeva: Sanskrit Text and English Translation with Comments and Notes* (R. K. Dr. Shringy, Trans.). Munshirm Manoharlal Pub Pvt Ltd.
- Drake, C., Jones, M. R., & Baruch, C. (2000). The development of rhythmic attending in auditory sequences: Attunement, referent period, focal attending. *Cognition*, 77(3), 251–288. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277\(00\)00106-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277(00)00106-2)
- Drake, C., & Palmer, C. (1993). Accent Structures in Music Performance. *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 10(3), 343–378. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40285574>
- Droit-Volet, S., & Gil, S. (2009). The time-emotion paradox. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences*, 364(1525), 1943–1953. <https://doi.org/10/cxj4bc>
- Droit-Volet, S., Ramos, D., Bueno, J. L. O., & Bigand, E. (2013). Music, emotion, and time perception: The influence of subjective emotional valence and arousal? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4, 417. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00417>
- Duchesne-Guillemin, M. (1981). Music in ancient Mesopotamia and Egypt. *World Archaeology*. (world). <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00438243.1981.9979803>
- Duffy, K. (2024). *The Role of Stone Tools in The Evolution of Music: Experimental Archaeology of Lithoacoustics* [Anthropology, University of Durham]. https://etheses.dur.ac.uk/15816/1/The_Role_of_Stone_Tools_in_The_Evolution_of_Music_Post_Exam_Corrected_.pdf?DDD5+=&utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Dugarov, D. S. (1980). *Buryat folk songs. Songs of the West Buryats [Бурятские народные песни. Песни западных бурят]*. Buryat Book Publishers.
- Duke, R. A. (1989). Musicians' Perception of Beat in Monotonic Stimuli. *Journal of Research in Music Education*, 37(1), 61–71. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3344953>
- Dumbrill, R. (2005). *The Archaeomusicology of the Ancient Near East*. Trafford Publishing.
- Dumesnil, R. (1949). *Le rythme musical: Essai historique et critique*. (2nd ed.). La Colombe.
- Earhart, W. (1946). *The Eloquent Baton* (5th ed.). M. Witmark & Sons.
- Eckardt, H., & Williams, S. (2018). The Sound of Magic? Bells in Roman Britain. *Britannia*, 49, 179–210. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0068113X18000028>
- El-Hamid, M. (2015). Shapes and Functions of the Bell in Graeco-Roman Egypt. *Journal of Association of Arab Universities for Tourism and Hospitality*, 12(1), 85–111.
- Elkin, D. G. (1962). *Perception of time [Восприятие времени]*. Russian Academy of Pedagogical Sciences.
- Emerit, S. (2013). Music and Musicians. In W. Wendrich (Ed.), *UCLA Encyclopedia of Egyptology* (Vol. 1, Issue 1, pp. 1–16). University of California Press. <http://digital2.library.ucla.edu/viewItem.do?ark=21198/zz002h77z9>
- England, N. M. (1964). Symposium on Transcription and Analysis: A Hukwe Song with Musical Bow. *Ethnomusicology*, 8(3), 223–233.
- Epstein, D. (1995). *Shaping time: Music, the brain, and performance*. Schirmer Books.
- Euclid. (1991). *The Euclidean Division of the Canon: Greek and Latin Sources with an Introduction, Annotations, and Indices* (André Barbera, Ed.; Vol. 8). University of Nebraska Press.
- Fabb, N., & Halle, M. (2008a). *Meter in Poetry: A New Theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- Fabb, N., & Halle, M. (2008b). *Meter in Poetry: A New Theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- Fabian, D., Timmers, R., & Schubert, E. (Eds.). (2014). *Expressiveness in music performance: Empirical approaches across styles and cultures*. Oxford University Press.
- Falk, D. (2004). Prelinguistic evolution in early hominins: Whence motherese? *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 27(4), 491–503. <https://doi.org/10/dvbfj5>

- Fassler, M. E. (1987). Accent, Meter, and Rhythm in Medieval Treatises “De rithmis.” *The Journal of Musicology*, 5(2), 164–190. <https://doi.org/10.2307/763850>
- Feldman, W. (1993). Ottoman Sources on the Development of the Taksim. *Yearbook for Traditional Music*, 25, 1. <https://doi.org/10.2307/768680>
- Fischer, H. (1986). *Sound-Producing Instruments in Oceania: Construction and Playing Technique—Distribution and Function* (D. Niles, Ed.; P. W. Holzkecht, Trans.). Institute of Papua New Guinea Studies.
- Fitch, W. T. (2024). Group Vocal Displays, Anti-Predator Behaviour and the Evolution of Musicality. In J. Jordania (Ed.), *Defense Strategies in Early Human Evolution* (pp. 15–34). Logos.
- Fletcher, N. H., Tarnopolsky, A. Z., & Lai, J. C. S. (2002). Rotational aerophones. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 111(3), 1189–1196. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1446053>
- Flett, J. F., & Flett, T. M. (1966). *Traditional Dancing in Scotland*. Vanderbilt University Press.
- Fränkel, H. (1976). *The flowering plum and the palace lady: Interpretations of Chinese poetry*. Yale Univ. Pr.
- Franklin, J. C. (2002). Diatonic Music in Greece: A Reassessment of Its Antiquity. *Mnemosyne*, 55, 669–702. <https://doi.org/10/d2vkvs>
- Friberg, A. (1995). *A quantitative rule system for musical performance* [Royal Institute of Technology]. <http://www.speech.kth.se/music/publications/thesisaf/sammfa2nd.htm>
- Friberg, A., & Battel, G. U. (2002). Structural Communication. In R. Parncutt & G. McPherson (Eds.), *The Science & Psychology of Music Performance: Creative Strategies for Teaching and Learning* (pp. 198–218). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195138108.003.0013>
- Friberg, A., Iwarsson, J., Jansson, E., & Sundberg, J. (Eds.). (1985). *SMAC 83: Proceedings of the Stockholm music acoustics conference July 28-August 1, 1983*. Royal Swedish Academy of Music.
- Garbuzov, N. (1950). *Zonal nature of tempo and rhythm [Зонная природа темпа и ритма]*. Academy of Science of the USSR.
- Garcia-Ventura, A., Tavolieri, C., & Verderame, L. (Eds.). (2018). *The Study of Musical Performance in Antiquity: Archaeology and Written Sources*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Garfias, R. (1975). *Music of a Thousand Autumns: Togaku Style of Japanese Court Music*. University of California Press.
- Garfinkel, Y. (2025). For whom the bell tolls: Horse harnesses at Megiddo and beyond. In *Rethinking Ancient Images from the Levant to Mesopotamia: Studies Offered to Tallay Ornan* (pp. 465–476). Archaeopress Publishing.
- Gasparov, M. L. (1996). *A history of European versification* (L. Holford-Strevens, Ed.; G. S. Smith, Trans.). Clarendon Press.
- Gasparov, M. L. (1999). *Meter and meaning. On one of the mechanisms of cultural memory [Метр и смысл. Об одном из механизмов культурной памяти]*. Russian state humanitarian university.
- Gasparov, M. L. (2000). *Studies in history of Russian verse. Metrics, rhythmic, rhyme, versification [Очерк истории русского стиха. Метрика, ритмика, рифма, строфика]* (2nd ed.). Nauka.
- Gertsman, Y. V. (1986). *Ancient music cognition [Античное музыкальное мышление]*. Muzyka.
- Gertsman, Y. V. (1988). *Byzantine musicology [Византийское музыкознание]*. Muzyka.
- Gioia, T. (2006). *Work Songs*. Duke University Press.
- Gjerdingen, R. O. (1989). Meter as a Mode of Attending: A Network Simulation of Attentional Rhythmicity in Music. *Intégral*, 3, 67–91.
- Goebl, W., Pampalk, E., & Widmer, G. (2004). Exploring expressive performance trajectories: Six famous pianists play Chopin’s pieces. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Music Perception and Cognition*, 505–509.
- Goodell, T. D. (1902). *Chapters on Greek Metric*. C. Scribner’s sons.
- Gourlay, K. A. (1975). *Sound-producing instruments in traditional society: A study of esoteric instruments and their role in male-female relations*. Australian Nat. Univ.
- Gow, A. S. F. (1934). Iynx, Rhombos, Rhombus, Turbo. *The Journal of Hellenic Studies*, (54), 1–13.
- Gracyk, T. (1996). *Rhythm and Noise: An Aesthetics of Rock*. I.B. Tauris.
- Green, L. (2002). *How Popular Musicians Learn: A Way Ahead for Music Education*. Ashgate Pub Ltd.
- Grigoryev, Ye. A. (2001). *A manual for the study of church singing and sight-reading [Пособие по изучению церковного пения и чтения]* (2nd ed.). Grebenshikov Old Orthodox Community.
- Håden, G. P., Bouwer, F. L., Honing, H., & Winkler, I. (2024). Beat processing in newborn infants cannot be explained by statistical learning based on transition probabilities. *Cognition*, 243, 105670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2023.105670>
- Hagel, S. (2005). Is nīd qabli Dorian? Tuning and modality in Greek and Hurrian music. *Mitteilungen Des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts. Orient Abteilung - Baghdad*, 36, 287–348.
- Hagel, S. (2009). *Ancient Greek Music: A New Technical History*. Cambridge University Press.

- Hagens, B. (2005). Timbre of the spheres: The bullroarer and the magic wheel. In Sethares, William A. (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Conference on Interdisciplinary Musicology (CIM05) Montréal, 10-12/03/2005* (pp. 1–11). University of Montreal.
- Halporn, J. W., Ostwald, M., & Rosenmeyer, T. G. (1980). *The Meters of Greek and Latin Poetry*. Hackett Publishing.
- Hammerschmidt, D., & Wöllner, C. (2020). Sensorimotor synchronisation with higher metrical levels in music shortens perceived time. *Music Perception*, 37(4), 263–277. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2020.37.4.263>
- Hammond, F. (1983). *Girolamo Frescobaldi*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674332195>
- Hannon, E. E., & Johnson, S. P. (2005). Infants use meter to categorize rhythms and melodies: Implications for musical structure learning. *Cognitive Psychology*, 50(4), 354–377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogpsych.2004.09.003>
- Hannon, E. E., & Trehub, S. E. (2005). Metrical Categories in Infancy and Adulthood. *Psychological Science*, 16(1), 48–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0956-7976.2005.00779.x>
- Hanson, K., & Kiparsky, P. (1996). A Parametric Theory of Poetic Meter. *Language*, 72(2), 287. <https://doi.org/10.2307/416652>
- Harbinson, D. (1966). Isorhythmic Technique in the Early Motet. *Music & Letters*, 47(2), 100–109.
- Harich-Schneider, E. (1954). *The rhythmical Patterns in gagaku and bugaku. [Mit Illustr. U. Notenbeisp.]*. Brill Archive.
- Harris, R. (2008). *The making of a musical canon in Chinese Central Asia: The Uyghur Twelve Muqam*. Ashgate.
- Hartman, C. O. (1996). *Free verse: An essay on prosody*. Northwestern University Press.
- Hastano, S. (1985). *The concept of pathet in Central Javanese gamelan music* [Department of Anthropology]. Durham University.
- Hasty, C. (1997). *Meter As Rhythm*. Oxford University Press USA.
- Haumann, N. T., Vuust, P., Bertelsen, F., & Garza-Villarreal, E. A. (2018). Influence of Musical Enculturation on Brain Responses to Metric Deviants. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 12, 218. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2018.00218>
- Hayes, B. (1989). The prosodic hierarchy in meter. In Kiparsky, Paul & G. Youmans (Eds.), *Rhythm and Meter* (pp. 201–260). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-409340-9.50013-9>
- Hayes, B. (1995). *Metrical Stress Theory: Principles and Case Studies*. University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/M/bo3621567.html>
- Haynes, B. (1997). Tu ru or not Tu ru: Paired Syllables and Unequal Tonguing Patterns on Woodwinds in the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Centuries. *Performance Practice Review*, 10(1), 41–60. <https://doi.org/10.5642/perfpr.199710.01.05>
- Hayward, G. (2014). *Singing as one: Community in synchrony* [Faculty of Music, Cambridge]. <https://www.researchgate.net/doi/10.13140/RG.2.1.1141.0640>
- Hickmann, H. (1951). Miscellanca Egyptologica. *The Galpin Society Journal*, 4, 25–29. <https://doi.org/10.2307/841259>
- Hoeg, C. (1935). *La notation ekphonetique* (Vol. 1). Levin & Munksgaard.
- Holden, R., & Vouras, M. (1965). *Greek Folk Dances*. Folkraft Press.
- Honeybone, P., & Salmons, J. (Eds.). (2017). *The Oxford Handbook of Historical Phonology*. Oxford University Press.
- Honing, H. (2012). Without it no music: Beat induction as a fundamental musical trait. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1252, 85–91. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2011.06402.x>
- Honing, H., Bouwer, F. L., Prado, L., & Merchant, H. (2018). Rhesus Monkeys (*Macaca mulatta*) sense isochrony in rhythm, but not the beat: Additional support for the gradual audiomotor evolution hypothesis. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 12(JUL). <https://doi.org/10/gdzd7n>
- Hoppin, R. H. (1978). *Medieval Music*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Houle, G. (1987). *Meter in music, 1600-1800: Performance, perception, and notation*. Indiana University Press.
- Huehnergard, J. (2019). Proto-Semitic. In N. Pat-El & J. Huehnergard (Eds.), *The Semitic languages* (Second edition, pp. 49–79). Routledge.
- Hugenberger, G. P., & Erickson, N. L. (2022). *Basics of Akkadian: A grammar, workbook, and glossary*. Zondervan Academic.
- Hui, Y., & Stock, J. P. J. (2023). *The Oxford Handbook of Music in China and the Chinese Diaspora*. Oxford University Press.
- Hummel, J. N. (1828). *A Complete Theoretical and Practical Course of Instructions on the Art of Playing the Piano Forte*. T. Boosey.
- Hunt, Y. (with Dragoumēs, M. P.). (1996). *Traditional dance in Greek culture*. Centre for Asia Minor Studies, Music Folklore Archive.
- Иlieva, A. (2007). *Theory and analysis of folk dance: Principles of structuring in Bulgarian folk dances [Теория и анализ на фолклорния танц. Принципи на формообразуването в българския танцов фолклор]*. Academic Publisher “Marin Drinov.”

- Illarionov, V. V. (2021). *Yakut folkloric fieldwork in the 1970-90s: Experience of scientific self-reflection [Якутская полевая фольклористика 70–90-х годов XX века: Опыт научной саморефлексии]*. Alaas.
- Ioannidou, A. (2009). Ancient Roots and Parallel Routes: The Internal Relationship between Byzantine Chant and Greek Folk Music. *Journal of Modern Hellenism*, (27), 153–169.
- Ivanov, V. V. (2003). Aesthetic heritage of Ancient and Medieval India [Эстетическое наследие древней и средневековой Индии]. In *Selected works on semiotics and history of culture. Comparative studies of literature. Versification* (Vol. 3, pp. 352–378). Slavic Culture.
- Iversen, J. R. (2016). In the beginning was the beat: Evolutionary origins of musical rhythm in humans. In R. Hartenberger (Ed.), *The Cambridge Companion to Percussion* (1st ed., pp. 281–295). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316145074.022>
- Jacoby, N., Margulis, E. H., Clayton, M., Hannon, E., Honing, H., Iversen, J., Klein, T. R., Mehr, S. A., Pearson, L., Peretz, I., Perlman, M., Polak, R., Ravnani, A., Savage, P. E., Steingo, G., Stevens, C. J., Trainor, L., Trehub, S., Veal, M., & Wald-Fuhrmann, M. (2020). Cross-Cultural Work in Music Cognition. *Music Perception*, 37(3), 185–195. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2020.37.3.185>
- Jacoby, N., & McDermott, J. H. (2017). Integer Ratio Priors on Musical Rhythm Revealed Cross-culturally by Iterated Reproduction. *Current Biology*, 27(3), 359–370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2016.12.031>
- Jacoby, N., Polak, R., Grahn, J. A., Cameron, D. J., Lee, K. M., Godoy, R., Undurraga, E. A., Huanca, T., Thalwitzer, T., Doumbia, N., Goldberg, D., Margulis, E. H., Wong, P. C. M., Jure, L., Rocamora, M., Fujii, S., Savage, P. E., Ajimi, J., Konno, R., ... McDermott, J. H. (2024). Commonality and variation in mental representations of music revealed by a cross-cultural comparison of rhythm priors in 15 countries. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 8(5), 846–877. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-023-01800-9>
- Jakobson, R. (1966). Grammatical Parallelism and Its Russian Facet. *Language*, 42(2), 399–429. <https://doi.org/10.2307/411699>
- Jeffery, P. (1995). *Re-Envisioning Past Musical Cultures: Ethnomusicology in the Study of Gregorian Chant*. University of Chicago Press.
- Jenkins, J. L. (1983). *Man and music: A survey of traditional non-European musical instruments*. Royal Scottish Museum.
- Jones, M. R. (2019). *Time Will Tell: A Theory of Dynamic Attending*. Oxford University Press.
- Jones, M. R., & Large, E. W. (1999). The Dynamics of Attending: How People Track Time-Varying Events. *Psychological Review*, 106(1), 119–159. <https://doi.org/10/d6qhrf>
- Jordania, J. (2008). Music and emotion: Humming in the beginning of human history. In R. Tsursumia (Ed.), *The Fourth International Symposium on Traditional Polyphony, Tbilisi, Georgia* (pp. 41–49). Nova Science. <https://doi.org/2008-26427>
- Jordania, J. (2011). *Why Do People Sing?: Music in Human Evolution*. Logos.
- Jordania, J. (2017). *A New Model of Human Evolution: How Predators Shaped Human Morphology and Behaviour*. Lambert Academic Publishers.
- Jordania, J. (2024). Music as aposematic signal: Predator defense strategies in early human evolution. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1271854. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1271854>
- Juslin, P. N. (2013). From everyday emotions to aesthetic emotions: Towards a unified theory of musical emotions. *Physics of Life Reviews*, 10(3), 235–266. <https://doi.org/10/f233sd>
- Juslin, P. N. (2019). *Musical Emotions Explained: Unlocking the Secrets of Musical Affect*. Oxford University Press.
- Kahla, A. el (with Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg). (2025). *Al-istikhbār as an idiom of performance in the Tunisian musical tradition: An indigenous ethnomusicologist's alternative perspective*. Verlag Dr. Kovač.
- Kallinen, K. (2006). *Towards a comprehensive theory of musical emotions: A multidimensional research approach and some empirical findings*. University of Jyväskylä.
- Karp, T. (1998). *Aspects of Orality and Formularity in Gregorian Chant*. Northwestern University Press.
- Kassebaum, G. R. (1987). Improvisation in Alapana Performance: A Comparative View of Raga Shankarabharana. *Yearbook for Traditional Music*, 19, 45. <https://doi.org/10.2307/767877>
- Katsanevaki, A. N. (2005). Archaic elements in the vocal musical tradition of the mountain populations of northern Greece: Results of research conducted among the Vlach-speaking and Greek-speaking populations of the mountain region of Northern Pindus, Greece. *Muzikologija: Časopis Muzikološkog Instituta Srpske Akademije Nauka i Umetnosti*, 5, 207–244.
- Katsanevaki, A. N. (2011). Chromaticism: A theoretical construction or a practical transformation? *Muzikologija: Časopis Muzikološkog Instituta Srpske Akademije Nauka i Umetnosti*, 11, 159–180. <https://doi.org/10/dvdtgb>
- Katz, J., Chemla, E., & Pallier, C. (2015). An Attentional Effect of Musical Metrical Structure. *PLoS ONE*, 10(11), e0140895. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0140895>

- Kazarova, M. R. (1935). Lazarnica. *Journal of the English Folk Dance and Song Society*, 2, 62–72.
- Keller, P. E., & Schubert, E. (2011). Cognitive and affective judgements of syncopated musical themes. *Advances in Cognitive Psychology*, 7(1), 142–156. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10053-008-0094-0>
- Kenoyer, J. M. (1991). *Ornament Styles of the Indus Valley Tradition: Evidence from Recent Excavations at Harappa, Pakistan*. 17(2), 79–98. <https://doi.org/10.3406/paleo.1991.4553>
- Kharlap, M. (1966). *On verse [О смухе]*. Art Literature.
- Kharlap, M. (1971). Beethoven's rhythmic system [Ритмика Бетховена]. In M. Fishman (Ed.), *Beethoven* (pp. 370–421). Muzyka.
- Kharlap, M. (1972). Traditional Russian musical system and the problem of origin of music [Народно-русская музыкальная система и проблема происхождения музыки]. In Y. Meletinskii (Ed.), *Early forms of art [Ранние формы искусства]* (pp. 246–247). Iskusstvo.
- Kharlap, M. (1978). The Tactus System of Musical Rhythmics [Тактовая система музыкальной ритмики]. In V. Kholopova (Ed.), *The Problems of Musical Rhythm: Collection of Essays [Проблемы музыкального ритма: Сборник статей]* (pp. 48–104). Muzyka.
- Kharlap, M. (1986). *Rhythm and Meter in Music of Oral Transmission [Ритм и метр в музыке устной традиции]* (Matters of history, theory, and methodology). Muzyka.
- Kharlap, M. (1997). Duration of musical notes and the paradox of their actual value: Memos on the specificity of musical timing and its notation. [Нотные длительности и парадокс их реального значения: Заметки к специфике музыкального времени и его нотации]. *Musical Academy [Музыкальная Академия]*, 1, 170–181.
- Kholopov, Y. (1999). On ancient rhythmics. The methodology of musical-phonetic transcription [Об античной ритмике. Метод музыкально-фонетической транскрипции]. *Music in oral transmission*, 16–22.
- Kholopov, Y. (2006). *Musical-theoretical systems [Музыкально-теоретические системы]*. Kompozitor.
- Kholopova, V. (1971). *Problems of rhythm in works of the 20th century composers [Вопросы ритма в творчестве композиторов XX века]*. Muzyka.
- Kholopova, V. (1980). *Musical Rhythm [Музыкальный ритм]* (Matters of history, theory, and methodology). Muzyka.
- Kholopova, V. (1983). *Russian musical rhythmics [Русская музыкальная ритмика]*. Soviet Composer.
- Kholopova, V. (2002). *Theory of music: Melos, rhythm, texture, thematicism [Теория музыки: Мелодика, ритмика, фактура, те-матизм]*. Lan.
- Kim, M., & Schachner, A. (2023). The origins of dance: Characterizing the development of infants' earliest dance behavior. *Developmental Psychology*, 59(4), 691–706. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001436>
- Kinney, L. (2008). *Dance, Dancers and the Performance Cohort in the Old Kingdom*. British Archaeological Reports.
- Kirnberger, J. P. (1982). *The Art of Strict Musical Composition* (D. Beach, Ed.; J. Thym, Trans.). Yale University Press. (Original work published 1776)
- Kleeman, J. E. (1985). The Parameters of Musical Transmission. *The Journal of Musicology*, 4(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.2307/763720>
- Knight, C., & Lewis, J. (2017). Wild Voices: Mimicry, Reversal, Metaphor, and the Emergence of Language. *Current Anthropology*, 58(4), 435–453. <https://doi.org/10.1086/692905>
- Koch, H. C. (1802). *Musikalisches Lexikon*. August Hermann dem Jüngern.
- Koda, H. (2008). Short-Term Acoustic Modifications During Dynamic Vocal Interactions in Nonhuman Primates—Implications for Origins of Motherese. In N. Masataka (Ed.), *The Origins of Language* (pp. 59–73). Springer Japan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-4-431-79102-7_5
- Kodály, Z. (1987). *Folk music of Hungary* (Lajos. Vargyas, Trans.). Da Capo Press.
- Kolinski, M. (1949). *Folk Music of Palestine* [LP notes]. Folkways Records.
- Kolltveit, G. (2008). Animal Bells in Early Scandinavian Soundscapes. In E. Hickmann, J. Orlamünde, & R. Eichmann (Eds.), *Studies in Music Archaeology VI. Current Challenges and New Objectives in Music Archaeology* (pp. 147–153). Marie Leidorf.
- Kotz, S. A., Ravnani, A., & Fitch, W. T. (2018). The Evolution of Rhythm Processing. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 22(10), 896–910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2018.08.002>
- Kovacic, M. (2009). The Use of the Church Bell: From Signaling Device to Musical (Percussion) Instrument. In G. Jähnichen (Ed.), *Studia Instrumentorum Musicae Popularis* (pp. 109–122). Monsenstein und Vannerdar.
- Kramer, J. D. (1988). *The Time of Music: New Meanings, New Temporalities, New Listening Strategies*. Schirmer Books.
- Kremenliev, B. (1952). *Bulgarian-Macedonian folk music*. University of California Press.
- Krims, A. (2000). *Rap Music and the Poetics of Identity*. Cambridge University Press.

- Krumhansl, C. L. (1997). An exploratory study of musical emotions and psychophysiology. *Canadian Journal of Experimental Psychology = Revue Canadienne De Psychologie Expérimentale*, 51(4), 336–353. <https://doi.org/10/bz3xtq>
- Krumhansl, C. L. (2002). Music: A Link Between Cognition and Emotion. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 11, 45–50. <https://doi.org/10/bcm3fn>
- Kumbani, J., Bradfield, J., Rusch, N., & Wurz, S. (2019). A functional investigation of southern Cape Later Stone Age artefacts resembling aerophones. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 24, 693–711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2019.02.021>
- Kvitka, K. V. (1971). *Selected Works [Избранные труды]* (V. L. Goshovsky, Ed.; Vol. 1). Soviet Composer.
- Kwami, R. (1998). Towards a Comprehensive Catalogue of Eve Drum Mnemonics. *Journal of African Cultural Studies*, 11(1), 27–38.
- Kyrgys, Z. K. (1992). *Singing culture of Tuvan people [Песенная культура тувинского народа]*. Tuvan Book Publishing.
- Lanford, M. (2011). A Reevaluation of Isorhythm in the “Old Corpus” of the Montpellier Codex. *College Music Symposium*, 51, 1–17.
- Larsson, M., & Falk, D. (2025). Direct Effects of Bipedalism on Early Hominin Fetuses Stimulated Later Musical and Linguistic Evolution. *Current Anthropology*, 66(2), 257–278. <https://doi.org/10.1086/734554>
- Lawergren, B. (1988). The origins of musical instruments and sounds. *Anthropos: Internationale Zeitschrift Für Völker- und Sprachkunde*, 83(1–3), 31–45.
- Leach, E. E. (2011). The Fourteenth Century. In M. Everist (Ed.), *The Cambridge Companion to Medieval Music* (pp. 87–103). Cambridge University Press.
- Lebedinsky, L. N. (1965). *Bashkir folk songs and instrumental patterns [Башкирские народные песни и наигрыши]*. Muzyka.
- Lerdahl, F., & Jackendoff, R. S. (1985). *A Generative Theory of Tonal Music*. MIT Press.
- Lester, J. (1986). *The Rhythms of Tonal Music*. Pendragon Press.
- Levin, T. C. (1999). *Tuva, Among the Spirits: Sound, Music, and Nature in Sakha and Tuva* (p. 23). Smithsonian Institution. SFW 40452
- Levitin, D. J., & Cook, P. R. (1996). Memory for musical tempo: Additional evidence that auditory memory is absolute. *Perception and Psychophysics*, 58(6), 927–935. <https://doi.org/10/dsvv7f>
- Lewis, J. (2009). As well as words: Congo Pygmy hunting, mimicry, and play. In R. Botha & C. Knight (Eds.), *The Cradle of Language* (pp. 236–256). Oxford University Press/Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780199545858.003.0013>
- List, G. (1974). The Reliability of Transcription. *Ethnomusicology*, 18(3), 353–377. <https://doi.org/10.2307/850519>
- Little, M. E. (2001). Gavotte. In *Grove Music Online*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.10774>
- Locke, D., & Agbeli, G. (1981). Drum Language in Adzogbo. *The Black Perspective in Music*, 9(1), 25–50. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1214103>
- Logeswaran, N., & Bhattacharya, J. (2009). Crossmodal transfer of emotion by music. *Neuroscience Letters*, 455(2), 129–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2009.03.044>
- London, J. (2012). *Hearing in Time: Psychological Aspects of Musical Meter* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Longuet-Higgins, H. C., & Lee, C. S. (1984). The Rhythmic Interpretation of Monophonic Music. *Music Perception*, 1(4), 424–441. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40285271>
- Loprieno, A. (1995). *Ancient Egyptian: A linguistic introduction*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lord, A. B. (2000). *The Singer of Tales* (S. Mitchell & G. Nagy, Eds.; 2nd ed.). Harvard University Press.
- Losev, A. (1995). Music as a subject of Logic [Музыка как предмет логики]. In *Form—Style—Expression [Форма—Стиль—Выражение]* (pp. 405–570). Mysl’.
- Love, S. C. (2016). Historical Hypermetrical Hearing. *Music Analysis*, 35(2), 142–170. <https://doi.org/10.1111/musa.12058>
- Lowth, R. (1969). *Lectures on the Sacred Poetry of the Hebrews*. G. Olms. (Original work published 1787)
- Lumaca, M., & Baggio, G. (2018). Signaling Games and the Evolution of Structure in Language and Music: A Reply to Ravnani and Verhoef (2018). *Artificial Life*, 24(02), 154–156. https://doi.org/10.1162/ARTL_a_00258
- Lumaca, M., Haumann, N. T., Vuust, P., Brattico, E., & Baggio, G. (2018). From random to regular: Neural constraints on the emergence of isochronous rhythm during cultural transmission. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, 13(8), 877–888. <https://doi.org/10/gd73qc>
- Maas, P. (1962). *Greek metre*. Oxford Clarendon Press.

- MacGregor, P. (1968). *Highland Dancing: The official textbook of the Scottish Official Board of Highland Dancing*. (2nd ed.). Thomas Nelson & Sons.
- Madison, G. (2006). Experiencing Groove Induced by Music: Consistency and Phenomenology. *Music Perception*, 24(2), 201–208. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2006.24.2.201>
- Madison, G., & Merker, B. (2002). On the limits of anisochrony in pulse attribution. *Psychological Research*, 66(3), 201–207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-001-0085-y>
- Madison, G., & Merker, B. (2004). Human sensorimotor tracking of continuous subliminal deviations from isochrony. *Neuroscience Letters*, 370(1), 69–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2004.07.094>
- Madison, G., Ullén, F., & Merker, B. (2017). Metrically Structured Time and Entrainment. In M. Lesaffre, P.-J. Maes, & M. Leman (Eds.), *The Routledge Companion to Embodied Music Interaction* (1st ed., pp. 22–30). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315621364-3>
- Magill, J. M., & Pressing, J. L. (1997). Asymmetric Cognitive Clock Structures in West African Rhythms. *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 15(2), 189–221. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40285749>
- Malloch, S., & Trevarthen, C. (2009). *Communicative musicality: Exploring the basis of human companionship*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Malm, W. P. (2000). *Traditional Japanese Music and Musical Instruments* (Vol. 1). Kodansha International.
- Mamcheva, N. A. (2012). *Musical instruments in the Nivkh traditional culture [Музыкальные инструменты в традиционной культуре нивхов]*. GUP Sakhalinskaya Regional Press.
- Mamcheva, N. A. (2025). *The world of Ainu music* (Vol. 1). Ostrovnaya Library.
- Manniche, L. (1975). *Ancient Egyptian musical instruments*. Deutscher Kunstverlag. <http://archive.org/details/ancientegyptianm0000mann>
- Manniche, L. (with Internet Archive). (1991). *Music and musicians in ancient Egypt*. British Museum Press. <http://archive.org/details/musicmusiciansin0000mann>
- Marr, N. Ya. (1936). *Selected works [Избранные работы]* (Vol. 2). The USSR Academy of Sciences.
- Martens, P. A. (2011). The Ambiguous Tactus: Tempo, Subdivision Benefit, And Three Listener Strategies. *Music Perception*, 28(5), 433–448. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2011.28.5.433>
- Marty, J.-P. (1988). *The Tempo Indications of Mozart*. Yale University Press.
- Mathiesen, T. J. (1985). Rhythm and Meter in Ancient Greek Music. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 7, 159–180. <https://doi.org/10.2307/745886>
- Mathiesen, T. J. (1999). *Apollo's Lyre: Greek Music and Music Theory in Antiquity and the Middle Ages*. University of Nebraska Press.
- Mattheson, J., & Harriss, E. C. (1981). *Johann Mattheson's Der vollkommene Capellmeister: A revised translation with critical commentary* (E. C. Harriss, Trans.). UMI Research Press.
- Matthews, T. E., Vuust, P., & Cannon, J. (2026). An Active Inference Model of Meter Perception and the Urge to Move to Music. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1556(1), e70129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.70129>
- Mazel, L. (1952). *On melody [О мелодии]*. Gos Muz Izdat [State Musical Publishing].
- Mazel, L. (1979). *Structuring of musical works [Строение музыкальных произведений]* (2nd ed.). Muzyka.
- Mazel, L., & Tsukkerman, V. (1967). *Analysis of Musical Works [Анализ музыкальных произведений]*. Muzyka.
- McAuley, J. D. (2010). Tempo and Rhythm. In M. Riess Jones, R. R. Fay, & A. N. Popper (Eds.), *Music Perception* (Vol. 36, pp. 165–199). Springer New York. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-6114-3_6
- McAuley, J. D., & Jones, M. R. (2003). Modeling effects of rhythmic context on perceived duration: A comparison of interval and entrainment approaches to short-interval timing. *Journal of Experimental Psychology. Human Perception and Performance*, 29(6), 1102–1125. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-1523.29.6.1102>
- McAuley, J. D., & Semple, P. (1999). The effect of tempo and musical experience on perceived beat. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 51(3), 176–187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049539908255355>
- McKinney, M. F., & Moelants, D. (2006). Ambiguity in Tempo Perception: What Draws Listeners to Different Metrical Levels? *Music Perception*, 24(2), 155–166. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2006.24.2.155>
- Mehr, S. A., Singh, M., Knox, D., Ketter, D. M., Pickens-Jones, D., Atwood, S., Lucas, C., Jacoby, N., Egner, A. A., Hopkins, E. J., Howard, R. M., Hartshorne, J. K., Jennings, M. V., Simson, J., Bainbridge, C. M., Pinker, S., O'Donnell, T. J., Krasnow, M. M., & Glowacki, L. (2019). Universality and diversity in human song. *Science*, 366(6468), eaax0868. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax0868>
- Meier, B., & Dittmer, L. A. (1956). The Musica Reservata of Adrianus Petit Coclico and Its Relationship to Josquin. *Musica Disciplina*, 10, 67–105.
- Meier-Brügger, M. (2013). *Indo-European Linguistics*. Walter de Gruyter.

- Meneghetti, G., & Rossi, B. (2010). An analytical model based on lumped parameters for the dynamic analysis of church bells. *Engineering Structures*, 32(10), 3363–3376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2010.07.010>
- Merchant, H., Grahn, J., Trainor, L., Rohrmeier, M., & Fitch, W. T. (2015). Finding the beat: A neural perspective across humans and non-human primates. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 370(1664), 20140093. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2014.0093>
- Mesoudi, A. (2023). Experimental Studies of Cultural Evolution. In J. J. Tehrani, J. Kendal, & R. L. Kendal (Eds.), *Oxford Handbook of Cultural Evolution* (1st ed., pp. 53–66). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198869252.013.6>
- Milka, A. P. (1982). *Theoretical foundations of functionality in music [Теоретические основы функциональности в музыке]*. Muzyka.
- Montagu, J. (2004). How old is music? *The Galpin Society Journal*, 57(May), 171–182.
- Montagu, J. (2017). How Music and Instruments Began: A Brief Overview of the Origin and Entire Development of Music, from Its Earliest Stages. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 2, 8. <https://doi.org/10/gmnfsc>
- Monteverdi, C. (2011). *Madrigals, Book VIII: Madrigali Guerrieri et Amorosi*. Dover Publications. (Original work published 1638, Alessandro Vincenti)
- Morley, I. (2005). The long-forgotten melody? Music in the Mesolithic. In P. Milner & N. Woodman (Eds.), *Mesolithic Studies at the Beginning of the 21st Century* (Issue 14, pp. 212–224). Oxbow Books. <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:97c80420-0d84-4a0a-b7ff-832f92781c7f>
- Morley, I. (2013). *The Prehistory of Music: Human Evolution, Archaeology, and the Origins of Musicality*. Oxford University Press.
- Musin, Y. (1967). *The Conducting technique [Техника дирижирования]*. Muzyka.
- Nagy, G. (1994). *Pindar's Homer: The Lyric Possession of An Epic Past*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Navarro Tomás, T. (with Internet Archive). (1983). *Métrica española: Reseña histórica y descriptiva*. Labor. http://archive.org/details/metricaespanolar0000nava_c3x6
- Nave-Blodgett, J. E., Snyder, J. S., & Hannon, E. E. (2021). Hierarchical beat perception develops throughout childhood and adolescence and is enhanced in those with musical training. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 150(2), 314–339. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000903>
- Nazaikinsky, Y. V. (1965). *On musical tempo [О музыкальном темпе]*. Muzyka.
- Nazaikinsky, Y. V. (1966). Research on performers' creativity [Исследования исполнительского творчества]. In *Laboratory of musical acoustics [Лаборатория музыкальной акустики]* (pp. 30–39). Muzyka.
- Nazaikinsky, Y. V. (1972). *On psychology of musical perception [О психологии музыкального восприятия]*. Muzyka.
- Nazaikinsky, Y. V. (2013). *Style and genre in music [Стиль и жанр в музыке]*. Tbilisi State Conservatoire.
- Nespor, M., & Vogel, I. (2007). *Prosodic Phonology: With a New Foreword*. Mouton de Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110977790>
- Nettl, B. (1992). *The Radif of Persian Music: Studies of Structure and Cultural Context in the Classical Music of Iran* (2nd ed.). Elephant & Cat.
- Niemi, J. (1998). The genres of the Nenets songs. *Etnomusikologian Vuosikirja*, 10(1), 96–137. <https://doi.org/10/gmnm6>
- Niemi, J. (2009). Evaluating parameters of structural analysis in indigenous Siberian singing. In J. Niemi (Ed.), *Perspectives on the song of the indigenous peoples of Northern Eurasia: Performance, genres, musical syntax, sound* (pp. 88–121). Tampere University Press.
- Nikolayeva, N. N. (with The Institute of Minority Ethnicities of the North of Russian Academy of Sciences). (2006). *Vocal works by M.P. Kulbertinova [Песенное творчество М.П. Кульбертиновой]*. Nauka.
- Nikolsky, A. (2015). Evolution of tonal organization in music mirrors symbolic representation of perceptual reality. Part-1: Prehistoric. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6(1405). <https://doi.org/10/f7wvp8>
- Nikolsky, A. (2016a). Chromaticism in the modern hemiolic mode of the Syrian Orthodox chant: The heritage of the Ancient Greek music. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7. <https://doi.org/10/gmnfz4>
- Nikolsky, A. (2016b). Opposition of folk and palace/temple music in Antiquity: On the origin of art music in light of historical ethnomusicology. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7. <https://doi.org/10/gmnfz6>
- Nikolsky, A. (2019). *Non-communicative Music Grammars of the 20th Century*. 37. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14850543>
- Nikolsky, A. (2020a). “Talking Jew’s Harp” and Its Relation to Vowel Harmony as a Paradigm of Formative Influence of Music on Language. In N. Masataka (Ed.), *The Origins of Language Revisited: Differentiation from Music and the Emergence of Neurodiversity and Autism* (pp. 217–322). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4250-3_8

- Nikolsky, A. (2020b). The pastoral origin of semiotically functional tonal organization of music. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11(June), 1358. <https://doi.org/10/gmnmfx2>
- Nikolsky, A. (2021). The Ancient Greek roots of Mediterranean Tonality and its Hemiolic Typology and their antithesis to Western tonality. *Frontiers in Psychology*, (update), 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.14898837.V2>
- Nikolsky, A., Alekseyev, E. Ye., Alekseev, I. Ye., & Dyakonova, V. E. (2020). The overlooked tradition of ‘personal music’ and its place in the evolution of music. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10(Feb.), 3051. <https://doi.org/10/gmnmfw>
- Nikolsky, A., & Benítez-Burraco, A. (2024). The evolution of human music in light of increased prosocial behavior: A new model. *Physics of Life Reviews*, 51, 114–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plrev.2023.11.016>
- Noorduyn, M. A. (2016). *Beethoven’s tempo indications*. University of Manchester.
- Notopoulos, J. (1956). *Folk Dances of Greece*. Folkways Records & Service Corp. Ethnic Folkways Library. <https://folkways-media.si.edu/docs/folkways/artwork/FW04467.pdf>
- Oller, D. K., Griebel, U., Iyer, S. N., Jhang, Y., Warlaumont, A. S., Dale, R., & Call, J. (2019). Language Origins Viewed in Spontaneous and Interactive Vocal Rates of Human and Bonobo Infants. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 729. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00729>
- Ophuijsen, J. M. V. (1987). *Hephaestion on Metre: A Translation and Commentary*. Brill Academic Pub.
- Ostrovsky, A. L. (1987). *The course of music theory [Курс теории музыки]* (3rd ed.). Muzyka.
- Palazzi, A., Wagner Fritzen, B., & Gauer, G. (2019). Music-induced emotion effects on decision-making. *Psychology of Music*, 47(5), 621–643. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735618779224>
- Palisca, C. V. (1959). A Clarification of “Musica Reservata” in Jean Taisnier’s “Astrologiae,” 1559. *Acta Musicologica*, 31(4), 133–161. <https://doi.org/10/cjnm6f>
- Parncutt, R. (1994). A Perceptual Model of Pulse Saliency and Metrical Accent in Musical Rhythms. *Music Perception*, 11(4), 409–464. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40285633>
- Parpia, S. (2016). Mughal Hunting Grounds: Landscape Manipulation and “Garden” Association. *Garden History*, 44(2), 171–190.
- Parsad, B. (2012). *Arts education in public elementary and secondary schools*. NCES, IES, U.S. Department of Education.
- Patel, A. D. (2014). The Evolutionary Biology of Musical Rhythm: Was Darwin Wrong? *PLoS Biology*, 12(3), e1001821. <https://doi.org/10/gmnmfvn>
- Peponi, A.-E. (2017). Aristotle’s Definition of Dance. In L. Gianvittorio (Ed.), *Choreutika: Performing and theorising dance in Ancient Greece* (pp. 215–243). Fabrizio Serra.
- Peretz, I. (2013). Towards a neurobiology of musical emotions. In P. N. Juslin & J. A. Sloboda (Eds.), *Handbook of Music and Emotion: Theory, Research, Applications* (pp. 99–126). OUP Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199230143.003.0005>
- Perlovsky, L. (2010). Musical emotions: Functions, origins, evolution. *Physics of Life Reviews*, 7(1), 2–27. <https://doi.org/10/ctj42z>
- Persoon, G. A., & Schefold, R. (2017). Frightened by the eagle; Recording songs and music from the Island of Siberut, Mentawai Islands. *Wacana*, 18(3), 581–613. <https://doi.org/10.17510/wacana.v18i3.629>
- Peust, C. (1999). *Egyptian phonology: An introduction to the phonology of a dead language*. Peust & Gutschmidt.
- Pinsky, R. (2000). *The Sounds of Poetry: A Brief Guide*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- Plutarch, Einarson, B., & De Lacy, P. H. (1967). *Moralia. On Music* [Dataset]. Harvard University Press. https://doi.org/10.4159/DLCL.plutarch-moralia_music.1967
- Polak, R. (2010). Rhythmic Feel as Meter: Non-Isochronous Beat Subdivision in Jembe Music from Mali. *Music Theory Online*, 16(4). https://www.mtosmt.org/issues/mto.10.16.4/mto.10.16.4.polak.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Polak, R. (2018). The lower limit for meter in dance drumming from West Africa. *Empirical Musicology Review*, 12(3–4), 205–226. <https://doi.org/10.18061/emr.v12i3-4.4951>
- Polak, R., London, J., & Jacoby, N. (2016). Both Isochronous and Non-Isochronous Metrical Subdivision Afford Precise and Stable Ensemble Entrainment: A Corpus Study of Malian Jembe Drumming. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2016.00285>
- Preminger, A. (2015). *Princeton Encyclopedia of Poetry and Poetics*. Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400872930>
- Price, P. (1983). *Bells and man*. Oxford Univ. Press.
- Provine, R. C. (2001). Korea. Music theory. In S. Sadie & J. Tyrrel (Eds.), *Grove Music Online*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.45812>
- Purser, J. (2024). Hebridean Rowing Songs. *Angles*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.4000/11qj5>
- Quantz, J. J. (2001). *On playing the flute* (E. R. Reilly, Trans.; 2nd ed). Northeastern University Press.

- Quintilianus, A. (1983). *Aristides Quintilianus on Music in Three Books*. Yale University Press.
- Rangacharya, A. (1996). *The Natyasastra: English Translation with Critical Notes*. Munshiram.
- Rault, L., & Brenton, J. (2000). *Musical instruments: Craftsmanship and traditions from prehistory to the present*. Harry N. Abrams.
- Raven, D. S. (with Internet Archive). (1968). *Greek metre: An introduction*. Faber.
<http://archive.org/details/greekmetreintrod0000rave>
- Ravignani, A. (2014). Chorusing, synchrony, and the evolutionary functions of rhythm. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01118>
- Ravignani, A., & Madison, G. (2017). The paradox of isochrony in the evolution of human rhythm. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8(NOV), 1820. <https://doi.org/10/gcj73j>
- Ravignani, A., Thompson, B., Grossi, T., Delgado, T., & Kirby, S. (2018). Evolving building blocks of rhythm: How human cognition creates music via cultural transmission. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1423(1), 176–187. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.13610>
- Rector, M. (2021). Historical Trends in Expressive Timing Strategies: Chopin’s Etude, Op. 25 no. 1. *Empirical Musicology Review*, 15(3–4), 176–201. <https://doi.org/10.18061/emr.v15i3-4.7338>
- Repetto, R. C., & Serra, X. (2016). *Melodic transformation processes in the arrangements of jingju banshi*. Fourth International Conference On Analytical Approaches To World Music.
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Melodic-transformation-processes-in-the-of-jingju-Repetto-Serra/744c846790d38a214ab8f9b4fb933397e4e5526e>
- Repp, B. H. (1990). Patterns of expressive timing in performances of a Beethoven minuet by nineteen famous pianists. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 88(2), 622–641. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.399766>
- Repp, B. H. (1995). Quantitative Effects of Global Tempo on Expressive Timing in Music Performance: Some Perceptual Evidence. *Music Perception*, 13(1), 39–57. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40285684>
- Repp, B. H. (1998a). A microcosm of musical expression. I. Quantitative analysis of pianists’ timing in the initial measures of Chopin’s Etude in E major. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 104(2 Pt 1), 1085–1100. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.423325>
- Repp, B. H. (1998b). Obligatory “expectations” of expressive timing induced by perception of musical structure. *Psychological Research*, 61(1), 33–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004260050011>
- Repp, B. H. (1999a). A microcosm of musical expression. III. Contributions of timing and dynamics to the aesthetic impression of pianists’ performances of the initial measures of Chopin’s Etude in E major. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 106(1), 469–478. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.427078>
- Repp, B. H. (1999b). Control of Expressive and Metronomic Timing in Pianists. *Journal of Motor Behavior*, 31(2), 145–164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222899909600985>
- Repp, B. H. (2005). Sensorimotor synchronization: A review of the tapping literature. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 12(6), 969–992. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03206433>
- Repp, B. H., & Bruttomesso, M. (2009). A filled duration illusion in music: Effects of metrical subdivision on the perception and production of beat tempo. *Advances in Cognitive Psychology*, 5(1), 114–134.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/v10053-008-0071-7>
- Repp, B. H., & Su, Y.-H. (2013). Sensorimotor synchronization: A review of recent research (2006–2012). *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 20(3), 403–452. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-012-0371-2>
- Reybrouck, M., & Eerola, T. (2017). Music and Its Inductive Power: A Psychobiological and Evolutionary Approach to Musical Emotions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00494>
- Richter, L. (1998). Antike Überlieferungen in der byzantinischen Musiktheorie. *Acta Musicologica*, 70(2), 133.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/932707>
- Roesner, E. H. (1990). The Emergence of Musica mensurabilis. In J. LaRue (Ed.), *Studies in Musical Sources and Style: Essays in Honor of Jan LaRue* (pp. 41–74). A-R Editions.
- Roesner, E. H. (Ed.). (2009). *Ars antiqua: Organum, Conductus, Motet*. Routledge.
- Roger, M., & Aubert, S. (1999, May 10). Autorotation and the theory of bullroarer sound. *5th AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference and Exhibit*. 5th AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference and Exhibit. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.1999-1827>
- Rombouts, L. (2014). *Singing Bronze: A History of Carillon Music*. Leuven University Press.
- Rosenblum, S. P. (2007a). *Performance Practices in Classic Piano Music: Their Principles and Applications*. Indiana University Press.
- Rosenblum, S. P. (2007b). *Performance Practices in Classic Piano Music: Their Principles and Applications*. Indiana University Press.

- Rothchild, F. (1979). *The Lost Tradition in Music: Rhythm and Tempo in J. S. Bach's Time*. Hyperion Pr.
- Rothstein, W. N. (1989). *Phrase rhythm in tonal music*. Schirmer Books.
- Rousseau, J.-J. (with University of Toronto). (1767). *Dictionnaire de musique* (G. de Lamoignon, Ed.). Chez la veuve Duchesne. <http://archive.org/details/dictionnairedem00rous>
- Rowell, L. (1979). Aristoxenus on Rhythm. *Journal of Music Theory*, 23(1), 63–79. <https://doi.org/10.2307/843694>
- Rowell, L. (2015). *Music and Musical Thought in Early India*. University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/M/bo3612674.html>
- Rozhdestvensky, G. (1974). *Conductor's fingering [Дирижёрская аппликатура]*. Музыка.
- Rudneva, A. (1994). *Russian traditional musical works: Essays on the theory of folklore [Русское народное музыкальное творчество: Очерки по теории фольклора]*. Композитор.
- Rudolf, M. (1980). *The Grammar of Conducting: A Practical Guide to Baton Technique and Orchestral Interpretation*. Macmillan USA.
- Sachs, C. (1940). *The History of Musical Instruments*. Dover Publications.
- Sachs, C. (1953). *Rhythm and Tempo: A Study in Music History*. Norton.
- Sachs, C. (1965). *World History of the Dance*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Sakhaltuyeva, O. Ye., & Nazaikinsky, Y. V. (1970). On the connection between the expressive means in musical performance [О взаимосвязях выразительных средств в музыкальном исполнении]. In Y. V. Nazaikinsky (Ed.), *Musical art and science [Музыкальное искусство и наука]* (Vol. 1, pp. 59–95). Музыка.
- Salali, G. D. (2017). *Social Structure and Knowledge Sharing Networks in Hunter-gatherers: A Case Study on the Plant Knowledge of the Mbendjele BaYaka Pygmies*. University College London.
- Sanders, E. H. (1980). Consonance and Rhythm in the Organum of the 12th and 13th Centuries. *Journal of the American Musicological Society*, 33(2), 264–286. <https://doi.org/10.2307/831113>
- Sárosi, B. (1986). *Folk music: Hungarian musical idiom* (M. Steiner, Trans.). Corvina.
- Sasaki, S. (2015). The Hunting Techniques and Equipment of the Peoples of Siberia and the Russian Far East. In O. A. Shaglanova & S. Sasaki (Eds.), *The Cultural Heritage of Buryats, Evenks and Semeyskiye. Material and Religious Articles From the Collections of the Ethnographic Museum of Transbaikalian Peoples* (pp. 101–111). Senri Ethnological Reports.
- Saulnier, D. (2017). *Gregorian Chant: A Guide to the History and Liturgy* (4th ed.). Paraclete Press.
- Schachter, C. E. (1977). Diversity and the Decline of Literacy in Music Theory. *College Music Symposium*, 17(1), 150–153. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40373870>
- Schlatter, G. (1985). *Bumerang und Schwirrholz: Eine Einführung in die traditionelle Kultur australischer Aborigines*. Reimer.
- Sclafani, V., De Pascalis, L., Bozicevic, L., Sepe, A., Ferrari, P. F., & Murray, L. (2023). Similarities and differences in the functional architecture of mother- infant communication in rhesus macaque and British mother-infant dyads. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 13164. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39623-3>
- Sheikin, Y. I. (1983). Proto-singing and singing in the Udege folklore [Допесенное и песенное в фольклоре удэ]. In V. Gusev, I. V. Matsiyevsky, & I. Zemtsovsky (Eds.), *Folk song. Problems of studying [Народная песня. Проблемы изучения]* (pp. 79–93). State Institute of Theater, Music and Cinema.
- Sheikin, Y. I. (1996). *Musical culture of peoples of Northern Asia [Музыкальная культура народов Северной Азии]*. Yakutskii scientific center.
- Sheikin, Y. I. (2002). *The history of music culture of Siberian ethnicities: A comparative historical investigation [История музыкальной культуры народов Сибири: Сравнительно-историческое исследование]*. Eastern Literature, Russian Academy of Science.
- Sheikin, Y. I. (2018). *Musical culture of the Chukchi [Музыкальная культура чукчей]* (O. E. Dobzhanskaya & T. Ignatyeva, Eds.). Nauka.
- Shelemay, K. K., Jeffery, P., & Monson, I. (1993). Oral and Written Transmission in Ethiopian Christian Chant. *Early Music History*, 12, 55–117. <https://doi.org/10/b4xfjf>
- Shepard, R. N. (2010). One cognitive psychologist's quest for the structural grounds of music cognition. *Empirical Musicology Review*, 20(1–2), 130–157. <https://doi.org/10.5084/pmmb2009/20/130>
- Shumaker, R. W., Walkup, K. R., & Beck, B. B. (2011). *Animal tool behavior: The use and manufacture of tools by animals* (Revised and updated ed). Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Singer, A. (1974). The Metrical Structure of Macedonian Dance. *Ethnomusicology*, 18(3), 379–404. <https://doi.org/10.2307/850520>
- Singer, N., Jacoby, N., Hendler, T., & Granot, R. (2023). Feeling the Beat: Temporal Predictability is Associated with Ongoing Changes in Music-Induced Pleasantness. *Journal of Cognition*, 6(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.5334/joc.286>

- Sioros, G., Miron, M., Davies, M., Gouyon, F., & Madison, G. (2014). Syncopation creates the sensation of groove in synthesized music examples. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01036>
- Sipos, J. (2001). *Karachay-Balkar Folksongs*. Akadémiai Kiadó.
- Sivan, D. (2001). *A grammar of the Ugaritic language* (2nd ed.). Brill. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789047427216>
- Skoulios, M. (2012). Modern theory and notation of Byzantine chanting tradition: A Near-Eastern musicological perspective. *NEMO Online*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5634143>
- Smith, J. D. (1997). The place of musical novices in music science. *Music Perception*, 14(3), 227–262. <https://doi.org/10/gmnfrr>
- Snyder, J. S., Gordon, R. L., & Hannon, E. E. (2024). Theoretical and empirical advances in understanding musical rhythm, beat and metre. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 3(7), 449–462. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-024-00315-y>
- Sodnom, B. (1976). From the history of Mongol songs [Из истории монгольских песен]. In S. Galsan (Ed.), *Works of Mongol philologists: 1960-1975 [Труды Монгольских Филологов: 1960-1975]* (pp. 135–198). Mongolian Academy of Sciences.
- Sokhor, A. (1968). *The aesthetic nature of genre in music [Эстетическая природа жанра в музыке]*. Музыка.
- Sokhor, A. (1971). Theory of musical genres: Problems and prospects [Теория музыкальных жанров. Задачи и перспективы]. In L. Rappoport (Ed.), *Theoretical problems of musical forms and genres. Collection of essays [Теоретические проблемы музыкальных форм и жанров]* (pp. 292–310). Музыка.
- Spitzer, J., Botstein, L., Barber, C., & Westrup, J. (2001). Conducting. In S. Sadie & J. Tyrrell (Eds.), *Grove Music Online*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.06266>
- Sterckx, R. (2000). Transforming the Beasts: Animals and Music in Early China. *T'oung Pao*, 86(1/3), 1–46. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4528831>
- Stetson, R. H. (1905). A motor theory of rhythm and discrete succession: II. *Psychological Review*, 12(5), 293–350. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0074322>
- Stone, R. M. (1985). In Search of Time in African Music. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 7, 139–148. <https://doi.org/10.2307/745884>
- Stupacher, J., Hove, M. J., Novembre, G., Schütz-Bosbach, S., & Keller, P. E. (2013). Musical groove modulates motor cortex excitability: A TMS investigation. *Brain and Cognition*, 82(2), 127–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2013.03.003>
- Sulzer, J. G. (2013). *Allgemeine Theorie Der Schönen Künste*. Nabu Press. (Original work published 1771, Bey M.G. Weidemanns Erben und Reich)
- Swager, B. (1993). *A History of the Carillon: Its Origins, Development, and Evolution as a Musical Instrument* [Music Department]. Indiana University.
- Takahashi, D. Y., Liao, D. A., & Ghazanfar, A. A. (2017). Vocal Learning via Social Reinforcement by Infant Marmoset Monkeys. *Current Biology*, 27(12), 1844–1852.e6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2017.05.004>
- Tarasova, I. A. (2021). “Genre”: A nomadic concept or an aesthetic universal? *International Journal “Speech Genres,”* 32(4), 252–258. <https://doi.org/10.18500/2311-0740-2021-4-32-252-258>
- Tarlekar, G. H. (with Internet Archive). (1991). *Studies in the Nāṭyaśāstra: With special reference to the Sanskrit drama in performance*. Delhi : Motilal Banarsidass. <http://archive.org/details/studiesinnatyasa0000tarl>
- Taruskin, R. (2009). *Music from the Earliest Notations to the Sixteenth Century: The Oxford History of Western Music*. Oxford University Press.
- Tatarintsev, B. I. (1998). *Tuvan throat singing. Problems of genesis [Тувинское горловое пение. Проблемы происхождения.]*. Tuvan Book Publishers.
- Temperley, D. (2004). *The Cognition of Basic Musical Structures*. The MIT Press.
- Temperley, D. (2008). Hypermetrical Transitions. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 30(2), 305–325. <https://doi.org/10/chv5hh>
- Temperley, D. (2021). The origins of syncopation in American popular music. *Popular Music*, 40(1), 18–41. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261143021000283>
- Temperley, N., & Temperley, D. (2011). Music-Language Correlations and the “Scotch Snap.” *Music Perception*, 29(1), 51–63. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2011.29.1.51>
- Tibbett, K. (2005). *Community specialisation, standardisation and exchange in a hunter-gatherer society: A case study from Kalkadoon country, northwest Queensland, Australia* [James Cook University]. <https://doi.org/10.25903/J80W-ST32>
- Todd, N. P. M., Cousins, R., & Lee, C. S. (2007). The Contribution of Anthropometric Factors to Individual Differences in the Perception of Rhythm. *Empirical Musicology Review*, 2(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.18061/1811/24478>
- Todd, N. P. M., & Lee, C. S. (2015). The sensory-motor theory of rhythm and beat induction 20 years on: A new synthesis and future perspectives. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 9, 444. <https://doi.org/10/gmnfjq>

- Touma, H. H. (1996). *The Music of the Arabs*. Amadeus Press.
- Toussaint, G. T. (2020). *The Geometry of Musical Rhythm: What Makes a “Good” Rhythm Good?, Second Edition*. Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Trehub, S. E. (2003). The developmental origins of musicality. *Nature Neuroscience*, 6(7), 669–673. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn1084>
- Treitler, L. (1984). Reading and Singing: On the Genesis of Occidental Music-Writing. *Early Music History*, 4, 135–208.
- Troelsgard, C. (1988). Ancient Musical Theory in Byzantine Environments. *Cahiers de l’Institut Du Moyen-Âge Grec Et Latin*, 56, 228–238.
- Trost, W., Frühholz, S., Schön, D., Labbé, C., Pichon, S., Grandjean, D., & Vuilleumier, P. (2014). Getting the beat: Entrainment of brain activity by musical rhythm and pleasantness. *NeuroImage*, 103, 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2014.09.009>
- Tsukkerman, V. (1964). *Musical genres and the foundation of music forms [Музыкальные жанры и основы музыкальных форм]*. Музыка.
- Tzonev, B. (1955). *A textbook on Bulgarian folk hora and rachenitsa [Учебник по български народни хора и ръченици]*. Science and Art [Наука и Изкуство].
- Uptis, R. (1987). Children’s understanding of rhythm: The relationship between development and music training. *Psychomusicology: A Journal of Research in Music Cognition*, 7(1), 41–60. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0094187>
- Van Kampen, D. (2022). The Rhythm of Gregorian Chant: An Analysis and an Empirical Investigation. *Journal of Music Research Online*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.20851/n442j159>
- VanderStel, J., & Temperley, D. (2022). The evolution of syncopation in twentieth-century American popular music. *Journal of New Music Research*, 51(2–3), 162–185. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2023.2223583>
- Velcheva, L. (2007). *Musical metrorythm [Музыкалният метроритъм]*. University Edition “St. Kliment Okhridsky.”
- Vensten-Tagrina, Z. V. (2008). *The phenomenon of personal song in the traditional Chukchi culture [Феномен личной песни в традиционной культуре чукчей]*. State Russian pedagogical university named after Gertsen.
- Vertkov, K., Blagodatov, G., & Yazovitskaya, E. (1963). *The atlas of musical instruments of the USSR peoples [Атлас музыкальных инструментов народов СССР]*. Muzgiz.
- Vieillard, S., Roy, M., & Peretz, I. (2012). Expressiveness in musical emotions. *Psychological Research*, 76(5), 641–653. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-011-0361-4>
- Vinogradov, V. S. (1984). *Music of the people of Asia and Africa [Музыка народов Азии и Африки]* (Vol. 4). Soviet Composer.
- Vladyshevskaya, T. V. (2006). *Musical Culture of Ancient Russia [Музыкальная культура Древней Руси]*. Znack.
- Vollaerts, J. W. A. (1960). *Rhythmic Proportions in Early Medieval Ecclesiastical Chant*. E. J. Brill.
- Waite, W. G. (1954). *The Rhythm of Twelfth-century Polyphony: Its Theory and Practice*. Yale University Press.
- Wang, A. (2023). Philosophizing Time in Sinitic Opera. *Music Theory Online*, 29(3). https://mtosmt.org/issues/mto.23.29.3/mto.23.29.3.yuwang.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Wang, B. (2025). Poetic Prosody and Musical Rhythm in Chinese Art Song: A Comparative Study of Text–Music Alignment. *CINEFORUM*, 65(3), 665–674.
- Warren, R. M., Gardner, D. A., Brubaker, B. S., & Bashford, J. A. (1991). Melodic and Nonmelodic Sequences of Tones: Effects of Duration on Perception. *Music Perception*, 8(3), 277–289. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40285503>
- Wegdell, F., Fryns, C., Schick, J., Nellissen, L., Laporte, M., Surbeck, M., Van Noordwijk, M. A., Masi, S., Hellwig, B., Willems, E. P., Zuberbühler, K., Van Schaik, C. P., Stoll, S., & Townsend, S. W. (2025). The evolution of infant-directed communication: Comparing vocal input across all great apes. *Science Advances*, 11(26), eadt7718. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adt7718>
- Wellesz, E. (1961). *A History of Byzantine Music and Hymnography*. Clarendon Press.
- Werner, H. (1923). *Die Ursprünge der Lyrik: Eine entwicklungspsychologische Untersuchung*. E. Reinhardt.
- West, M. L. (1981). The Singing of Homer and the Modes of Early Greek Music. *The Journal of Hellenic Studies*, 101, 113–129. <https://doi.org/10/dmwpnn>
- West, M. L. (1982). The Metre of Arius’ “Thalia.” *The Journal of Theological Studies*, 33(1), 98–105.
- West, M. L. (1992). *Ancient Greek music*. Oxford University Press.
- West, M. L. (1994). The Babylonian musical notation and the Hurrian melodic texts. *Music and Letters*, 75(2), 161–179. <https://doi.org/10/fb8jwk>
- West, M. L. (1997). Akkadian Poetry: Metre and Performance. *Iraq*, 59, 175. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4200442>
- West, M. L. (2003). *The east face of Helicon: West Asiatic elements in Greek poetry and myth* (Reprinted). Clarendon Press.
- West, M. L. (2013). *Greek metre* (2nd ed.). Clarendon Press.

- Westergaard, P. (1975). *An introduction to tonal theory*. Norton.
- Whitham, J. C., Gerald, M. S., & Maestriperi, D. (2007). Intended Receivers and Functional Significance of Grunt and Gurney Vocalizations in Free-Ranging Female Rhesus Macaques. *Ethology*, 113(9), 862–874. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0310.2007.01381.x>
- Wichmann, E. (1991). *Listening to Theatre: The Aural Dimension of Beijing Opera*. University of Hawaii Press.
- Widdess, R., & Wolpert, R. F. (1981). Aspects of form in North Indian alap and dhrupad. In *Music and Tradition: Essays on Asian and Other Musics Presented to Laurence Picken* (pp. 143–182). Cambridge University Press.
- Will, U., Clayton, M., Wertheim, I., Leante, L., & Berg, E. (2015). Pulse and Entrainment to Non-Isochronous Auditory Stimuli: The Case of North Indian Alap. *PLOS ONE*, 10(4), e0123247. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0123247>
- Williams, E. V. (1985). *The Bells of Russia: History and Technology*. Princeton University Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt7zvp84>
- Witek, M. A. G., Clarke, E. F., Wallentin, M., Kringelbach, M. L., & Vuust, P. (2014). Syncopation, Body-Movement and Pleasure in Groove Music. *PLOS ONE*, 9(4), e94446. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0094446>
- Wöllner, C., & Hammerschmidt, D. (2021). Tapping to hip-hop: Effects of cognitive load, arousal, and musical meter on time experiences. *Attention, Perception & Psychophysics*, 83(4), 1552–1561. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-020-02227-4>
- Woodhouse, J., Rene, J. C., Hall, C. S., Smith, L. T. W., King, F. H., & McClenahan, J. W. (2012). The Dynamics of a Ringing Church Bell. *Advances in Acoustics and Vibration*, 2012, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/681787>
- Wright, O. (1969). *The Modal System of Arab and Persian Music, 1250-1300: An Interpretation of Contemporary Texts*. University of London.
- Yamaya, H. (1998). *Classification and Analysis of Rhythm and Harmony in Flamenco Guitar*. University of California, Santa Cruz.
- Yang, J. (2022). Viennese Style in Viennese Waltzes: An Empirical Study of Timing in the Recordings of The Blue Danube. *Musicologica Austriaca: Journal for Austrian Music Studies*, (2022). <https://www.musau.org//parts/neue-article-page/view/135>
- Yesipova, M. V. (2008). Phono-instruments (Ethnophones). In M. V. Yesipova, O. V. Frayonova, & Y. I. Nekliudov (Eds.), *Musical Instruments: Encyclopedia [Музыкальные инструменты: Энциклопедия]* (p. 786). DeKa-VS.
- Yeston, M. (1976). *The Stratification of Musical Rhythm*. Yale University Press.
- Yevdokimova, Y. K. (1983). *History of Polyphony. Polyphony of the middle Ages: 10-15th centuries [История полифонии. Многоголосие средневековья: X-XIV века]* (Vol. 1). Muzyka.
- Zannos, I. (1990). Intonation in theory and practice of Greek and Turkish music. *Yearbook for Traditional Music*, 22(1990), 42–59. <https://doi.org/10/cd2hst>
- Zannos, I. (1994). *Ichos und Makam: Vergleichende Untersuchungen zum Tonsystem der griechisch-orthodoxen Kirchenmusik und der türkischen Kunstmusik*. Orpheus-Verlag. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Ichos-und-Makam-%3A-Vergleichende-Untersuchungen-zum-Zannos/8fcfeb1cda5824c28d4150ea0de6f2f90f6c7219>
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1967). *Russian “drawn-out” songs: Research experience [Русская протяжная песня: Опыт исследования]*. Muzyka.
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1974). Semasiology of Musical Folklore (Methodological Premises) [Семасиология музыкального фольклора (методологические предпосылки)]. In M. Aranovsky (Ed.), *Problems of Musical Thinking [Проблемы музыкального мышления]* (pp. 177–207). Muzyka.
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1975). *The Melodics of Calendar Songs [Мелодика календарных песен]*. Muzyka.
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1983). Song as a historical phenomenon [Песня как исторический феномен]. In V. Gusev (Ed.), *Popular song: Problems of study [Народная песня. Проблемы изучения]* (Vol. 6, pp. 22–35). State Academy of Theatrical Arts.
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1985). Towards the theory of genre in folk music [К теории жанра в фольклоре]. In V. Voigt (Ed.), *Artes populares*. (Vol. 14, pp. 21–42). Eötvös Loránd Tudományegyetem Folklore Tanszékének évkönyve.
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1987a). Musical instrument and musical cognition (on presentation of a problem) [Музыкальный инструмент и музыкальное мышление (к постановке вопроса)]. In I. V. Matsiyevskii (Ed.), *Folk musical instruments and instrumental music [Народные музыкальные инструменты и инструментальная музыка]* (Vol. 1, pp. 125–131). Soviet Composer.
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1987b). On melodic formula in Russian folklore [О мелодической “формульности” в русском фольклоре]. In V. Yeremina (Ed.), *Ethnographic origins of folkloric phenomena: Russian folklore [Этнографические истоки фольклорных явлений. Русский фольклор]* (Vol. 14, pp. 117–128). Nauka.

- Zemtsovsky, I. (1987c). *Tracing Vesnyanka from Tchaikovsky's Piano Concerto: Historical morphology of a folk song [По следам веснянки из фортепианного концерта П. Чайковского]*. *Музыка*.
- Zemtsovsky, I. (1997). An Attempt at a Synthetic Paradigm. *Ethnomusicology*, 41(2), 185–205. <https://doi.org/10/b4gsb4>
- Zemtsovsky, I. (2002). The Apologia of Text [Апология текста]. *Musical Academy [Музыкальная Академия]*, 4(683), 100–110.
- Zhang, H., & Song, C. (2013). Some Issues in the Study of Chinese Poetic Prosody. *Language and Linguistics, Breaking down the Barriers: Interdisciplinary Studies in Chinese Linguistics and Beyond*, 1149–1171.
- Zhornitskaya, M. (1983). *Folk choreographic art of the indigenous population of North-Eastern Siberia [Народное хореографическое искусство коренного населения Северо-Востока Сибири]*. Nauka.
- Zhou, L., Yang, Y., & Li, S. (2022). Music-induced emotions influence intertemporal decision making. *Cognition and Emotion*, 36(2), 211–229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699931.2021.1995331>